

H2020 DAEMON Project
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Deliverable 5.2

Report on evaluation results and initial proof-of-concept demonstrations

Abstract

D5.2 is the second deliverable of DAEMON's WP5, which builds on D5.1. Our goal within this WP is to focus on validation activities, performance evaluations and functional assessment tests of all the NI-solutions that we have been developing to date. This deliverable presents the result of DAEMON's efforts of validating the research activities we have been conducting within the project's WP3 and WP4, which we have presented in D3.2 and D4.2. The performance evaluation aims at meeting 9 target KPIs in well-defined scenarios, which we measured and assessed by developing 8 *evaluations*. Each evaluation relies on a set of technical tools, employed to perform 30 *experimental activities*, covering all 8 NI functionalities we propose in WP2. Finally, we discuss the demonstrations that we have already presented for four proof of concepts corresponding to four evaluations (E1, E2, E3 and E4). Furthermore, we put forward our plan for five additional demonstrations of the proof of concepts corresponding to five NI functionality evaluations (E1, E2, E3, E4 and E8), and a demo of integrated NI solutions in the DAEMON NI architecture.

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List of Acronyms

4G – Fourth Generation
5G – Fifth Generation
5GC – 5G Core
AI – Artificial Intelligence
AMF – Access and Mobility management Function
BBDev – Intel DPDK's Wireless Baseband Device Library
BS – Base Station
C-EF – Coordinated Energy-efficient First
CPaaS – Cloud communication Platforms as a Service
CUPS – Control-User Plane Separation and 4G Evolved Packet Core (EPC)
C-MWT – Coordinated MWT
C-R-EF – Coordinated Radio- controlling Energy-efficient First
DL – Downlink
DMARL – Distributed multi-agent RL
DU – 5G Distributed Unit
EC – Energy Consumption
EPC – 4G Evolved Packet Core
FFNN – feed-forward neural network
FL – Federated Learning
GMNO – Global Mobile Network Operator
GRC – GNU Radio Companion
IoT – Internet of Things
KNN – K-Nearest Neighbor
LSTM – long short term memory
MANO – Management and Orchestration
MCU – Microcontroller Unit
MME – Mobility Management Entity
MNA – Mobile Network Aggregators
MNO – Mobile Network Operator
MSE – Mean Squared Error
MTS – Mixed Time Scale
MVNO – Mobile Virtual Network Operator
NO – Network Operator
OLR – Online Learning for Reservations
OSM – Open-Source MANO
O-MWT – O-RAN Minimum Waiting Time
PCB – Printed Circuit Board
PI – Proportional Integral
PLT – Page Load Time
PoC – Proof of Concept
PPO – Proximal Policy Optimization
RCS – Radar Cross Section
RIS – Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RL – Reinforcement Learning
RSU – Roadside Unit
SDR – Software-Defined Radio
SLA – Service Level Agreement
SB3 – Stable-Baselines3
SMF – Session Management Function
SP – Service Provider
SO – Service Orchestration
TB – Threshold-based method
TRL – Technology Readiness Level
TDR – Time Domain Reflectometry
UPF – User Plane Function
V2X – Vehicle-to-everything
vBS – virtualized Base Station
VNA – Vector Network Analyzer
VNF – Virtual Network Function
WP – Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable presents updates on DAEMON's evaluation results for the NI-solutions we have developed in WP3 and WP4, targeting 8 functionalities assisted via NI.

Specifically, WP5 receives the activities that correspond to these functionalities (from WP3 and WP4) and aims to validate them by ultimately collecting the target KPIs we set for the NI solutions. Our evaluation methodology relies on a set of tools that includes experimental testbeds, simulators or emulators, which are possibly fed with measurement data. Furthermore, WP5 is responsible of the implementation of the solutions from WP3 and WP4 into such experimental, simulation or emulation systems. Finally, WP5 provides feedback to WP2, WP3 and WP4 concerning the efficiency of both the design and the operation of the NI solutions developed within the project.

In this document, we present an update on the results of WP5 activities. We report on the performance of the NI functionalities we developed in the project to date, as well as the executed and planned demonstrations for the proof-of-concepts corresponding to the different evaluations. The document consists of six sections.

In Section 1, we describe the structure of our performance evaluation methodology. We introduce the target KPIs defined to validate the NI-solutions, the evaluation methodology to measure such KPIs, and the tools exploited to perform tests in the different experimental activities.

In Section 2, we detail the 9 target KPIs to assess the performance, reliability and sustainability of these NI-solutions. We also describe 7 evaluations planned designed to prove the validity of the proposed techniques in realistic experimental or measurement data-driven settings.

In Section 3, we illustrate the complete set of technical tools employed during the performance tests, which we categorized into experimental testbeds, simulators and emulators, and datasets.

In Section 4, we show the results of 30 experimental activities carried on by the consortium, each targeting specific KPIs within their assigned evaluations. Each activity collects a set of KPIs via proof-of-concept evaluations, which are either experimental-driven or data-driven. We mention that two activities also performed a pilot with industrial partners.

In Section 5, we discuss the proof of concept demonstrations that we have already executed as well as the ones we plan for the different NI functionalities evaluations. With this effort, we highlight the technical readiness level of the NI functionalities that we implement.

In section 6, we provide some conclusions and a final outlook of the document.

1 Introduction

Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2) reports the progress we have made within WP5 towards validating, testing and assessing the performance of the Network Intelligence (NI) solutions we have been developing within WP3 and WP4 of DAEMON. Given the NI solutions we have presented in D3.2 [1] and D4.2 [2], in this report we focus on performing a comprehensive assessment of the DAEMON solutions towards evaluating our set of target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In this effort, we leverage diverse tools for each functionality, including experimental testbeds, simulators and emulators, or impressive amounts of network data.

Table 1. List of performed evaluations to date, with the associated activities, tools and target KPIs.

Evaluation	Short description of the evaluation	Planned KPIs	PoC/Pilot Means (Tools used)	Activities	NI Func. (WP2)	PoC/Pilot Demo Activity
E1	NI for sustainable virtualized Radio Access Network (RAN)	K1, K2, K4, K5, K9, K3, K8	Experimental-driven (T1, S2)	A1, A2, A3, A24, A29	F4	Executed Demo: A1 Planned Demo: A2
E2	NI for VNF placement and control	K1, K2, K3, K8, K4, K5, K9, K7	Experimental and data-driven (T5, T8, D10)	A4, A5, A6, A7, A8, A30	F5	Executed Demo: A4 Planned Demo: A7
E3+E5	NI for real-time anomaly detection	K3, K7, K4, K5, K8	Experimental and data-driven (T8, D3, D8)	A9, A19, A25,	F8	Executed Demo: A9 Planned (Pilot) Demo: A19
E4	NI for Edge orchestration	K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K8, K9, K7	Experimental-and data-driven (D1, D5, D6, D9, T4, S4, S1)	A10, A11, A12, A13, A14, A15, A16, A17, A26	F2	Executed Demo: A11 Executed Pilot: A13
E6	NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning	K2, K4, K9, K5, K6	Data-driven (D3, D9)	A20, A21, A22, A27	F6, F7	Planned PoC: A20, A21, A22
E7	NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	K2, K4, K9, K5, K6	Experimental-driven (T9)	A23	F1	Planned PoC: A23
E8	NI for in-backhaul learning	K3	Experimental and data-driven (D7, D11, D12, T12)	A18, A28	F3	Planned Demo: A18

The solutions we have been developing within WP3 and WP4 target 8 key NI-assisted network functionalities. Such functionalities are distributed across different micro-domains of the next-generation mobile architecture (namely, Core, Transport, Edge, Far Edge, and Beyond Edge), and across controllers, orchestrators and functions that operate at different timescales. They are listed as follows.

- F1: Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) control ;
- F2: Multi-timescale edge resource management;
- F3: In-backhaul support for service intelligence;
- F4: Compute-aware radio scheduling;
- F5: Energy-aware Virtual Network Function (VNF) orchestration;
- F6: Self-learning Management and Orchestration (MANO);
- F7: Capacity forecasting; and
- F8: Automated anomaly response.

In this deliverable, we report our progress in terms of results of the evaluations we performed across these 8 NI-assisted functionalities, compared to the progress we previously reported in deliverable D5.1 [3]. We

develop a set of **8 different evaluations** that aim to measure the KPIs we have identified in order to capture the performance, reliability and sustainability of the NI solutions DAEMON has proposed so far. Different from D5.1 [3], in this report **we integrate an additional evaluation (Evaluation 8), which focuses on NI solutions for in-backhaul learning**. We also group together the activities corresponding to the two evaluations related to anomaly detection, namely **Evaluation 3** and **Evaluation 5**, and report our progress for these two at the same time (**E3 + E5**). We chose this for simplification in terms of reporting, given that both evaluations validate tailored NI solutions for anomaly detection. All the evaluations are summarized in Table 1. Note that they represent two evaluations more than the six targeted in the Description of Action, which shows our commitment to assessing the technologies designed within DAEMON. We offer a detailed view of our evaluations in Section 2.2.

By definition, each evaluation effort leverages a set of existing tools described in Section 3 (experimental testbeds, simulators and emulators, or datasets) to run a **proof of concept (PoC)** for the capability of the NI solution to achieve the KPIs that each NI functionality targets. In other words, the PoC's goal is to show the feasibility of the NI functionality we integrate within the DAEMON architecture. In some cases, we evolve these PoCs into **pilots** (specifically, for activities A13 of E2 and A19 of E3), which we define as evaluation efforts that we perform in collaboration with industrial partners that might benefit from deploying the NI functionality.

We structure the 8 evaluation efforts in separate sub-activities that correspond to the specific NI solutions we designed in WP3 and WP4, and that address all the 8 different network functionalities. In Table 1, we provide an overview of the current ongoing **30 activities**, how they map to the corresponding network functionality, and which KPIs they target. **Our goal with every PoC/pilot is to gauge how close we are to our clear target for the different KPIs that DAEMON identified.** We detail in Section 2.1 these KPIs, their associated targets, and our progress toward achieving them. Furthermore, for each activity, we also justify in Section 4 how we are collecting the corresponding KPIs as part of the corresponding (experimental-driven or data-driven) PoC/pilot. We provide in Figure 1 an overall view of the total set of activities within DAEMON, and we show which micro-domain their evaluation tackles within the next-generation architecture, as well as the corresponding KPI group they tackle. We detail the results of each activity in Section 4.

Figure 1. Positioning of Evaluation activities per NI functionality and architecture micro-domain. We show for each Evaluation per micro-domain the corresponding activities and the KPIs that they aim to address.

One important addition in this document (compared to the previous reported status in D5.1) is the description of the demonstration activities that we are preparing for each evaluation. The demonstrations correspond to a subset of the PoC/pilots that we perform for each evaluation category. We highlight the fact that we have already presented three such demonstrations of PoC efforts, corresponding to four different evaluations (namely, E1, E3, E4 and E5).

We summarize our efforts toward presenting activity-based demonstrations of the PoC/pilot evaluations in Table 1. We further detail in Section 5 the planned demo activities for additional PoCs/pilots, thus showcasing the different evaluations of the NI functionalities. Furthermore, we not only demonstrate evaluation activities in isolation but also propose a demo for the NI architecture that DAEMON proposes.

In the remainder of this document, we provide updates on the KPIs, evaluation, tools, activities, and demonstration efforts, as follows:

- [Section 2](#) gives an update on the status of collecting the target KPIs set for the NI solutions we have been developing in the project and the different evaluations to validate such solutions.
- [Section 3](#) lists the tools that we employed to implement the evaluations above and how we proceeded to implement the proof of concept for the NI solutions in realistic experimental or data-driven settings.
- [Section 4](#) provides an update on the results of the evaluations we carried out to date in DAEMON and how we have collected (or plan to collect) the target KPIs via each activity within an evaluation.
- [Section 5](#) discusses the executed and planned demonstrations for some of the proof of concepts we presented in Section 4.

2 Target KPIs and evaluations

The ambitious vision and objectives of DAEMON call for a credible and solid validation and performance evaluation of the eight NI-assisted functionalities introduced in WP3 and WP4 to improve B5G networks' performance, sustainability and reliability. To date, we developed preliminary NI solutions, which:

- **Increase network performance and efficiency (DAEMON Objective 2.1)** by supporting network functionalities that allow for extremely fast and adaptive control of (i) RIS in a new Beyond Edge domain, (ii) computational resources in the Edge domain, and (iii) support for service intelligence in the user plane of the Transport domain.
- **Enable the sustainable operation of B5G systems (DAEMON Objective 2.2)** by means of solutions for (iv) computation-aware radio scheduling, (v) energy-aware VNF orchestration and (vi) self-learning MANO.
- **Ensure an extreme reliability of zero-touch B5G (DAEMON Objective 2.3)** by exploiting (vii) capacity failure avoidance via anticipatory allocation and (viii) anomaly detection.

2.1 Target KPIs

In the following, we list the set of KPIs set in DAEMON's Description of Action as Objective 4.1 and report the current status of capturing these KPIs through the related activities, which we capture in the "Activities" column of Table 2. In the "Average overall progress of the associated activities" column of Table 2, we show the average progress towards collecting the KPI over all the activities that collect that specific KPI.

Table 2. List of target KPIs: K1, K2, K4, K6 set the target relative to the current baseline; K3, K5, K7, K8, K9 define absolute targets that involve substantial improvements over today's state-of-the-art technology.

KPI	Description	Activities	Evidence supporting the feasibility of the target and improvement over the baseline	Average overall progress of the associated activities
K1	VNF energy consumption reduction	A6, A15, A26, A4, A5, A24, A1, A2, A29, A7	According to recent assessments, energy consumption in the edge and core of softwarized mobile networks may increase as much as 25% due to the impact of active cooling, among other issues. Thus, DAEMON aims at savings of up to 25% of energy costs thanks to a NI-assisted VNF placement based on energy considerations. Furthermore, additional 25% savings will be allowed by NI-assisted VNFs that can adapt their energy footprint to the context of the location where they are running.	68%
K2	Saving of computational resources at the edge	A15, A26, A20, A21, A27, A24, A30, A1, A2, A10, A29, A11, A7,	Current results of the DAEMON partners show that by applying intelligent radio and CPU scheduling in O-RAN architectures, one can reduce the requirement of the computing resources required by virtualized base stations by up to 20% with minimal impact on performance. The improved NI design developed by DAEMON shall advance those techniques from multiple perspectives as outlined in Objectives 1-3, hence making a 40% reduction target viable in the scenarios considered here.	75%
K3	Response time of AI-based NI algorithms	A15, A26, A9, A19, A8, A17, A18, A28	By leveraging on recent advances in highly elastic Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, DAEMON will build NI algorithms capable of meeting the hard requirements of delay- and reliability-sensitive traffic through effective trade-offs with accuracy. To the best of our knowledge, DAEMON will provide the first AI-based NI with guarantees in terms of response time.	62%
K4	OPEX savings	A15, A26, A4, A5, A20, A22, A24,	Preliminary studies of the DAEMON consortium demonstrate how AI models trained with customized loss functions that reflect monetary costs can avoid Service-Level Agreement (SLA) violations and reduce Operation Expenditure (OPEX) by up to 40%. While these figures refer to local solutions, the structured coordination of NI	69%

		A16, A1, A2, A29, A17, A18	instances enabled by the DAEMON architecture will allow targeting further cost savings of up to 60%.	
K5	Reliability	A24, A1, A2, A29, A11, A12, A13	Current state-of-the-art solutions developed by the DAEMON partners can satisfy SLA with a level of reliability between three and four 9's. The cooperative, multi-timescale NI orchestration model envisaged in DAEMON will significantly improve the amount and quality of information available to NI algorithms, making it possible to target further gains in the reliability of resource allocation decisions to, e.g., meet Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) requirements in certain conditions.	61%
K6	Wireless capacity (bps/m2) increase	A23	NI-controlled intelligent surfaces that can adapt the propagation properties of wireless channels to the environment dynamics will allow DAEMON to at least double the bit-rate per square meter in scenarios of interest, in line with early results.	50%
K7	Anomaly detection recall and sensitivity	A9, A19, A25	Recent methods for network anomaly detection achieve a precision-recall Area Under Curve (AUC) in the 0.66-0.88 range leaving substantial room for improvement toward 5G systems. Having access to NI coordination, as well as to novel tools for a tailored design of AI, the NI-assisted anomaly detection mechanisms designed by DAEMON will target a 0.9 precision-recall AUC with at least 85% scoring in both precision and recall in scenarios of interest.	63%
K8	Vertical service response time	A8, A11, A12, A13	By taking advantage of in-network support, backhaul-assisted computing as a service for third parties shall contribute to reducing the response time of vertical services from minutes in current production systems to seconds with DAEMON NI-assisted functionalities.	78%
K9	Optimality gap of network management decisions	A21, A22, A27, A3, A13	Building on the previous experience of the partners in anticipatory networking over long time horizons, DAEMON will ensure that decisions on network resource and function allocation occurring at periodicities of hours will perform very close (99%) to optimum oracles in scenarios of interest where the optimum can be defined. This will ensure that such decisions are precise enough to assist constructively faster NI, which uses such longer timescale decisions (e.g., policies) as input.	88%

2.2 Evaluations

In order to assess the performance of the NI-assisted functionalities and demonstrate how they can achieve the KPI targets set out above, we are performing eight dedicated evaluations, as follows.

- **Evaluation 1 (E1)** demonstrates real-time control and non-real-time orchestration of virtualized RAN (vRAN) services and resources. Experiments will have been carried out at sites T1 and T5 and with emulator S2 and focus on evaluating mechanisms that maximize the sustainability of dense vRAN deployments, minimizing their footprint and their operational and capital cost typically associated with greenfield deployments. Associated functionalities: Compute-aware radio scheduling.
- **Evaluation 2 (E2)** implements and demonstrates NI solutions that support network slice management and orchestration operations. Experiments have been conducted at site T8 and target the evaluation of the scalability, elasticity and stability of the NI-assisted automation and orchestration approaches developed by the project. Associated functionalities: Energy-aware VNF orchestration.
- **Evaluation 3 (E3) and Evaluation 5 (E5)** both validate tailored NI solutions for anomaly detection both in controlled environments and in a production core network, testing NI-assisted solutions for anomaly response in very large-scale settings. Experiments have been carried out at site T8 using ground-truth information on resolved incidences in the real-world network infrastructure of Telefonica, a major European operator. The NI-assisted anomaly detection designed within the

project is integrated into a big data platform where the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) operations teams inject live telemetry data, allowing for real-time evaluations in realistic scenarios. The experiments take full advantage of datasets D7, D8, D11, D12, D13 and D14 in order to assess the capability of the NI to (i) trigger alarms in the presence of network anomalies within the available data, (ii) detect the root cause of such anomalies, and (iii) recommend network healing actions that include anticipatory resource and VNF reallocations based on capacity forecasting. Associated functionalities: Automated anomaly response, Capacity forecasting.

- **Evaluation 4 (E4)** implements and deploys the NI-assisted solutions for service orchestration and resource allocation algorithms in the Edge micro-domain. Experiments shall leverage site T4, simulators S1 and S4, and datasets D1, D5, D6 and D9, validating the capabilities of the solutions developed by the project to dynamically orchestrate, allocate and deploy radio and network services. This setup is the ideal environment where to validate NI-driven tasks like, e.g., real-time radio technology classification or traffic classification in a real-world scenario characterized by high-dimensional and very dynamic input data. Associated functionalities: Multi-timescale Edge resource management.
- **Evaluation 6 (E6)** validates the NI solutions designed for long-timescale operations, i.e., MANO, VNF orchestration and the associated allocation of resources. Experiments have been built on dataset D3 since the performance of such network functionalities is best evaluated in large-scale scenarios. To this end, network load time series and other radio-cell-level and core network KPIs are used to demonstrate NI-assisted network function and capacity orchestration in a nationwide scenario. Associated functionalities: Self-learning MANO, Energy-aware VNF placement, Capacity forecasting.
- **Evaluation 7 (E7)** targets the demonstration of NI to configure Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) in a controlled environment. Experiments will leverage site T9, where one transmitter will send a flow of data to one receiver in non-line-of-sight. A large codebook, optimized through NI, will then be tested to assess the passive beamforming gains of the reflective RISs. Associated functionalities: RIS control.
- **Evaluation 8 (E8)** implements and supports NI functionalities for in-backhaul support of service intelligence. Experiments have been built on datasets D7, D11 and D12, and testbed T12. Associated functionalities: In-backhaul support for service intelligence.

Note that these evaluations extend our Objective 4.2, in the Description of Action, with two additional evaluations. We provide in Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2) reports the progress we have made within WP5 towards validating, testing and assessing the performance of the Network Intelligence (NI) solutions we have been developing within WP3 and WP4 of DAEMON. Given the NI solutions we have presented in D3.2 and D4.2, in this report we focus on performing a comprehensive assessment of the DAEMON solutions towards evaluating our set of target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In this effort, we leverage diverse tools for each functionality, including experimental testbeds, simulators and emulators, or impressive amounts of network data.

Table 1 a complete view of the association between KPIs and evaluations, showcasing the tools they employ and the activities they comprise. We clarify that, with respect to deliverable D5.1, we decided to add an extra evaluation for in-backhaul learning, namely E8. Our choice is motivated by the fact that during the implementation of the NI functionalities we defined in WP2, we found the need to separate the NI modules that support the in-backhaul learning activities, which correspond to the NI functionality F3.

3 Technical tools

In this section, **we present the technical tools that we employed for the performance evaluation of the NI-assisted functionalities developed in the project.** We keep the same separation in three categories, namely (i) simulations and emulators, (ii) experimental testbeds, and (iii) datasets.

3.1 Experimental testbed sites

We provide an overview of the full list of experimental sites in Table 3. In this document, we have included new evaluations that leverage the “Dockerized srsRAN + Open5GS testbed” (T6), the “Infrastructure for HADES validation testbed” (T13) and the “MNO Big Data Platform” (T14), not previously described in D5.1. For this reason, we provide a detailed description of three testbed sites in the remainder of this section (namely, T6, T13 and T14).

Table 3. Experimental sites, with related evaluations and KPIs. New testbeds are highlighted in bold.

ID	Name	Short description	Related evaluation	Related KPIs
T1	Virtualised radio stack	This testbed will be used to demonstrate compute-aware radio scheduling solutions studied in T3.1	E1	K1, K2, K4, K5
T2	5Tonic	Large-scale facility for the testing of orchestration solutions using a commercial access network	E2	K1, K4, K5, K8, K9
T3	Multi-site 5G radio testbed	Multi-site 5G Testbed, which spans across two different sites in Barcelona and Madrid (Spain), offers a novel and unique framework for testing diverse Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) applications	E3	K4, K5, K7, K8
T4	Smart highway	A real-life testbed for experimentation with vehicular communications and distributed edge computing	E4	K2, K5, K8
T5	SDR testbed with power meter	Software Defined Radio (SDR) testbed with a power meter to evaluate power consumption in virtualized RANs	E4	K1, K4, K9
T6	Dockerized srsRAN + Open5GS	Fully virtualizable solution for the creation of a 4G/5G network in a box, using srsRAN	E1	K1, K2, K4, K5
T7	VNF deployment and Edge Infrastructure	Testbed comprised of Bullsequana Edge nodes, which are for mobile computation, and high-performance commutators (Mellanox SN2100)	E1, E4	K1, K2, K3, K4
T8	Virtualised platform OSM and open stack	A set of servers on which an Open-Source MANO (OSM) and OpenStack deployment is realized	E2, E3	K3, K7
T9	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	A set of custom-made RIS prototypes designed and built within DAEMON to demonstrate RIS control solutions	E7	K6
T10	Eclipse Zenoh testbed	The machines within this testbed will be used to test Eclipse Zenoh's scalability, reliability and performance under different scenarios 10GbE are connected using a ring topology.	E4	K2
T11	Network capabilities, cloud resource testbed	OpenStack-based multi-cloud infrastructure, consisting of 720+ CPU cores, 1700GB+ RAM and 120+ TB storage space, interconnected mostly via 10Gbps fiber/copper links	E6	K2, K5, K9
T12	P4 programmable testbed for in-backhaul NI	Three Intel Tofino programmable switches deployed in a full 100-Gbps testbed with two dedicated servers for network emulation	E5, E8	K3, K7
T13	Infrastructure for HADES validation	Edge devices and equipment to measure energy consumption	E2	K1
T14	MNO Big Data Platform	Big Data platform of an operational MNO. Production environment [4]	E4	K2

3.1.1 Dockerized srsRAN and Open5GS (T6)

The softwarization of mobile network functions allowed network operators to reduce their operational expenditure by using open software and also enabled researchers and practitioners to experiment with new network functionalities. This software-driven transition is being accelerated with the introduction of cloud-native architectures, which greatly increases the flexibility and scalability of the software. In what follows, we introduce the different components of our cloud-native mobile network design, several of them chosen among the set of open-source solutions that have become available during the last few years.

Figure 2. The solutions that build the end-to-end architecture of this tool.

3.1.1.1 Overview

The different components of our design and development are illustrated in Figure 2. For orchestration, we chose Kubernetes, an open-source system for deploying and managing containerized applications. For the core network implementation, we selected Open5Gs, motivated by its adaptability to the cloud native paradigm. For the UE and the Access network, we rely on srsRAN, an open-source software that provides a full mobile network stack implementation for those elements. Furthermore, the srsRAN community is very active and its contributors keep intensively improving the product to keep up with the latest 3GPP standards. To simplify the deployment and support repeatability, we developed a simple channel emulator, which enables deploying a fully programmable end-to-end network without requiring expensive hardware. Finally, we chose Prometheus, one of the monitoring solutions promoted by the CNCF [5], as the monitoring framework to collect the status of the whole system. In what follows, we detail these components

3.1.1.2 Management and Orchestration

Kubernetes (also known as k8s) is a container orchestration platform, widely adopted in the cloud computing domain for more than five years. A typical cloud native application consists of a set of container images (e.g., Docker images) that are deployed and managed by Kubernetes, using configuration files that describe the functionality and the services they provide. Its scaling and redundancy capabilities have already been demonstrated in production environments, and it is envisioned that telco operators will rely on Kubernetes for next-generation networks, motivated by the need to make more efficient use of the heterogeneous virtualized infrastructure (which spans over central and edge data centers). To manage the additional management complexity, a huge ecosystem of open-source projects, that extends the possible operational tasks, has been created under the umbrella of the Cloud Native Computing Foundation.

3.1.1.3 Core Functions

Open5Gs is a very popular open-source implementation of a mobile network core. Written in C, it stands as a reference among researchers and mobile telecommunications practitioners for experimentation and future enhancements. Currently supporting up to 3GPP 5G Release 16, it contains the most important components of the 5G Core (5GC) and 4G Evolved Packet Core (EPC) with Control-User Plane Separation (CUPS) [6], meaning it can operate on both 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) and Standalone (SA) modes, as it can serve both 4G E-UTRAN NodeB (eNBs) and 5G next Generation NodeB (gNBs). Its straightforward build procedure makes its deployment in small-scale private networks very easy, while its modular architecture could be considered as a natural candidate for running it into microservices-based cloud-native environments powered by Kubernetes. As illustrated in Figure 3, Open5Gs pods will be deployed over the virtual infrastructure, while srsENB is directly running on top of Docker containers.

3.1.1.4 RAN functions

SrsRAN provides a software RF-frontend based on ZeroMQ, an open source message queueing library written in C. When using this driver, the transmitted I/Q baseband symbols between UE and base station are transferred over various transport methods, like inter-process communication (IPC) or TCP sockets. Choosing this driver avoids the need for high expertise in RF channel configuration and facilitates the introduction of researchers who want to simulate a radio access network environment, but whose RF channel is not their main area of interest or would be reluctant to invest in actual hardware transceivers. We next discuss how we take advantage of ZeroMQ to implement a channel emulation model.

Figure 3. Core and RAN Infrastructure setup.

Figure 4. Possible configuration of the tool as evaluated in [7].

3.1.1.5 Channel emulation: GRC Broker

As mentioned, the use of ZeroMQ enables running the network in a fully softwarized way. Furthermore, it also enables the emulation of complex topologies via programming (e.g., arbitrary complex topologies can be created by dynamically connecting endpoints, as they do in large-scale emulators using hardware in the loop [8]). The main challenge when emulating complex mobility scenarios relies on the handling of I/Q symbols, e.g., sending low-power symbols from the eNB to trigger a Handover Request from the UE.

Following the srsRAN Documentation, we utilized the GNU Radio Companion (GRC), which is another open-source project mainly used for software-defined radio (SDR) and, among others, contains modules for the ZeroMQ library. We coded in Python a GRC Broker, located between the UE and the cells of the eNB(s) implementing the RF interface, as illustrated in Figure 4. This module intercepts the transmitted I/Q symbols and performs operations on them to emulate the channel condition for the two traffic directions:

- In the downlink direction, in order to simulate the distance between the UE and the cells, we made use of multiplier blocks followed by an adder. Multiplier blocks multiply the time-domain cells' transmitted samples with a constant gain value in the range $[0, 1]$, adjusting UE's perception of the cells' signal strength. The adder block simply performs the superposition of the modified samples, as would be the case in the real environment.
- In the uplink direction, we used a throttle block that retransmits the I/Q symbols toward the cells of the eNB(s).

This setup can be used to create different evaluation scenarios as well as the implementation of additional features into the GRC Broker. The software is available as open source at [9] [10].

3.1.2 Infrastructure for HADES Validation (T13)

Figure 5 shows the edge infrastructure used to validate HADES. The infrastructure consists of eleven heterogeneous nodes, one a manager node and the other ten distributed in three Kubernetes clusters. Specifically, as a Kubernetes instance, we use Microk8s (release 1.23), a lightened version of Kubernetes. This version reduces the resources required compared to the standard version of Kubernetes, decreasing Energy Consumption (EC) and improving the proposal's applicability.

The manager node (Node 1) contains instances of HADES, OSM (its most up-to-date release, ELEVEN), the application repository and three virtualized VIMs (that are virtualized using OSM's native emu-vim tool). All this on an Ubuntu 20.04 LTS virtual machine hosted on a Windows 10 operating system using VirtualBox. This node, which manages the entire infrastructure, has an Intel Core i7-7700K (4.2 GHz of CPU, two cores dedicated to the VM) and 16 GB of DDR4 2400 MHz RAM (8 GB dedicated to the VM). The first cluster (Cluster 1) consists of four nodes: a Raspberry Pi 4 as the master node (which is also a worker) with three associated worker nodes (a desktop, a laptop and a Raspberry Pi 3 B+). Concretely, the master node (Raspberry Pi 4, Node 2) has Ubuntu Mate 20.04.1 as the operating system running over a Broadcom BCM2711 Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit (up to 1.5 GHz) SoC and 4 GB LPDDR4-3200 SDRAM of RAM. Node 3 (desktop) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, having an Intel Core i5-4440 (3.10 GHz) CPU as processor and 12 GB of DDR3 1333 MHz of RAM. The laptop (Node 4) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS and has an Intel Core i5-5300U (2.30 GHz) as a processor and 4 GB of DDR3 1600 MHz of RAM. The Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (Node 5) runs Ubuntu Server 20.04, its processor is a 64-bit Cortex-A53 (ARM v8) SoC (1.4 GHz) and has 1 GB LPDDR2 SDRAM of RAM. On the other hand, Cluster 2 is formed by three nodes: another Raspberry Pi 4 (same configuration as Node 2) operating as a master node (which is also a worker) that manages two worker nodes (a desktop and a laptop). Node 7 desktop has Ubuntu 20.04 LTS as the operating system, an Intel Core i5-3570K (up to 3.70 GHz) CPU as processor and 12 GB of DDR3 1333 MHz of RAM. Finally, the laptop (Node 8) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, too, and has an Intel Core i5-5200U (2.20 GHz) and 4 GB of DDR3 1600 MHz of RAM. Finally, Cluster 3 contains three nodes: Node 9, operating as master and worker, which is a Raspberry Pi 4 (same characteristics as Nodes 2 and 6); Node 10, a laptop (same characteristics as Node 4); and Node 11, a Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (same characteristics as Node 5). This infrastructure follows the commonly used structure in Edge Computing of using low-power nodes (powerful enough) as master nodes. Nodes have a clean operating system installation, trying to minimize the number of background tasks.

Figure 5. Infrastructure for the evaluation of HADES.

To perform an efficient task allocation, HADES uses the nodes' idle and busy energy consumption. Therefore, the nodes' energy consumption has been analyzed at idle (with the Microk8s installed) and during a 1-minute CPU matrix stress test. The matrix stressor is an excellent way to exercise CPU floating-point operations and the processor's memory and data cache. To measure energy consumption, we use Watts Up? Pro [11], a physical meter that allows real-time monitoring of the amount of energy supplied to the device connected to the power supply.

Regarding communication, the round-trip time between nodes is obtained by pinging from node a to b (considering the average of sending 1000 small packets). The transmission rate has been analyzed using the iPerf¹ tool (considering the average transmission rate of sending packages during 100 seconds). Finally, the power transmission is given directly from the characteristics of the nodes' network cards.

¹ <https://iperf.fr/>

3.1.3 MNO Big Data Platform (T14)

TID leverages a big data platform within O2 UK’s infrastructure to deploy AI models in collaboration with O2’s team in their network environment. The infrastructure includes more than 250 nodes, 3PB of storage, 60TB of RAM, and more than 5,000 CPUs. The data ingestion service runs 24/7 and receives more than 10TB/day. The figure above captures the specifics of the software stack running in the UK cluster.

Figure 6. MNO Big Data Platform.

In DAEMON, we leverage TID’s access to this platform and the support of O2 UK for data treatment operations to validate using real operational data the novel AI models the consortium aims to build throughout its lifetime. Specifically, we integrated our activity A13 within this platform. For this, we worked closely in collaboration with O2 UK to build custom solutions, and test them directly on O2’s big data and analytics platform.

3.2 Simulators and emulators

In terms of simulators and emulators, the project counts with the same four platforms that we previously introduced in deliverable D5.1. For completion, we further summarise them in Table 4, and refer the reader to D5.1 for a detailed description. The table also indicates which evaluations and KPIs rely on each respective simulator.

Table 4. Simulators and emulators available in the project, with related evaluations and KPIs.

ID	Name	Short description	Related evaluation	Related KPIs
S1	Edge/Cloud simulator	Used for resource management performance evaluation	E4	K4
S2	P4 programmable RAN	Include disaggregated RANs, P4 bmv2 switch and NBL CN	E1	K8
S3	System level simulator	Advanced component validation and optimization	E3	K7
S4	EnergyEdgeCloudSim	Extension of EdgeCloudSim environment that considers energy consumption	E4	K1, K2, K3, K4

3.3 Datasets

The evaluations carried out in the project build upon 15 datasets to date. Table 5 provides a list of these datasets, whose details are then expounded in the rest of the section. The table also indicates what evaluations and KPIs are associated with each dataset. New datasets are highlighted in bold in Table 5 and are presented in detail next.

Table 5. Measurement datasets available in the project, with related evaluations and KPIs.

ID	Name	Short description	Dataset status	Source	Data velocity	Data volume	Eval.	KPIs
D1	MNO radio performance	Collected from an operational mobile network in the UK	Private	Real	Depending on the specific data feed (e.g., hourly, per 15 min, real-time)	Order of TB per day	E4, E5	K5, K7, K8, K9

D1a	MNO Users' Catalog	Augmented version of D1 with a daily view of the activity of each device connected to the radio network of the MNO	Private	Real	4h window or 24h window	Order of GB per day	E4	K4
D1b	MNO radio performance augmented	Augmented version of D1 with dataset D2	Private	Real	Depending on the type of data	Depending on the type of data	E6	K5, K6, K7, K9
D2	End-user performance	Measurement data from OTE telecom operator, aggregated over geographical areas	Private	Real	1 sample every 15 minutes	Depending on the type of data	E6	K2, K4, K5, K6, K9
D3	Service-level traffic demand	Collected in the core network of a major European mobile operator, describing the mobile traffic generated by the subscriber base of the operator over the territory of an European country	Private	Real	1 sample per minute	Order of TB	E6	K2, K4, K9
D4	vRAN performance and power consumption	Set of measurements of the performance and power consumption of a vBS using the srsRAN software in testbed T5	Open source (Link)	Real	1 sample every 20 seconds	12.2 MB	E4	K1, K2, K3
D5	Edge Dataset	Measurements of latency and cumulative confidence when an android application sends compressed images to an edge server	Open source (Link)	Real	1 Sample per minute	2.8 MB	E4	K2
D6	Wireless interactions in multiple BSS using Channel Bonding	Data from WLAN deployments applying Dynamic Channel Bonding (DCB) generated via the Kommondor simulator	Open source (Link)	Synthetic	3 samples per minute	20 KB per deployment	E4	K5, K8
D7	Intrusion Detection Evaluation Dataset	Validation dataset for anomaly-based intrusion detection approaches	Open source (Link)	Real	Variable ²	8.3 GB	E8	K3, K7
D8	IPX Signaling Dataset for IoT	Data obtained monitoring the IP eXchange Provider (IPX-P) infrastructure supporting three core network functions that enable the data roaming service for IoT devices	Private	Real	Signaling dialogues arrive every 5min	Order of GB per day	E3	K5, K7, K8, K9
D8*	IPX Signaling Dataset for IoT augmented	Similar dataset to D8 obtained from a different IoT-managed connectivity provider	Private	Real	Signaling dialogues arrive in real-time	Order of tens of GB per day	E3	K5, K7, K8, K9
D9	YouTube file requests	Collection of traces from a campus network measurement on Youtube traffic	Open source (Link)	Real	1 sample every 5 minutes	Order of MB per day	E4, E6	K3, K4
D10	GEC case study	Energy measurements obtained from a Generic Edge Computing (GEC) application designed to represent an IoT/EdgeCloud system	Open Source (link)	Real	1 sample every second	14,3 MB	E2	K1
D11	IoT devices dataset	Measurement data for 28 IoT devices collected in a living lab emulating a smart environment	Open source (link)	Real	Variable ²	12.7 GB	E8	K3
D12	Applications and protocols dataset	Real-world traces collected from 20 workstations deployed at the University of Brescia campus	Open source (link)	Real	Variable ²	581 MB	E8	K3

² The dataset is composed of .pcap files with packet traces that have a high variability of time of arrival.

D13	Malicious attacks dataset	Network traffic captured on a testbed recreating normal and attack traffic behaviors	Open source (link)	Real	Variable ²	22.6 MB	E8	K3
D14	Malicious packets dataset	Network traffic captured in the Cyber Range Lab of UNSW of Canberra recreating normal and malicious traffic	Open source (link)	Real	Variable ²	10 GB	E8	K3
D15	Shanghai Data set	Records of accessing the Internet in the city of Shanghai.	Open source (link)	Real	Variable	51 MB	E4	K1, K2, K3, K4

3.3.1 MNO Users' Catalog (D1a)

In the devices catalog, we build a comprehensive daily view of the activity of each device in the entire population of devices connected to the radio network of the MNO (namely, VMO2 in the UK). We created this dataset using an analytics pipeline that we deploy on top of the data we have available in D1 from the operator. **We have tested this pipeline and deployed it within the production environment of the MNO.** The resulting datasets support Activity A13, which we present in Section 4.4.4. By integrating our analytics pipeline within the production MNO network, we allow for fast deployment of further analytics based on the characteristics and activity of the devices connecting to the radio access network of the MNO.

The devices catalog relies on different raw data feeds that we aggregate per user per day. The result is a daily per-device summary, and it is the result of a complex data analytics pipeline that processes a series of raw data feeds that the operator collects from the network. These include radio signaling traffic, in particular events generated by the devices connecting to the radio sectors to request resources for voice or data communication. We previously reported and described these raw data feeds within D1 (MNO radio performance).

3.3.2 MNO radio performance (D1b)

We augmented the D1 dataset on MNO radio performance with a similar dataset from OTE, which the entity provided to the DAEMON consortium. OTE is the leading mobile network operator in Greece, with close to 50% of the total customers in the country. OTE provides access to nationwide datasets of network KPIs (e.g., per-cell served users, traffic, throughput, latency, etc.). Similar to TID's dataset, the dataset from OTE includes information for its commercial mobile network for two types of geographical regions; dense and urban areas. Datasets are hosted on a standalone file server at OTE's premises. OTE also implemented the necessary network configuration and created different accounts for each DAEMON partner with the necessary privileges in order to access the dataset.

3.3.3 IPX Signaling Dataset for IoT (D8*)

We augmented the D8 dataset that we previously presented in D5.1 with a similar dataset (which we tag as D8*) that we collected from the dedicated IoT operator. In this effort, we essentially built similar datasets from two different players within the same space (namely, IoT-managed connectivity providers). The dataset for the dedicated IoT operator was collected in January 2020 and includes approximately 270,000 unique devices. In total, the dataset D8 (including the D8* addition) contains more than one billion signaling interactions that we analyze using Apache Spark. Note that each such interaction, called a dialogue, consists of one or multiple request-response pairs.

Figure 7. Overview of the IoT cellular ecosystem and the role of roaming for global IoT connectivity. We show the interfaces we monitor to build the dataset of signaling traffic (MAP and GTP signaling dialogues). In the lower part, we show an example of MAP signaling dialogue between a VLR in Italy and a HLR in Germany to authenticate the IoT device with the IMSI 262xx.

Figure 7 shows schematically where and on which interfaces we collect the data. We capture the raw signaling traffic and process it to rebuild the signaling dialogues between core network functions in the home network and those in the visited network whose RAN is used by devices. There are no ethical concerns regarding the datasets we analyze, as no identifying information is processed.

Dataset D8* is similar to the definition of D8 in D5.1 [3], though captured from a different operator. If D8 is captured from Telefonica's systems, we build D8* in collaboration with a dedicated IoT Provider from Germany.

Considering SCCP signaling, we monitor the Mobile Application Part (MAP) protocol that supports end-user mobility and allows network elements (e.g., the HLR (Home Location Registry), VLR (Visited Location Registry), Mobile-services Switching Centre (MSC)) to communicate. We collect traffic corresponding to the procedures of each device: i) authentication and security, and ii) location management (update/cancel location).

For the GTP-c signaling, we monitor dialogues required to manage data tunnels between roaming partners. Here we capture the create, update, and delete Packet Data Protocol (PDP) context procedures that devices trigger before and after a data communication. Specifically, we generate one record for each create session exchange and retain basic information such as the tunnel ID, which enables mapping of create and delete procedures.

3.3.4 Shanghai Data set (D15)

The dataset, provided by Shanghai Telecom, contains more than 7.2 million records of accessing the Internet through 3,233 base stations from 9,481 mobile phones for six months. As shown in **Table 6**, the Telecom dataset shows 6 parameters: Month, Date, Start Time, End Time, Base Station Location, and Mobile Phone ID. The trajectory of users can be found in the dataset.

Table 6. Telecom parameters.

ID	Parameter Name	Description
1	Month	The month when one record happens
2	Date	The date when one record happens
3	Start Time	The time when a record starts
4	End time	The time when a record ends
5	Base Station Location	The longitude and latitude of the base station where the mobile phones access the Internet
6	User ID	Mobile phone

4 Results

As anticipated in Table 1 and Table 2, the results achieved by the project to date are organized into activities, which jointly contribute to progressing in each planned evaluation, and capture the KPIs we identified. **Overall, the project carried out 30 activities to date. In the following subsections, we present the results for each evaluation E1-E8 and detail the outcome of each associated activity by justifying how it collected the target KPIs.**

4.1 NI for sustainable virtualised RANs

Evaluation E1 focuses on real-time control and non-real-time orchestration of vRAN services & resources. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E1 via activities A1-A5. Table 7 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate current progress per activity and main innovations of such activities.

Table 7. List of activities for E1.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Progress
A1	Reliable RAN virtualisation	E1	T1	K1, K2, K4, K5	K1, K2, K4, K5	4	Yes	100%
<i>Main innovation:</i> 1) Reliable DU design suitable for Virtualization; 2) Centralised real-time control of radio and computing resources								
A2	AI-driven O-Cloud	E1	T1	K1, K2, K4, K5	K2, K4	4	Yes	66%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Centralised real-time control of radio and computing resources								
A3	Application aware radio scheduling	E1	S2	K9	K9	3	TBD	70%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Traffic classifier to steer scheduler settings								
A29	ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs	E1	T5	K1, K2, K4, K5	K2, K4, K5	4	Yes	40%
<i>Main innovation:</i> ML-based radio resource scheduling with machine reasoning								

4.1.1 Reliable distributed unit for virtualisation (A1)

In this activity, designed in the context of WP3 (see Section 2.1 of D3.2 [1]), we evaluate Nuberu. Nuberu is a novel pipeline architecture for 5G Distributed Units (DUs) that enable the use of shared virtualization platforms reliably.

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	The industry standard today is to deploy individual instances of 5G DUs per server, with the associated energy toll (baseline consumption of individual server). Nuberu enables the use of shared computing platforms. As a result, multiple 5G DUs can share the same server, which directly improves energy consumption by saving the baseline energy consumption of additional servers, which ranges between 29% and 50% of savings per server [12].
K2	Nowadays, it is common practice for the industry to utilize single instances of 5G Distributed Units (DUs) on each server. However, Nuberu offers the ability to employ shared computing platforms, which allows multiple 5G DUs to share a single server and therefore saves computing resources.
K4	The OPEX savings achieved by Nuberu come exclusively from the energy savings explained in K1.
K5	DUs are inherently hard to virtualize because the pipeline of signal processing operations therein must be met with 99.999% probability in order to attain reliability. The key technology advancement of Nuberu is to remove such a hard requirement, which enables us to attain the same degree of reliability irrespective of the computing availability at the cost of network latency.

To validate and evaluate Nuberu, our pipeline design discussed in Section 2.1 of D3.2 [1], we have implemented it into srsRAN's stack with the parameters shown in Table 8 and use its implementation of the baseline architecture as our benchmark.

Table 8. Parametrization of Nuberu.

Parameter	Value
Pipeline parallelization depth (M)	4
Nr. DL-Data DU workers	3 per forethead
Nr. UL-Data DU workers	3 per forethead
UL-Data DU worker's buffer size	8 grants
DL-Data DU worker's buffer size	25 grants
Phase II budget (τ)	1.3 ms
UL Congestion Control (α, β)	3, 0.9
DL Congestion Control (α, β, λ)	3, 0.9, 2
E-HARQ (γ_1, γ_2)	600, 200

This provides a fair comparison because, in this way, both Nuberu and the baseline approach rely on identical implementations of individual tasks such as "PUSCH process" or "PDSCH process". Consequently, we can show that the gains provided by Nuberu do not come from optimizing signal processing operations within individual tasks but from Nuberu's architectural advantages over unreliable computing platforms.

We use an off-the-shelf Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU D-1528 server with six x86 cores @ 1.90GHz, and Linux containers to host vDU instances. To avoid uncontrolled effects, we disable hyperthreading and apply CPU shielding to allocate five cores to host vDU instances; the remaining core is reserved for the OS and other processes (e.g., for monitoring). To focus on harsh computing environments, we do not use any hardware acceleration.

4.1.1.1 Downlink

We begin by assessing the performance of Nuberu with downlink traffic. To this end, we set up a scenario comprised of one vDU transmitting as much load as possible with high SNR, and measuring throughput (rate of bits successfully decoded by the receiver) and buffering (time elapsed between scheduling a data grant for encoding and actually delivering it over the air). Figure 8 compares the network throughput achieved by the baseline approach and by Nuberu with different settings of λ and for different amounts of computing resources allocated to the vDU's encoder, which are measured as the number of bits that are encoded by unit of time, between 8 b/ μ s and 200 b/ μ s. As a reference, a dedicated Intel Xeon core @ 1.9GHz provides an encoding performance of 200 b/ μ s.

Figure 8. Downlink throughput (left) and vPHY buffering (right) with a saturating load. Comparison between the baseline and Nuberu under different computing capacities

We first note that the baseline approach is inelastic: its throughput collapses suddenly when its DU jobs exceed the available processing time budget (see Figure 9). In marked contrast, Nuberu preserves high throughput irrespective of the available computing capacity, providing *elasticity* upon computing fluctuations. Indeed, Nuberu's parameter λ serves to choose the desired trade-off between data buffering at the vPHY (shown by the right-most subplot) and throughput. When $\lambda = \infty$, effectively disabling congestion control, Nuberu is greedy and maintains maximum throughput irrespective of the computing capacity but incurs high buffering. Conversely, lower values of λ help reduce buffering at the cost of throughput when there is a shortage of computing resources.

4.1.1.2 Congestion Control

We next evaluate the performance of Nuberu's congestion controller. To this aim, we use the same setup as before with the encoder's computing capacity equal to 12.5 b/ μ s, and with $\alpha = 3$ and $\lambda = 2$. Based on

this, we run a set of experiments with different DL load patterns and settings of β , where the load is varied by changing the duty cycle of an on-off generation process with no traffic during the off period and saturating rate during the on period. We plot in Figure 9 the evolution over time of the throughput achieved for the different loads and values of β considered.

Figure 9. Congestion control performance for different loads and settings of β . $\alpha = 3$, $\lambda = 2$. Colored lines show mean throughput. Shades cover the area between the 10th and the 90th percentile. Dashed black lines represent the maximum rate limit to avoid congestion as set by $\lambda=2$.

Nuberu's congestion control effectively limits the data rate generated by the DU to avoid congestion, as set by parameter λ , when there are shortages of computing resources. To illustrate this, the plot also depicts with dashed black lines the theoretical rate limit that achieves this for $\lambda = 2$. On the one hand, $\beta < 0.9$ values are overly aggressive, rendering highly unstable performance and low throughput. On the other hand, $\beta > 0.9$ results in slow convergence to adapt $cwnd_{DL}$ to the optimal value when the load is bursty (< 1), which generates a data rate that violates the buffer constraint set by $\lambda = 2$. We hence use $\{\alpha = 3, \beta = 0.9\}$ in all our experiments.

Figure 10. Throughput-delay trade-off for different loads.

To provide more insights about the throughput-delay tradeoff achieved by the congestion controller, we run more experiments with additional DL load patterns. For each pattern, we measure the mean throughput and one-way end-to-end delay (between end-user applications synchronized with IEEE 1588 protocol) over 1-second windows for Nuberu ($\lambda = 2$, $\alpha = 3$, $\beta = 0.9$) and the baseline and map each result in the throughput-delay plot shown in Figure 10. To ease visualization, we only plot a small subset of the results and a curve fitting all of them. As shown by the figure, Nuberu substantially outperforms the baseline despite the use of buffering to accommodate the computing jitter. Conversely, the baseline approach frequently loses synchronization, hence providing overly low throughput and, as a result, high end-to-end delay.

Figure 11. E-HARQ accuracy and false positive rate for different γ settings and for different combinations of MCS, TB size, SNR, and computing capacity.

4.1.1.3 Uplink (Early HARQ)

Different combinations of Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR), Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), and Transport Block (TB) size values, and computing capacity have a different impact on Early Hybrid Automated-Repeat-Request (E-HARQ). To assess this, we test different Π_γ and show in Figure 11 its accuracy (ratio of predictions made right, at the top), and its ratio of false positives (bottom subplot). The latter is relevant because a false positive, i.e., acknowledging a TB that is not decodable, incurs substantially higher cost because the TB has to be recovered by higher layers such as RLC or even TCP (if RLC does not use ARQ). This exercise lets us explore the parameter space of our E-HARQ approach and choose the most appropriate setting. Although $\{\gamma_1 = 600, \gamma_2 = 400\}$ reaches a negligible false-positive ratio ($\sim 0.04\%$) and high accuracy (95%), we have selected $\{\gamma_1 = 400, \gamma_2 = 200\}$ because it provides 99% accuracy while keeping low a false positive ratio ($\sim 0.1\%$).

Figure 12. Maximum computing latency supported by Nuberu's E-HARQ given a target accuracy.

Certainly, the actual performance is determined by the (extrinsic) information available before the Minimum Viable SubFrame (MVSF, see Section 2.1 of D3.2 [1]) deadline in each job. To get additional insight on this, we present in Figure 12 the minimum computing capacity required by the decoder to attain a given target of accuracy from 50% to 99% for 3 different SNR regimes (low, with SNR below 20 dB, medium, with SNR up to 25 dB, and high), and 6 different MCS indexes (14 to 19) from 3GPP. As a baseline to compare against, we plot with a red line the computing capacity required to run up to 10 decoder iterations in our time budget, which is the usual threshold to decide on the decodability of a TB when E-HARQ is not employed. As a reference, a dedicated Intel Xeon core @ 1.9GHz provides a decoding performance of $\sim 80 \text{ b}/\mu\text{s}$ per iteration. To attain high accuracy during medium and high SNR regimes, we only require sufficient computing resources so our decoder can process $\sim 2.5 \text{ bits}/\mu\text{s}$ (400 ns per bit).

The rest of MCS values alternate between high and mild processing requirements depending on the accuracy target and MCS during low SNR conditions. Remarkably, our E-HARQ mechanism alone lets us reduce by 35x the amount of computing capacity required to carry out the task.

Figure 13. Network capacity region of Nuberu and our baseline. Different computing capacity settings equal to $k \cdot c_0$, where c_0 is the nominal encoding/decoding capacity of a dedicated Intel Xeon core @ 1.9GHz.

4.1.1.4 Single-vDU network capacity region

We now empirically characterize the network capacity region of one vDU under high SNR regimes, which generate the highest computational load and are a worst case. To this end, we measure DL and UL throughput for a wide set of UL/DL network load combinations. We also vary the number of computing resources allocated to the encoder and the decoder by scaling them down to $k \cdot c_0$, where c_0 is the nominal encoding/decoding capacity of a dedicated Intel Xeon core @ 1.9GHz, and $k \leq 1$. Our results are shown in Figure 13 for Nuberu, tuned with and without E-HARQ and $\lambda=\{2, \infty\}$, and for our baseline approach. To ease visualization, we only present the region envelope and a few points around it.

Obviously, when we have dedicated and over-dimensioned computing capacity ($k = 1$), the networking capacity region shows a rectangular shape where uplink and downlink reach maximum spectral efficiency. However, if we reduce the system's computing capacity by $k = 1/2.5$, Nuberu $\lambda = \infty$ (in purple line) preserves the highest theoretical spectrum efficiency.

Moreover, Nuberu $\lambda = 2$ (in dark blue line) provides a much higher maximum aggregate throughput than our baseline approach (yellow line). Most of this capacity gain comes from E-HARQ, as it can be seen from the fact that Nuberu falls to the baseline's performance when E-HARQ is disabled (green line). As we reduce the number of computing resources ($k = 1/5$ and $k = 1/5.5$), the baseline's capacity region keeps shrinking while Nuberu sustains high downlink capacity (even if E-HARQ is disabled) as well as an uplink (unless E-HARQ is disabled and the computing conditions are the harshest, i.e., $k = 1/5.5$).

Remarkably, with $k = 1/5.5$, which represents an 80% computing resource reduction over the best scenario for the baseline approach, Nuberu reaches $\sim 95\%$ of the maximum theoretical spectrum efficiency.

4.1.1.5 Shared Computing resources

In the previous sections, we have characterized the performance of a single vDU instance with Nuberu (and the baseline). In the following, we keep the maximum processing speed of our experimental platform (which attains 200 encoded bits/ μ s and ~ 80 decoded bits/ μ s per iteration) and deploy multiple vDU instances sharing the common computing resource (five Intel Xeon cores @ 1.90GHz).

Figure 14. Network performance for a variable number of vDUs contending for computing resources.

Specifically, we let one vDU under test (Nuberu or Baseline) compete for resources with a variable number of competing vDUs that generate DU jobs with a duration that follows a normal distribution with average 1 ms and standard deviation 0.25 ms. Figure 14 depicts the UL and DL throughput (left and right subplots, respectively) when the vDU under test uses Nuberu with the same settings used before (blueish and green bars) and when it uses the baseline approach (yellow bar) for different scenarios where the number of competing vDUs spans between 0 and 10.

Nuberu's performance remains high in all scenarios. Only when E-HARQ is not employed UL throughput drops approximately 5% per competing vDU. When using E-HARQ, UL throughput only drops 10% when $\lambda = 2$ and $\sim 2\%$ when $\lambda = \infty$. Conversely, Nuberu attains the maximum spectral capacity in the DL channel regardless of the number of contending vDUs. In marked contrast, the performance of our baseline approach drops significantly with every competing vDU: UL performance collapses when it competes with more than 1 vDU, and DL throughput only reaches 27% with 2 competing vDUs and $< 5\%$ with a higher (>2) amount of competitors. This result provides strong evidence of the elasticity and high efficiency of Nuberu in shared cloud environments.

4.1.1.6 Multiple-vDU capacity region

The results shown above validate Nuberu's superior performance when sharing a platform with different amounts of computing interference. However, they do not evaluate how the available computing capacity is distributed among different instances of vDU, i.e., *fairness*.

Figure 15. Network capacity region in a 2-vDU scenario. Encoder/decoder processing speed equal to $c0/4$, where $c0$ is the nominal speed of a dedicated Intel Xeon core @ 1.9GHz.

Consequently, we conclude our evaluation with an empirical characterization of the network capacity region of a system with two vDUs (vDU 1 and vDU 2) sharing the same computing platform. Both vDUs are homogeneous in this case, that is, they both implement Nuberu (with and without EHARQ, and for $\lambda = \{2, \infty\}$) or the baseline architecture. Different from the experiments of Section 4.1.1.5, which showed competing vDUs with fixed load, we now test a wide set of UL and DL network load combinations; and we reduce the encoder/decoder processing speed of our platform by a quarter ($k = 1/4$ in §VI-D) to study harsh computing conditions.

Figure 15 depicts the throughput performance achieved by vDU 1 versus the obtained by vDU 2 for both DL (left plot) and UL (right plot) directions. Like before, we only present the capacity frontier with fitting lines and a few experimental points around it to simplify the plot. “Nuberu ($\lambda = \infty$)” maximizes the throughput of both vDUs in both DL and UL; “Nuberu ($\lambda = 2$)” maximizes UL performance and roughly halves DL throughput to control buffering at the PHY; and “Nuberu ($\lambda = 2$, no E-HARQ)” further halves UL throughput to avoid dropping UL data that cannot be decoded on time. In contrast, while the baseline approach reduces DL throughput in a similar way as Nuberu when $\lambda = 2$, its UL performance is roughly a third of the maximum spectrum capacity. This is because the users frequently lose synchronization with the DUs and cannot communicate while re-attaching. Importantly, this result proves that the individual performance gains provided by Nuberu do not come at the cost of fairness but because of a more efficient pipeline design when there are shortages of computing resources.

4.1.2 AI-driven O-Cloud (A2)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	Not collected yet.
K2	The industry standard today is to deploy individual instances of 5G Distributed Units (DUs) per server. Nuberu enables the use of shared computing platforms. As a result, multiple 5G Distributed Units (DUs) can share the same server, with the associated savings in computing resources. The industry standard today is to deploy individual instances of 5G Distributed Units (DUs) per server. Our AI-driven O-Cloud solution shall enable the use of shared computing platforms reliably. As a result, multiple 5G Distributed Units (DUs) can share the same server, with the associated savings in computing resources.
K4	Not collected yet.
K5	Not collected yet.

4.1.2.1 Multiplexing opportunities in O-Cloud platforms

DU traffic is bursty at very small timescales. Using Falcon, we tracked the load fluctuations (Radio Block (RB) usage, MCS, SNR, and TB size every 1-ms subframe) in several 4G³ cells from a large operator in a major European city at different times during April 2022. Figure 16 shows the instantaneous load fluctuations of one cell during 10s on April 14th. We observe very quick load fluctuations within the millisecond timescale, which motivate real-time control mechanisms to meet the 5-nines reliability target.

Figure 16. Instantaneous load fluctuations in a 4G cell.

Figure 24 in D5.1 [3] presented two families of processors for LDPC workloads: (i) low-performing low-consuming CPUs (software) and (ii) high-performing high-consuming HAs such as GPUs. We next analyze the utilization of a high-performing HA to handle the workload stemming from these real traces. Among the candidates to represent the second family, we have chosen an NVIDIA V100 GPU because it is programmable with a CUDA-based SDK, provides CPU-like time-to-market figures, and enables AI-on-5G for future work.

³ Our goal is to collect data that is representative of today's real demand for radio resources and SNR patterns. Because the penetration of 5G in the target city is low, we believe that 4G data is a better fit for this purpose.

Figure 17. UE demand profiles used for evaluation.

Labeled “4G”, Figure 17 characterizes the behavior of one UE during a 10-minute time frame on the morning of April 14th (TB size on the left, inter-TB arrival time in the middle, and SNR on the right). To assess a wider range of scenarios with more demanding UEs, we generated a synthetic profile “5G” by amplifying the buffer of each “4G” UE by a factor equal to the capacity gain of 5G (roughly 3.6x). Similarly, we generated the additional profiles depicted in Figure 17 by amplifying “5G” by $\{2, \dots, 64\}x$. To emulate the behavior of multiple UEs in a controllable manner, we extract patterns from as many individual UEs as needed at random times from the selected profile and normalize their timestamps. Every TTI, we observe the buffer of each UE and allocate NR resources using a round-robin scheduler.

Figure 18. GPU HA mean usage for different workloads.

Figure 18 depicts the relative busy time of the GPU HA (y-axis) to process the workload generated by a different number of concurrent UEs (x-axis) in a single 100-MHz 5G DU with the aforementioned demand profiles (colors). For the 5G workload generated by the “4G” and “5G” demands, the HA utilization is below 12%, even up to 10 UEs. In fact, 85 simultaneously active “5G” UEs, or 10 UEs saturating the whole bandwidth (“5Gx64”), would be required to fully use the HA, which evinces opportunities to share HAs in real scenarios.

O-RAN estimates that the maximum latency tolerance of the O-FH interface is $100 \mu s$. Assuming a $5\text{-}\mu s/\text{Km}$ propagation delay, the area of RUs that can be connected to a single edge cloud aggregating DUs is up to 400 Km^2 when using a 2D Manhattan tessellation model. In fact, NTT Docomo famously centralizes up to 48 LTE cells in a single platform. Hence, it is indeed feasible to aggregate the workload of multiple DUs and multiplex the resources of high-performing HAs in centralized edge clouds.

4.1.2.2 Diversity across FEC professors

In the following, we present an experimental campaign to analyze the behavior of two processors that are representative of the two aforementioned families: HA1, which uses an LDPC library on an AVX512-accelerated Intel Xeon Gold 6240R CPU core @ 2.40GHz — we tested Intel FlexRAN’s and two different open-source library — and HA2, which is the GPU HA used before. Our results shed light on the opportunities to achieve HA diversity gains and the type of solutions required to pool these resources appropriately. For each test, we select an MCS $m \in M := \{0, 1, \dots, 27\}$, an SNR $s \in S := \{1, 2, \dots, 30\}$ dB,

and a bandwidth $b \in B := \{1, 2, \dots, 250\}$ RBs. Then, following 3GPP, we generate a random TB with a size given by b RBs with MCS m , and execute the downlink PHY pipeline, which yields the OFDM symbols of the constituent CBs. To emulate the wireless channel, we add AWGN noise with zero mean and the appropriate variance to attain the selected mean SNR s across all the symbols. Finally, we execute the uplink UL pipeline by offloading the LDPC decoding operation into the selected HA.

For each combination of MCS, bandwidth, and SNR, we generate 10 random TBs and measure the latency and energy consumption of the chosen HA.

4.1.2.2.1 Latency performance

Figure 19 shows the median latency performance of the GPU-based HA (HA₂), at the bottom, and the CPU pool (HA₁) running the Intel FlexRAN LDPC library at the top. We present results for all combinations from S and M and for subset $\{50, 100, 150, 200\}$ from B. We use a colored gradient to measure latency (in log scale) and blank cells when TBs cannot be decoded within a typical threshold of 10 iterations. Unsurprisingly, the GPU HA provides roughly an order of magnitude improvement in latency. However, CPUs can decode TBs within 3 ms, a common deadline, in a wide range of contexts, such as TBs modulated with a high MCS and less than 150 RBs.

Figure 19. Median latency when decoding TBs of different sizes (combinations of RBs and MCSs) under different SNR conditions with both CPU (Intel FlexRAN) and GPU acceleration. Log scale in the z-axis.

The figure also shows is determined mostly determined by the MCS and SNR of the soft bits received, which in turn determine the number of decoding iterations required for each CB.

4.1.2.2.2 Energy consumption

Figure 20 shows the energy consumed by the CPU and GPU LDPC processing. For the less demanding bandwidth setting in our dataset, the GPU HA consumes more than 28% of the energy required by the CPU. Yet, for the most exacting bandwidth configuration, the GPU HA consumes only around 71% more than the CPU HA. As discussed earlier, the latency provided by CPUs precludes their use for larger TBs; however, the remarkable advantages of CPUs in terms of both capital and operating (energy consumption) costs make CPUs particularly appealing to handle small or medium-sized TBs.

Figure 20. Median energy to decode TBs of different sizes (combinations of RBs and MCSs) under different SNR conditions with both CPU (Intel FlexRAN) and GPU acceleration. Log scale in the z-axis.

4.1.2.2.3 Library/driver implementation

We conclude this analysis with a final remark: the performance of an LDPC processor depends not only on the HA but also on the implementation of the library or the driver operating the HA. We show this in Figure 21, which compares the latency performance of Intel FlexRAN and two open-source libraries, “OS1” and “OS2” based on Open Air Interface and SRSRAN. The plot depicts substantial differences across libraries.

First, both FlexRAN and OS2 provide, on average, 4.3 times lower latency than OS1. This is explained because our OS1 library under test does not exploit SIMD acceleration.

Second, OS2 is unable to decode some high-MCS, high SNR TBs (see blank cells in the plot). The reason lies behind the 8-bit quantization used in this specific library to encode soft bits (a codification used by default in all three CPU HAs to expedite the work). We have repeated the experiments with 16-bit resolution and the processor can decode those TBs as expected at a large latency toll (see right plot).

Figure 21. Median processing latency for different TB sizes with 200 RBs under different SNR conditions using different CPU libraries. Log scale in the z-axis.

Finally, there are mild—yet relevant—differences in performance when comparing *decodable* TBs with FlexRAN and OS2. More specifically, FlexRAN outperforms OS2 by around 10% on average but by over 30% when considering TBs that require more than one iteration to decode (i.e., those that need more decoding effort), even though they both exploit SIMD. The reason is that all three libraries implement a different flavor of LDPC decoding (coincidentally, OS2 and our NVIDIA driver use the same approach), which renders a different number of decoding iterations in the face of noise.

4.1.2.3 O-RAN policies

In light of the above, we are interested in designing an AAL that (i) can share high-end HAs across multiple DUs to maximize their utilization and (ii) can exploit low-consuming CPUs when possible (during low-load instants) to reduce the system’s energy toll. And to this end, we need to augment the AAL with real-time control policies that can adapt swiftly to real workloads to attain the 5-nines reliability target.

To study this, we implemented O-RAN’s AAL in a server with two HAs used before — 16 cores from an Intel Xeon CPU (HA₁) and an NVIDIA GPU V100 (HA₂) — using Intel DPDK’s Wireless Baseband Device Library (BBDev). Like DPDK’s solutions for Ethernet, BBDev provides an abstraction for wireless processing tasks by means of devices. O-RAN LPUs can be implemented as BBDev devices. Consequently, we implemented an LPU for HA₁ using the publicly available Intel FlexRAN library and an LPU for HA₂ using a driver that we built from scratch (~1K lines of C code) and a proprietary LDPC decoder. Moreover, we conservatively sized each LPU queue to accommodate every TB that could possibly be processed in time in the most demanding case.

In O-RAN, each O-DU subscribes to the desired HAs, and then they enqueue TBs to its *local* LPUs. HAs can be shared but there is no coordination between DUs, which is inefficient. To show this, we deployed a variable number of 100-MHz 5G DUs in our AAL, each emulating five UEs with the “5G” demand profile introduced earlier and set $D = 3$ ms. TBs violating deadline D are discarded, losing throughput. The signals demodulated by each DU are encoded as LLRs (soft bits) in real-time and stored in a memory pool (*mempool*) as BBdev *test* vectors to be allocated to an LPU using some *policy*.

Figure 22. Network throughput and energy consumption per bit in a heterogeneous O-Cloud for a different number of vDUs hosting “5G” UEs. Deadline $D=3$ ms.

4.1.2.3.1 Coordination

The first policy, “O-Greedy”, follows a simple heuristic: given a TB, the DU selects the fastest HA, HA₂, as long as its queue is not full; otherwise, it selects HA₁. Figure 22(left) shows the system reliability as a function of the aggregated network demand. Reliability quickly drops when the demand goes beyond 400 Mb/s (~100 UEs) as HA₂ queues saturate, thus frequently missing deadlines.

We now test an approach called “O-MWT” (O-RAN Minimum Waiting Time). For every TB, the corresponding DU computes the completion time at each HA by *looking at the occupancy of its own queues*, and then selects the fastest LPU. Note that this requires DUs to have perfect knowledge of each TB processing latency *a priori*. Hence, to implement this approach, we simulate both HAs using the

dataset introduced before. Though this is not possible in practice, it illustrates the performance gain from exploiting queuing information, which in Figure 22 attains 18% more throughput and 10% less energy cost on average before reliability drops to 0%. In contrast to O-MWT, with "C-MWT" (Coordinated MWT) DUs consider each other's queues to calculate completion time. That is, C-MWT illustrates the advantages of *centralized coordination*, which, as shown in the figure, further increases reliability by 15% and reduces energy by 19% on average in the same scenarios.

4.1.2.3.2 Energy efficiency

C-MWT aims at minimizing latency. However, minimizing the latency of FEC operations has no benefit to the end-users' quality of experience as long as deadlines are met. Hence, we could exploit CPUs more than C-MWT to reduce energy consumption. To illustrate this, we simulate another heuristic called "C-EF" (Coordinated Energy-efficient First) that proceeds as follows. Given a TB, the DU calculates whether it could be processed on time by HA₁ (CPU pool), which is selected should this be the case; otherwise, the DU offloads the TB to HA₂. Like before, this is not a practical approach as it relies on information that is unknown *a priori*, but it is helpful to understand the potential gains of opportunistic offloading methods. As depicted in Figure 22, "C-EF" can save up to 80% of the energy cost for low-loaded scenarios without sacrificing reliability.

4.1.2.3.3 Energy efficiency

All of these policies are unable to meet the 5-nines reliability target given sufficiently large workloads. This is because the DUs' MAC-layer schedulers allocate radio resources unaware of the available computing capacity and the associated deadlines. Hence, we advocate for *data-driven, compute-aware radio scheduling mechanisms* that control congestion in LPU queues to guarantee timely processing in the AAL.

To stress this, we simulate "C-R-EF" (Coordinated Radio- controlling Energy-efficient First), a version of C-EF that, observing the future, does not schedule a radio grant if the associated TB cannot be processed in time. In this way, C-R-EF trades off radio resources that are *wasted* by the other policies in Figure 22 for reliability when the AAL gets congested. Indeed, "C-R-EF" meets the 5-nine reliability target at all times with an 18% lower energy cost than C-EF on average in the scenarios evaluated in the figure. Note that our analysis only considers the energy consumed by the AAL and ignores the energy wasted by the RU in transmitting data needlessly by all of the approaches except C-R-EF.

4.1.2.4 Conclusion

Based on the analysis presented in this section, we advocate for an approach that jointly (i) centralizes the allocation of processing tasks into shared HAs and (ii) imposes radio scheduling policies that are aware of the congestion in the AAL. This approach will be designed during Year 3 in WP3 and an empirical evaluation will be presented in D5.3, accordingly.

4.1.3 Application aware radio scheduling (A3)

Collected KPI	Justification
K9	The ability to classify traffic at the time scale of seconds allows scheduling the traffic in a better way than assigning network resources in a fixed way governed by some predefined policy. The performance of the best classification algorithms studied here is high enough to allow the system to work very close to the theoretically optimal performance.

In Section 4.3 of deliverable D3.1 [13] we discussed three methods to classify traffic based on the evolution of the RLC (radio link control) buffer: a threshold-based method (TB), a method based on K-nearest neighbors (KNN) and a method based on a feed-forward neural network (FFNN). We reported more detailed results in Section 4.1.3 of D5.1 [3]. In Section 2.3 of deliverable D3.2 [1] we introduced a method based on long short-term memory (LSTM), which we justified by arguing that the trends in the RLC buffer evolution (besides the absolute value of the RLC buffer values which the three methods from deliverable D3.1 also take into account) may bring valuable information in the classification process. An initial result discussed in deliverable D3.2 indicates that this is indeed the case. We also showed how the LSTM classifier learns by considering how the loss measured over the validation set (i.e., 20% of the training set) evolves as the training proceeds. In fact, this provides us with a criterion to stop the training way before over-training would risk hampering the performance.

Here we present a more thorough comparison of the performance of all four methods. We explored the parameter space of each of the methods to determine the optimal meta parameters (for KNN the optimal number of neighbors, for FFNN the number of hidden layers and the number of cells per layer and for LSTM the number of entries used as input and the number of entries used as output). For each of the configurations, we performed three runs: in each run, the split between the training set and the test set was randomly changed. This allows us to report on the confidence interval for each of the metrics: i.e., performance is always expressed as the "average of the metric \pm the standard deviation of the metric" in the tables below).

As performance metrics, we consider the following:

- The time to train the algorithm by running a number of times (i.e., number of epochs) through the training set. We performed all experiments on a Linux machine with 24 Xeon CPUs @ 2.30GHz using the python library TensorFlow for FFNN and LSTM; and the python library sklearn for KNN, both of which were configured to run in parallel on the 24 CPUs.
- The inference time for one classification. We inferred the classes for all samples in the test set in bulk and divided that time by the number of samples in the test set.
- The loss on the test set, which can be interpreted as the conditional entropy after classification or the average number of bits required to correct a misclassification. This value should be as far away as possible from the entropy in the test set (i.e., the number of bits required to encode the class of a signal without doing any classification, which is close to 2 bits, as there are 4 classes). The optimal value for this metric, i.e., 0 bits, is not reachable because there are always confusing signals, i.e., signals that could be associated with two or more classes.
- The probability of correct classification.

Table 9 and Table 10 show the results. It is clear that from the point of view of the correctness of the classification, LSTM performs the best, with FFNN as a close second. LSTM has a slight disadvantage in that it requires longer training time than FFNN.

Table 9: Optimal parameters, training time and inference time of the considered classifiers.

Method	Structure	Number of trainable parameters	Training time [sec]	Number of epochs to train	Inference time [msec]
TB	$F = 2$	-	73±3	-	0.80±0.03
KNN	$K = 3$	-	15±10	-	120.7±15.5
FFNN	$L = 5, C = 80$	192,885	345±50	11.3±1.2	7.8±2.5
LSTM	$I = 100, C = 100$	80,905	1337±221	53.0±8.7	6.8±0.2

Table 10: Conditional entropy and probability of correct classification of the considered classifiers.

Method	Structure	Conditional entropy	Probability estimated label is correct
TB	$F = 2$	0.63±0.01	0.685±0.003
KNN	$K = 3$	0.36±0.02	0.799±0.009
FFNN	$L = 5, C = 80$	0.24±0.02	0.916±0.002
LSTM	$I = 100, C = 100$	0.20±0.02	0.953±0.003

4.1.3.1 Conclusion

We compared the performance of the classification algorithms that we introduced in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2. We have shown that LSTM performs the best, provided that one is willing to take the longer training time into account.

4.1.4 ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs (A29)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	Thanks to the capability of adapting the instantaneous scheduling decision to the specific conditions, this solution is capable of fitting under the available computing capacity, modeled by the congestion factor parameter β
K2	The same parameter β can be interpreted as the available computing capacity at the edge. Setting this value allows configuring the available capacity.
K4	By operating under the capacity β , the Operator can save OPEX over time in a controllable manner.
K5	The system is trained to never exceed the decoding time under all circumstances, increasing the reliability of the system.

In this section, we evaluate the algorithm discussed in Section 2.5 of D3.1 against the vanilla radio resource scheduler available in srsRAN, which implements a Round Robin Policy, which we consider as a general benchmark for commercial state-of-the-art radio schedulers. We evaluate our algorithm in a

single UE scenario that transmits uplink UDP data at full buffer speed. We implemented this algorithm using the virtualized testbed presented in Section 3.1.1 (T6)

Figure 23. The reward obtained by our algorithm under High (left, avg. 30 dB), Medium (center, avg. 17 dB), and Low (right, avg. 11 dB) scenarios for different congestions β .

We depict in Figure 23 the reward collected by our system over time, for different SNRs and β . We observe that it could converge to the steady state policy within 50 episodes. This corresponds to a few hundred of ms since we define each episode as 64 TTIs. However, different SNR levels yield different convergence points: with worse channel conditions the adopted TBS is reduced to match the SNR and hence can carry fewer data bits. In low SNR, the difference between different values of β is reduced.

Figure 24. The percentage of traffic served by a gNB running our algorithm ATHENA and the Baseline algorithm for different congestions β .

We now compare the performance of our algorithm against the Baseline srsRAN implementation in terms of achieved scheduling performance. We do so by sweeping the SNR ranges from 5 to 35 dB, while the UE is at full buffer. We run a 500s UL traffic generation, and we plot in Fig. 6 the amount of data received correctly (*i.e.*, with a successful CRC check and T_{dec} below 3ms) by our algorithm and the baseline. When $\beta = 0$, the Baseline scheduler does not suffer frame losses due to deadline violation. We can observe that both strategies successfully process 100% of the data, but they do that in different ways. While the baseline processes favor lower TBS, as just 20% of the traffic is handled when the SNR is high (and higher TBS are possible), our algorithm provides a more linear spread of the selected TBS vs the channel condition. When CPU impairments are introduced ($\beta=0.8$ and $\beta=1$), the baseline cannot cope anymore with the data transmission, processing at most 60% and 40% of the data, respectively. This loss is huge if we consider that with just very few missed frames, real systems lose synchronization [14].

4.2 NI for VNF placement and control

Evaluation E2 focuses on NI solutions that support network slice management & orchestration operations. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E2 via activities A4-A8 and A30. Table 11 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate progress and main innovations of such activities.

Table 11. List of activities for E2.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Progress
A4	AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration	E2	T5	K1, K4	K1	4	Executed	100%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Energy-driven O-RAN orchestration (non-real-time RIC)								
A5	AI-aided RAN/edge orchestration	E2	T5	K1, K4	K1	4	No	50%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Joint Energy-driven O-RAN orchestration (non-real-time RIC) and AI service								
A6	Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing	E2	D10	K1	K1	3	No	90%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Optimisation of edge computing system deployments exploiting variability								

A7	Combining VNFs at the edge	E2	None ⁴	K1, K2	K1, K2	3	Yes	100%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Adaptation of VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources								
A8	AI Enhanced MANO	E2	T8	K3, K8	K3	5	Yes	60%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Automated resource reallocation for supporting critical services								
A30	Placement and routing for network services	E2	None ⁵	K2	K2	2	No	100%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Automated resource allocation for new services								

4.2.1 AI-aided energy-driven RAN orchestration (A4)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	This activity evaluates two solutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BP-vRAN, which balances network performance and power consumption. More specifically, we show that we can save 12.5% of power without sacrificing uplink performance - SBP-vRAN, which maximizes network performance given any hard constraint on power consumption.
K4	The OPEX savings achieved by this solution come exclusively from the energy savings explained in K1.

The motivation for this activity was presented in Section 4.1.4 of D5.1 [3], and a formal description of two related problems was presented in Section 2.3 of D4.2 [2]:

- BP-vRAN: The goal is to balance network performance and power consumption.
- SBP-vRAN: The goal is to maximize throughput subject to hard power consumption constraints.

The document described two solutions to these problems based on Bayesian learning. In the following, we will summarize a thorough experimental evaluation to assess the performance of these solutions.

Figure 25. Experimental vBS and UE testbed.

Our testbed is shown in Figure 25 and comprises a vBS, the user equipment (UE)⁶, and a digital power meter. Both the vBS and the UE consist of an Ettus Research USRP B210 as RU, srsNB/srsUE (from srsRAN suite) as BBU for both the eNB and UE, and two small factor general-purpose PCs (Intel NUCs with CPU i7-8559U@2.70GHz) deploying each respective BBU and the near-RT RIC of Figure 26. The vBS and the UE are connected using SMA cables with 20dB attenuators, and we adjust the gain of the RU's RF chains to attain different SNR values. Without loss in generality, we select a 10-MHz band that renders a maximum capacity of roughly 32 and 23 Mbps in DL and UL, respectively. We use the power meter GW-Instek GPM-8213 to measure the power consumption of the BBU and the RU by plugging their power supply cable to a GW-Instek Measuring adapter GPM-001. Finally, we have integrated E2's interface and the ability to enforce control policies *on the fly* (see Section 2.3 of D4.2 [2]) in srsNB.

⁴ Activities A7 makes use of randomly generated data to validate the solution.

⁵ Simulation based on python code

⁶ We use one UE emulating the load of multiple users.

Figure 26: O-RAN compliant system architecture and workflow.

We use three auxiliary PCs (not shown in the picture) hosting the non-RT RIC and the network traffic end hosts, which use *mgen*⁷. We have finally implemented the O1 interface (Figure 26) using the USB-based power meter SCPI (Standard Commands for Programmable Instruments) interface concerning power consumption measurements and a REST interface for the remainder. A final remark is that our RU (USRP B210) does not integrate a variable power amplifier. Instead, it uses a fixed power amplifier consuming 3W and a variable attenuator for power calibration. To compensate for this, we post-process the power measurements to include a variable RU consumption according to a linear model based on previous works and a 3W cap.

For our evaluation, we consider $|\mathcal{P}^{dl}| = 20$, $|\mathcal{M}^{dl}| = 28$, $|\mathcal{M}^{ul}| = 24$, and $|\mathcal{A}^{dl}| = |\mathcal{A}^{ul}| = 11$. In consequence, the size of the control set is $|\mathcal{X}| \approx 1.6 \cdot 10^6$. Note that, for a decision period of 10s, we would need 185 days to explore every control policy in \mathcal{X} once, which highlights the need for a data-efficient learning strategy. To visualize our results, we use lines representing the average along 10 independent runs and a colored shadow representing the area within the 10th and 90th percentiles.

4.2.1.1 Convergence evaluation

We start off by evaluating the convergence of BP-vRAN and SBP-vRAN. To this end, we consider the special case of a single context and observe their performance over time with no prior training up till they converge to yield optimal policies. We select a context with high SNR = 35 dB (CQI = 15) in DL and UL and high traffic demands (relative to our testbed’s capacity) equal to 25 and 20 Mbps for DL and UL, respectively. Figure 27 and Figure 28 show the temporal evolution of different metrics for both algorithms during 150 orchestration periods.

Figure 27. Convergence rate evaluation of BP-vRAN for different configurations of the objective function.

Let us first discuss the results of BP-vRAN in Figure 27. We observe that the power consumption and throughput are lower for lower values of b , e.g., 12.5% power drop and 33.75% throughput drop between $b = 25$ and $b = 16$. Note that the meaning of the parameter b is described in D4.2 [2] along with the algorithm design. Briefly, higher values of b favor throughput performance over power consumption and viceversa. Note that $b = 16$ only penalizes DL throughput. This is because it imposes a mild power requirement, and hence BP-vRAN only sacrifices transmission power, which reduces DL SNR and thus DL throughput. Lower values of b force BP-vRAN to sacrifice UL throughput too.

⁷ <https://www.nrl.navy.mil/itd/ncs/products/mgen>.

Figure 28. Convergence rate evaluation of SBP-vRAN for different values of the power budget P_{max} .

Concerning SBP-vRAN, we evaluate different values of P_{max} up to $P_{max} = 20$, which is an upper bound for the power consumption irrespective of the policy and the context. The results in Figure 28 depict how SBP-vRAN learns to use configurations within the power budget with high probability, sacrificing throughput when so required. Note that, in all the cases, SBP-vRAN always selects policies very close to P_{max} . This is because the optimal policy, i.e., the one that maximizes throughput, usually requires consuming all the P_{max} budget. To this end, SBP-vRAN gradually expands its safe set close to P_{max} and therefore an explicit strategy to expand the safe set is not needed. Specifically, Figure 29 shows that all the controls are safe for $P_{max} = 20$, with 15.4% and 53.2% less safe policies for $P_{max} = 14$ and $P_{max} = 12$, respectively. As expected, lower values of P_{max} incur a smaller safe policy set.

Figure 29. Time evolution of safe set size of SBP-vRAN for different power budget values P_{max} .

We conclude this evaluation with the observation that despite using a large set of policies \mathcal{X} , both algorithms converge in, at most, 30 orchestration periods. This result highlights the *data efficiency* nature of our solutions, which are able to find optimal policies by observing only a very small subset of \mathcal{X} .

4.2.1.2 Performance in real network contexts

Next, we evaluate the performance of BP-vRAN and SBP-vRAN using a realistic one-day traffic pattern from (Figure 30, top). Concerning channel quality, we consider a worst-case pattern emulating UEs with high mobility (Figure 30, bottom), which compromises network capacity (well below the demand). Due to the granularity of our traffic pattern dataset, we set the orchestration period length to 5 minutes in these experiments (note there is no loss in generality). We run our algorithms for two days and present results of the second day to focus on the attained system performance. Their convergence, evaluated in the previous subsection, takes just a few periods (well within a day). This is possible because the knowledge acquired by our algorithms for one context is transferred to other similar contexts. That is, after a few periods, the algorithms select efficient policies even for unseen contexts. To remove the clutter introduced by the high SNR variability under evaluation, each point in Figure 31 and Figure 32 corresponds to the average across all the points of a SNR cycle (see Figure 30, bottom).

Figure 30. One-day traffic pattern (top) and worst-case channel quality pattern (bottom).

Figure 31 shows the total power consumption (a) and the evolution of throughput along the day (b) using BP-vRAN and different configurations of the objective function. We observe that the power consumption evolves with the traffic demand and with the selected value of b . For instance, when $b = 16$, the achieved throughput is penalized in favor of better power consumption during daylight, but no performance degradation is required during the night (between 2 am and 7 am). Similarly, Figure 32 shows the performance of SBP-vRAN under the same scenarios. Specifically, SBP-vRAN manages to satisfy the power budget constraint with probabilities 0.99 and 0.93 when P_{\max} equals 14 and 12, respectively, while maximizing throughput (which we calculated through an exhaustive search).

Figure 31. Performance evaluation of BP-vRAN throughout one day.

Figure 32. Performance evaluation of SBP-vRAN throughout one day.

4.2.1.3 Comparison with other approaches

We complete our evaluation by comparing our approaches with a Reinforcement Learning-based solution. Specifically, we use a deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) implemented by an actor-critic deep neural networks (NNs) design. We mildly modified the architecture of a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) proposed in previous works such as [15] with a *sigmoid function* for the actor's output, which improved performance in our setup and optimized all the hyper-parameters to minimize convergence time. Our experiments show that the DDPG converges to the same solutions as our proposals but with important convergence flaws. To illustrate them, we compare the learning process of the DDPG against our approaches.

We first configure the DDPG to balance network throughput and power consumption (as BP-vRAN does). Figure 33.a shows the evolution of the objective function along time for both BP-vRAN and the DDPG for different values of b , as before. Notably, the DDPG converges to the same optimal policy learned by BP-vRAN but has to invest one order of magnitude longer time. The main reason is that our approach infers correlations in the objective function over the context-action space more efficiently than an NN-based approach and finds optimal policies for unseen context-action pairs. This highlights the *data-efficiency* nature of our solution. It is also worth reminding that, differently from our benchmark, BP-vRAN has mathematical guarantees in performance.

In order to implement the constrained problem solved by SBP-vRAN, we configure the DDPG to optimize a step function that takes the value of the reward when the observed power is below P_{\max} , and the minimum reward value otherwise. Figure 33.b shows the evolution over time of the power consumption and the associated throughput performance of the vBS for SBP-vRAN and DDPG. We begin the experiment with a power constraint equal to 15W and suddenly change it to 13W at decision period 2,000.

Our results render three observations: (i) SBP-vRAN attains considerable convergence improvements over its benchmark (roughly, an order of magnitude). (ii) SBP-vRAN is unaffected by a sudden change in the power constraint; note that it only requires the change of P_{\max} . Conversely, DDPG needs to change the configuration of the step function, which forces it to restart its learning process from scratch, failing the hard constraint until decision period 3500, approximately. (iii) DDPG cannot perform safe exploration: it must use policies that violate the power constraint to learn so. On the other hand, our approach computes the uncertainty of each estimation, which allows us to implement safe exploration and satisfy the constraint with high probability.

Figure 33. Comparison of (a) BP-vRAN and (b) SBP-vRAN with DDPG-based approaches.

4.2.2 AI-aided RAN/edge orchestration (A5)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	This KPI has not been collected yet
K2	This KPI has not been collected yet.

The motivation for this activity was presented in Section 4.1.5 of D5.1 [3]. As explained in Section 2.4 of D4.2 [2], the solution to the problem defined in this activity will be presented in the upcoming deliverable for WP4 (namely, D4.3). Consequently, the associated results will be presented in the upcoming deliverable for this work package (namely, D5.3).

4.2.3 Energy-aware deployment of VNFs for generic Edge computing (A6)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	We calculate the VNF energy saving using the GEC dataset. So, we can analyze the influence of the specific VNF on energy consumption.

Section 3.3.3 from D3.2 [1] presented the latest updates of the SAVRUS approach. Specifically, we contributed four algorithms to the energy-aware orchestration of VNFs supported by Software Product Lines (SPLs). In this section, we reported the results of the empirical validation of these algorithms using Research Questions (RQ). The general goal of these RQs is to compare these algorithms' capabilities and reasoning times with others from the state of the art. The concrete research questions are:

- RQ1: What is the level of empirical support that the state of the art currently has to represent and provide reasoning to quality-measured VNFs?
- RQ2: Is our CT framework for SPLs a feasible alternative to analyze and optimize VNFs orchestration?
- RQ3: How do the alternative tools scale for the complete set of quality-aware reasoning operations present in SDNs systems?

4.2.3.1 Methodology and setup

Table 12 shows the 5 SPLs we have used for validation. They are all real-world SPLs with different properties (e.g., size) to reinforce the results and conclusions. As far as we know, our approach is the only work that applies SPLs to SDN/NFV domain, so we had to use models from other domains as validation objects. Also, quality-measured virtualized network use cases are not available in the literature, so 3 SPLs are from different domains. However, they are third-party use cases, well-known in the literature, and they share specific quality-reasoning requirements like Cost in \$ and Battery minimization. For illustration purposes, we will provide several examples based on a reduced SPL of our Virtual Network Orchestration System represented by the VNS model of Figure 34.

Table 12. Variability details generated with reporting operations in CQL IDE of the SPLs with quality attributes analyzed.

SPL	Description	Features	Constraints	Configurations	Quality attributes
Pizza	Italian Vendor Machine [16]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 12 • Numerical: 1 	Empty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 42 • Measured: 84 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature Level: (1) Cost $\in (5.25)\\$: Function Addition • Configuration Level: (2) Time $\in (1, 10^3)$seconds
Truck	Truck Factory [17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 33 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 10 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 234 • Measured: 234 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature Level: 1. Size $\in [0,10]$metres²: Function: Product
JHipster	Software Generator [18]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 45 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 13 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 26256 • Measured: 105024 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature Level: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Usability $\in (0,10)$: Function: Addition 2. Battery $\in (0,20)$: Function: Addition 3. Footprint $\in (0,10)$: Function: Addition • Configuration level: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Compileable $\in [true, false]$
(1) VNS and (2) Full VNS	Virtual Network System	Figure 34 version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 18 • Numerical: 1 Full version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 40 • Numerical: 3 	Figure 34 version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 1 • Arithmetic: 1 Full version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 63 • Arithmetic: 4 	Figure 34 version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 63 • Measured: 315 Full version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 2130000 • Measured: 10650000 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature Level: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dependency $\in [L, M, H]$: Function: Maximum 2. Usability $\in (1,10)$: Function: Mean 3. Security $\in [L, M, H]$: Function: Minimum • Configuration level: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Time $\in (1, 10^3)$seconds 5. Energy $\in (1, 10^3)$

We present them ordered by the size of their configuration space. The smallest is *Pizza*, taken from [19] and including the QAs additive Cost in \$ at the feature level and Time in seconds at the configuration level. With 6 times its configurations space, we have *Truck*, which we extracted from [20] and extended with random values of a multiplicative Size in square meters as a feature-level QA. A larger case with a measured space 449 times bigger is *JHipster*, which already included the QAs: Usability, Battery, and memory Footprint as additive QAs at the feature level, and Compileable, a binary QA (i.e., yes or no) at the configuration-level. The largest model is the complete version of the one represented in Figure 34: the DAEMON's VNS SPL. For completeness, we also included the reduced version represented in Figure 34. We distinguish them as *FullVNS* and *VNS* respectively. *FullVNS* comprises 40 boolean and 3 numerical features, 64 logic and 4 arithmetic constraints, and space of 2+ million configurations. Its QAs are the same as in Figure 34; consequently, its QAs space is of 10+ million configurations measurements.

Considering our analysis summarised in Table 12, we selected the most complete open-source tools for each group of reasoning operations: (1) ClaferMoo [21] due to its support of feature-level QAs and certain flexibility to define functions; (2) AAFM Python framework for its speed at the cost of not supporting QAs, (3) SATIBEA [22] as the representative of IBEA based genetic algorithm for optimization due to its documentation and user support, and finally (4) CQL IDE, the state-of-the-art CT tool. The different models and datasets are available at <https://github.com/danieljmg/SPLC22>.

We ran the presented SPLs and tools on a desktop computer comprising an Intel(R) Core i7-4790 CPU@3.60 GHz processor with 16 GB of memory RAM and an SSD running an up-to-date Windows 10 H22H1 X86_64 with the latest supported versions of the tools and shared libraries (e.g., Java JDK 18.0.2). Besides double-checking the internal statistics of each tool, we measured reasoning time with the Windows PowerShell Measure-Command. Initial JAVA virtual machine overhead was purposely removed, and it is not affecting the time results.

- Truck: Minimize $Size_1 * Size_2$
- JHipster: Minimize total Battery + total Footprint
- VNSs: Minimize energy rate

Table 14. Averaged performance in seconds of aggregation operations in state-of-the-art reasoners for Table 12 models. For unsupported advanced aggregations, we switched them for addition and tagged their performance with an asterisk.

Reasoner	ClaferMoo				AAFM Python Framework				CQL IDE			
SPL:	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster
Unconstrained	0.9 5 s	+1.8 2 36 s	2.1 5 s	2.99 s	1.67 s	*1.79 2.3 3 s	*1.85 s	1.78 s	0.2 7 s	0.39 211 s	0.4 2 s	2.68 s
Constrained	0.9 7 s	*1.89 237 s	2.1 7 s	3.01 s	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	0.2 7 s	0.4 2 12 s	0.4 2 s	2.69 s
Range	0.9 5 s	*1.8 2 32 s	2.1 5 s	2.94 s	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	0.2 7 s	0.41 212 s	0.4 3 s	2.69 s
Mean:	0.9 57 s	*1.83 235 s	2.1 6 s	2.98 s	1.67 s	*1.79 2.3 3 s	*1.85 s	1.78 s	0.2 7 s	0.4 2 12 s	0.4 23 s	2.69 s

In this case, an asterisk indicates that the reasoner did not support modeling configuration-level QAs. In that case, we provided random values to allow some level of comparison. Nevertheless, ClaferMoo and SATIBEA do not currently support weighted and new domain objectives. SATIBEA sampling parameters are configured as suggested in the documentation: 20000 evolutions [22].

Table 15. Averaged performance in seconds of optimization operations in state-of-the-art reasoners for Table 12 models. We tagged the performance with an asterisk if the reasoner ignores quality attributes at the configuration level.

Reasoner	ClaferMoo				AAFM Python Framework				CQL IDE			
SPL:	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster	Pizza	VNS Full	Truck	JHipster
Min/Maximize	*0.98 s	*1.87 3 44 s	2.23 s	*4.36 s	*1.67 s	*1.79 2 s	1.85 s	*1.78 s	0.3 8 s	0.52 274 s	0.6 8 s	3.48 s
Multiobjective	*1.02 s	*1.97 3 55 s	2.38 s	*4.5 s	*1.85 s	*2.01 2 .1 s	2.03 s	*1.95 s	0.4 2 s	0.67 312 s	0.7 8 s	3.95 s
Weighted	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	0.4 2 s	0.68 317 s	0.8 2 s	4.02 s
New Domain	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	Unsupported	0.4 1 s	0.63 274 s	0.7 3 s	3.47 s
Mean:	*1 s	*1.92 3 49s	2.31 s	*4.43 s	*1.76 s	*1.9 2. 05 s	1.94s	*1.87 s	0.4 1	0.63 294 s	0.7 5 s	3.73 s

4.2.3.3 Discussion and Scalability Results

In this subsection, we answer the RQs by considering the results of the previous tables. The goal of RQ1 is to assess if we can successfully apply SPL tools to reason about quality-aware orchestration of VNFs, and in general, to the SDN/NFV domain. Only those SPLs tools that include numerical features, complex constraints and support reasoning and optimization of configuration-level QA apply to this domain. While in the current situation, we find academic tools for very specific and basic reasoning, in practice, the network industry will discard them as they are not enough by themselves. Additionally, those tools are not directly configurable or extendable, and there is where CQL IDE with our CT operations highlights. **The RQ1 answer is that the best current tools could be viable if they are extended like we are doing with CQL IDE, that is, if they provide a unified solution beyond boolean features, logic constraints, additive attributes, and max/minimize optimization.**

The RQ2 answer is that our algorithms feasibly extend CQL IDE for all the quality-aware operations, and hence it provides support for managing QoS in VNFs orchestration. Further, we should mention that CT knowledge is uncommon in the industry, which is required to properly adjust such flexible tools.

Regarding run times, if we are only analyzing SDNs variability, AAFM Python Framework is the fastest with a worst performance of 60 seconds. Similarly, for simple aggregation and optimization functions, SATIBEA

is the fastest. This was expected, as it always works with the same number of samples, and increasing them is not translated to higher accuracy, as is stated in the literature [22]. ClaferMoo tends to be the slowest, sometimes due to how their reasoning algorithms work, like counting by enumeration [23]. However, it covers more operations than the average. Nevertheless, we consider CQL IDE the proper alternative for the DAEMON project, as it is among the fastest ones while supporting all sorts of quality-aware reasoning. In summary, and **answering RQ3, all the solutions scale linearly**, but without always being the fastest, CQL IDE shines for its large application domain.

4.2.3.4 *Threats to validity*

Internal Validity. To control randomness, we repeated the experiments 97 times and averaged the results for a confidence level of 95% with a 10% margin of error [24]. Additionally, we are aware of the need to extend this validation with the tool's accuracy based on their specific reasoning techniques. Nevertheless, the aim of this work is to provide the means to tackle the complete VNFs reasoning casuistic and not to provide a more accurate alternative to partially capable approaches. Consequently, we consider the evaluation sufficient for its purpose.

External Validity. One could argue that not all the evaluated SPLs are NFVs, but well-known models with registered complex quality measurements are rare in the SDN literature. Consequently, by choosing the real-world SPLs of Table 12, we pretended to cover a variety of properties, QAs and functions commonly found in VNF cases. Nonetheless, we are aware that they do not cover every possible casuistic individually. While one could claim that large spaces are not enough and colossal spaces should be tested, we should mention that larger spaces are very rare for VNF orchestrators. The problem in SDN systems is the complexity of the reasoning and not the size of it. Testing our algorithms with just one CT reasoner could be another threat. The problem is that CT tools are rare due to the intrinsic abstraction and knowledge requirement.

4.2.4 Combining VNFs at the edge (A7)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	In order to compute the energy consumption, we use an energy model that we presented in D3.2 to measure the energy of different configurations of the Planetarium. We obtain the energy saving by measuring the differences in energy consumption between the different configurations.
K2	The saving of computational resources of the edge is directly related to the savings on energy consumption.

In Section 2.1.3 of Deliverable 4.2, we presented HADES, an extension of OSM that enables the placement and configuration of VNFs/KNFs and their subsequent resource allocation and deployment at the edge, minimizing energy consumption and ensuring the quality of service. In this deliverable, the results of the experiment validate this proposal.

4.2.4.1 *Case study: augmented reality services*

As a case study, we have implemented PlanetARium, an application that uses augmented reality (AR) services to display virtual planets, constellations, etc., according to the information obtained from a camera. This application is designed to be used for academic purposes. AR applications are widely used in edge computing approaches due to their inherent collaborative properties in uplink data collection, computing at the edge, and downlink data delivery. AR applications are computationally intensive and delay-sensitive. In addition, processing all the information on devices with low computational capacity is prohibitively expensive because it would affect users' expectations regarding QoS [25].

PlanetARium comprises several interconnected microservices, each being a KNF of the same SFC (see Figure 35). The desired QoS stipulated by the infrastructure manager in the deployment module is 15 FPS. Concretely, the KNFs that form the SFC are the following:

- **Video capturer (KNF 1):** captures video from a camera and adapts its resolution to the one selected by the user. This KNF requires a node with a camera.
- **Feature Communicator (KNF 2):** receives the video stream and converts it to black-and-white video for easy element detection.
- **Filter Selector (KNF 3):** applies a filter to reduce the brightness of the received video and a blur, assimilating the image to a night sky for a more immersive experience.
- **Planet Tracker (ArUco Detector, KNF 4):** searches for ArUco codes in the received video, identifying each one and determining its coordinates.
- **Galaxy Tracker (QR Detector, KNF 5):** searches for QR codes in the received video. Once identified, it obtains their coordinates and sends them to the visualizer.

- **Visualizer (KNF 6):** receives the processed video stream and the coordinates of planets and galaxies. It then overlays the corresponding virtual elements on the video and creates a server accessible through a browser.

Figure 35. Service function chain of PlanetARium.

All tasks run as Docker containers and communicate through sockets. For video capture and element detection, PlanetARium uses the open source tool OpenCV⁸ for Python 3, while for 3D element rendering NodeJS and Three JS. Concerning their requirements in terms of RAM and disk, they are obtained using the Linux command `htop` and `Docker Stats`⁹. To ensure the desired QoS, we extract the computational cost and amount of data to transmit for one task iteration. Knowing the time it takes for the deployment to perform a complete iteration (i.e., to execute each task once) allows us to see the number of iterations per second (15, in our case, 0.067 seconds per iteration as the maximum). However, the same task may require a different number of cycles for two other devices and, to a lesser extent, vary between iterations (e.g., due to different inputs). Thus, we measure 2000 iterations of each task (using different inputs) for each node and establish an average number of CPU cycles and an average amount of data transmitted. This way, bias could exist by considering only one input type for each task. We use the Linux tool `perf` to obtain the computational cost and a traffic sniffer to get the amount of data transmitted between nodes. PlanetARium KNFs do not reserve or limit node bandwidth.

4.2.4.2 Experiments on energy saving

To analyze the reduction in energy consumption obtained through our proposal, we compare the energy consumption of the default Kubernetes deployment with that of HADES for the infrastructure and application presented in previous sections. For this purpose, we will consider the deployment of PlanetARium in four different scenarios: in Cluster 1, in Cluster 2, in Cluster 3, and in the complete infrastructure (Clusters 1-3). In Scenarios 1-3, we use the default Kubernetes scheduler (Kube-scheduler) and HADES. At the same time, in the fourth one, we will perform the deployment only with HADES (OSM does not allow considering more than one cluster by itself). Finally, we will measure the energy consumption of the nodes before and after deploying the application, thus obtaining the deployment energy consumption. To evaluate the QoS of the deployment, we introduce an on-screen frame counter to check if the deployment complies with the QoS requirement of 15 FPS. For a fair comparison of results, all tests were performed at the exact location and on the same day, under the same temperature conditions and node status. Figure 36 shows the resulting KNF assignments.

Scenario 1 (Cluster 1): Kube-scheduler assigns KNFs 1-4 to Node 3 and KNFs 5-6 to Node 4. HADES opts for giving KNFs 1 and 5 to Node 2, KNFs 2-3 and 6 to Node 5 and KNF 4 to Node 4. Note that HADES assigns KNF 1, which requires a camera, to Node 2 because the Node 2 camera supports video capture at 15 FPS (the minimal QoS desired); the same check would be performed for any other peripheral that could compromise the QoS. Regarding energy consumption, the base consumption (before the application deployment) of Cluster 1 is 77.9 W, and 92.2 W after the PlanetARium deployment. Therefore, the application EC with Kube-scheduler is 14.3 W. When deployed with HADES, the energy consumption after the deployment drops to 85.7 W, which means an application EC of 7.8 W. Regarding QoS, both deployments meet the non-functional requirement of 15 FPS. It is crucial to allocate the right resources to each KNF to achieve this. Lines 2-5 of Table 16 contain the resource allocation of HADES for Scenario 1. As HADES does, Kubernetes does not set a maximum resource usage margin (so QoS cannot be assured as deployments increase).

Scenario 2 (Cluster 2): Kube-scheduler deploys KNFs 1-4 in Node 7 and KNFs 5-6 in Node 8. On the other hand, HADES assigns KNFs 1-2, 5-6 to Node 6, while KNFs 3-4 to Node 8. The base energy consumption of this cluster is 76.9 W, increasing to 91.6 W after the deployment using Kube-scheduler. Thus, the application energy consumption is 14.7 W. As for deployment with HADES, the energy consumption is 84.8 W, resulting in an application EC of 7.9 W. Concerning QoS, both deployments meet the QoS of 15 FPS established in the configuration phase. Lines 6-9 of Table 16 show the HADES resource allocation.

⁸ <https://docs.opencv.org/4.x/>

⁹ <https://docs.docker.com/>

Figure 36. Task assignment.

Table 16. HADES deployment of PlanetARium.

		KNF 1	KNF 2	KNF 3	KNF 4	KNF 5	KNF 6
Scenario 1	Node	2	5	5	4	2	5
	CPU limit (m)	400-500	400-500	600-700	1400-1500	1200-1300	400-500
	RAM Limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52	42-52
	Reduction on energy consumption	45.4%					
Scenario 2	Node	6	6	8	8	6	6
	CPU limit (m)	400-500	300-400	200-300	1400-1500	1200-1300	200-300
	RAM Limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52	42-52
	Reduction on energy consumption	46.7%					
Scenario 3	Node	9	11	11	10	9	11
	CPU limit (m)	400-500	400-500	600-700	1400-1500	1200-1300	400-500
	RAM Limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52	42-52

	Reduction on energy consumption	The OSM deployment does not meet the QoS					
Scenario 4	Node	2	2	2	8	6	6
	CPU limit (m)	400-500	300-400	400-500	1400-1500	1200-1300	200-300
	RAM Limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52	42-52
	Reduction on energy consumption	49.6% / 51%					

Scenario 3 (Cluster 3): Kube-scheduler assigns KNF 1 to Node 9, KNFs 2-3, 5-6 to Node 10 and KNF 4 to Node 11. HADES opts for giving KNFs 1 and 5 to Node 9, KNFs 2-3 and 6 to Node 11, and KNF 4 to Node 10 (see Figure 36). The base energy consumption of Cluster 3 is 14.9 W, which grows to 20.7 W with the default OSM deployment, meaning an application EC of 5.8 W. With HADES, the energy consumption after deployment is 22.6 W, representing an application energy consumption of 7.7 W, an increase of 1.9 W over the default OSM deployment. Comparing the two deployments is not fair, as the Kubernetes deployment does not meet the expected QoS; FPS fluctuates between 3 and 11. This is because Kubernetes assigned the most CPU-demanding task (KNF 4, see Figure 36) to the least CPU-powerful node (Node 11), causing a bottleneck. On the other hand, the HADES deployment meets the expected QoS (resource allocation is shown in lines 10-13 of Table 16).

Scenario 4 (Clusters 1-3): HADES assigns KNFs 1-3 to Node 2, KNFs 5 and 6 to Node 6 and KNF 4 to Node 8 (see Figure 36). The whole infrastructure, considering all clusters, has a base energy consumption of 169.7 W, which rises to 176.9 W after the deployment of PlanetARium. Consequently, the application consumes 7.2 W. Concerning QoS, the HADES deployment meets the expected frame rate of 15 FPS; lines 14-17 of Table 16 contain the resource allocation in the case of HADES.

Figure 37 collects the energy consumption obtained for the different scenarios. Experiments reveal that the HADES deployments have reduced the energy consumption compared with the Kube-scheduler in all the scenarios considered in this work for the same QoS (Scenarios 1,2 and 4). Specifically, for Scenario 1, the application energy consumption is 14.3 W when deploying the application using Kube-scheduler, being 7.8 W with HADES. Therefore, obtaining a reduction in energy consumption of 6,4 W means a decrease of 45.4%. For Scenario 2, the application energy consumption is 14.7 W, deploying PlanetARium with Kube-scheduler and 7.9 W with HADES, resulting in an energy consumption reduction of 6 W (46.7%). In Scenario 4, the application's energy consumption is 7.2 W, the most energy-efficient deployment. This energy consumption represents a 49.6% reduction in EC compared to deployment using Kube-scheduler in Scenario 1 and 51% for Scenario 2---the scenarios in which the frame rate with Kube-scheduler is as desired. Likewise, it has been proved that the allocation of resources made by HADES has fulfilled the minimum QoS of 15 FPS established in all cases. At the same time, the deployment of the Kube-scheduler in Scenario 3 did not achieve that purpose.

Figure 37. Energy consumption for the different scenarios.

4.2.5 AI-Enhanced MANO (A8)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	We measure the response time of the AI-enhanced MANO algorithm, which is the average latency between a request to the MANO algorithm and the response of the MANO algorithm. Initial validation of the proposed algorithm illustrates a response time of the AI algorithm of about 280 - 330ms.

K8	We measure the response time of the application, which is the delay for the whole request and response process. Not collected yet.
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This activity targets the development and experimental assessment of a platform for AI-supported MANO. Currently, the work has focused on the integration of the components of the platform towards deploying a comprehensive and flexible architecture that will enable structured MANO tests in the presence of NI. The AI-enhanced MANO solution is deployed on a set of servers on which the OSM and OpenStack are deployed. To enable intelligence at the orchestration and management level, multiple interfaces with different components are used. Specifically, the connection with Open-Source MANO has been enabled through the OSM's Northbound API featuring ETSI NFV SOL005. Communication with OpenStack has been done through its provided API with a RESTful web service endpoint to access, provision, allocate and automate the resources. Data and logs are retrieved directly from Elasticsearch REST API, which is also used in cases of configuration and access to other Elasticsearch features. Additionally, custom APIs have been designed and developed to enable the acquisition of information from VNFs, applications and infrastructure with the use of exporters that send specific metrics to the Elasticsearch and Diagnostic components. Finally, the connection with Verticals has been performed with a custom API that directly connects the AI-enhanced MANO with the Verticals retrieving in this way all requirements or specific SLAs.

Figure 38. AI-enhanced MANO solution.

The architecture of the AI component is shown in Figure 38 and its connections and functions are explained below.

1. Direct Verticals info (i.e., Metrics/KPIs) of the Network Service (NS) that will be deployed acquired from AI-enhanced MANO or by utilizing the 5G EVE APIs.
2. Internally an API SERVER gets the request and triggers the AI component to evaluate the optimal deployment of the VNFs based on Vertical requirements and KPIs.
3. The API SERVER gets the VNF's info from the OSM (OSM NB API) and historical data from the db.
4. The API SERVER retrieves the metrics exported from the MEC platform and the MEC's VNF instances, to evaluate the metrics in real-time.
5. The AI component acquires all information in real-time (MEC's metrics, VNF IDs, and VNF requirements) from the API SERVER and uses old data and previous decisions. The AI finds the optimal deployments and migrations for the NSs in MECs.
6. The AI component triggers the OSM (OSM NB API), through the API SERVER, for any migration or reallocation of resources.

Initial validation of the proposed algorithm illustrates a response time (K3) of the AI algorithm of about 280 - 330ms. The next steps are: a) to validate the Vertical service response time (K9) and; b) to integrate this activity with A9 activity and provide an integrated prototype. The plan is that federated learning powered solutions (A9) will identify any anomalies (or QoS degradations) in the applications under monitoring and it will trigger the AI-enhanced MANO solution to reallocate resources in order to alleviate the problem.

4.2.6 Placement and routing for network services (A30)

Collected KPI	Justification
K2	The industry standard today is to deploy new network services in predetermined data centers, according to some static rule for which often template scripts are manually adapted. This does not guarantee that the resources of the data centers are optimally used. With the placement and routing algorithms studied here, the load can be automatically distributed over various data centers, thus savings computing resources.

In Section 6.1 of Deliverable D4.1 [26], a RL (reinforcement learning) method, referred to as SFC-E (service function chain embedding), was described to embed a new network service, described by an SFC (service function chain) in an infrastructure of a datacenter (shared with all other network services). As the results were reported in that section, they were not repeated in deliverable D5.1 [3]. In Section 5.1 of Deliverable D4.2 [2] a DMARL (distributed multi agent RL) based and a DDQL (double deep Q learning) based method to split an SFC over various data centers was introduced. This section reports typical results obtained with that method.

Figure 39. Considered mesh topology.

In particular, we assess the performance over the (partial) mesh topology consisting of five PoPs (points of presence) shown in Figure 39.

4.2.6.1.1 DDQL versus DMARL

First, we compare the performance of the DDQL against the DMARL algorithm in Figure 40. At first glance, in Figure 40 (left), in which we plot the corresponding collected rewards as moving averages across the last 100 episodes, we observe that both methods perform similarly. In particular, toward the end of the experiment, the two algorithms manage to retrieve an average reward of 7.0. Taking the reward function into account, we infer that both learning schemes obtain SFC embeddings that are, on average, 30% from the optimal. However, by zooming in at the 4,000-6,000 episodes interval, it becomes apparent that the DMARL framework exhibits faster convergence towards the aforementioned score than DDQL. In fact, this is further corroborated by Figure 40 (middle), where it becomes clear that, at the exact same interval, the rate of optimal embeddings of DMARL grows more rapidly than that of DDQL. According to that same figure, the rejection rates are negligible for both algorithms.

Figure 40. Performance comparison between DDQL and DMARL: (left) Learning progress; (middle) Optimal and rejected SFCs; (right) SFC embedding footprint.

Although informative, Figure 40 (left) and (middle) do not convey a lot about the differences in the underlying algorithmic behaviors. To this end, we consider Figure 40 (right), which depicts the footprint of (i.e., the number of PoPs utilized for) optimal SFC embeddings. The most evident difference here is centered on the incapacity of DDQL to achieve many “1-PoP” embeddings, which is counterbalanced by its higher capacity to achieve “>2-PoP” embeddings compared to DMARL. Our interpretation of this behavior is as follows: DDQL has a partial view of the real state, but its observation contains information about the entire topology. This enhances its inherent capacity to distribute VNFs across many PoPs, since it can reason about the state of the entire multi-datacenter system. At the same time, its observations only include the average available CPU capacities of each PoP, which limits its confidence in consolidating multiple VNFs into the same PoP.

Although the aforementioned limitation can be mitigated by extending DDQL's observation space with additional metrics (at the risk of further slowing its convergence), we deem that this analysis indicates the implications of decision-making with incomplete information in the context of SFC-E.

Figure 41. Action selection rules identified by DMARL agents.

4.2.6.1.2 Detailed DMARL analysis

To further delve into the behavior developed by the DMARL scheme, we employ Figure 41. Here, we attempt to shed light on the learning aspect of the team of agents in the mesh topology by examining certain action selection rules that have been identified over the course of training. To this end, we monitor the evolution of $p(x|f_1, f_2, f_3)$ at every training step, which shall be interpreted as the probability of taking action $x \in X = \{0,1,2\}$ (where 0 indicates an unwillingness to host the VNF, 1 a neutral position and 2 a high willingness to host the VNF), given that the flags f_1 =hosts_another, f_2 =hosts_previous, and f_3 =in_shortest_path take certain values. Recall that these binary flags, precisely defined in Section 5.1 of deliverable D4.2 [2] are part of the observation.

As per Figure 41, every agent manages to discover four key rules which, from a human perspective, seem rather intuitive for the SFC-E problem. Specifically, the increase of $p(0|0,0,0)$ implies that the agents tend to express low willingness for hosting the current VNF when all flags are down, i.e., no other VNFs are placed in the associated PoP (hosts_another=0), the previous VNF is placed in another PoP (hosts_previous=0), and the associated PoP is not in the shortest path from the source to the destination (in_shortest_path=0). In contrast, a growing $p(2|1,1,1)$ means that agents tend to express a high willingness to host the current VNF when all flags are up. At the same time, the counter-intuitive $p(2|0,0,0)$ (high willingness when all flags are down) and $p(0|1,1,1)$ (low willingness when all flags are up) seem to decrease over time. Our argument that these rules are indeed learned is backed by the fact that the respective probabilities diverge from the horizontal dotted line at $p=1/3$, which indicates random action selection. Nevertheless, these lines never reach either 1.0 or 0.0, which may imply that the additional observation dimensions (besides the three flags) also play an important role in action selection.

4.2.6.1.3 Conclusion

The comparison of DDQL and DMARL indicates that DMARL outperforms the single-agent DDQL method, which we mainly attribute to the full observability of the former (of the PoP that it governs) against the partial observability of the latter. We further corroborate that the team of agents manages to learn certain intuitive action selection rules.

4.3 NI for real-time anomaly detection and automated anomaly response

In this section, we present the two evaluations related to anomaly detection, namely **Evaluation E3** – which focuses on NI solutions that support anomaly detection in real-time in both controlled environments and in a production core network, and **Evaluation E5** – which aims at evaluating NI solutions for anomaly response. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E3 and E5 via activities A9, A19 and A25. The DAEMON consortium decided to merge these two evaluations given the proximity of the two topics they covered, and the fact that only one activity was carried out in E3 and two in E5 to date. Table 17 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate progress and main innovations of these activities.

Table 17. List of activities for E3.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Progress
A9	Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection	E3+E5	T8	K3, K7	K3	4	Yes	60%
<u>Main innovation:</u> Use federated learning for improving the efficiency of Anomaly Detection								

A19	Anomaly detection for a roaming platform	E3+E5	D8	K3, K7	K7	5	Yes	80%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Device-level anomaly detection for IoT verticals								
A25	Anomaly detection in mobile service traffic at base station level	E3+E5	D3	K3, K7	None	3	No	80%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Hybrid forecast for traffic anomaly detection								

4.3.1 Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection (A9)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	We measure the response time of the Federated Learning (FL)-powered algorithm, which is the average latency between a request for the FL client is delivered to the FL controller and the response of the FL controller including the updated model, is delivered to the FL clients. Initial results demonstrate a response time of the FL-powered algorithm (K3) of around 200-250 ms.
K7	Not yet collected. We will generate network impairments and we calculate the precision of the proposed solution to identify the impairments.

In Section 4.4.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [3], we presented the main considerations of the solution, including the high-level architecture and the approach to be used. In the current deliverable, the detailed design of the solution is presented.

The design of our solution has followed the guidelines established in D2.2 [27] in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2. Those concern the incorporation of prior knowledge in decision-making schemes: the FL setting enables each FL client to extract knowledge from its own specific datasets (based on metrics collected locally) and exchange this knowledge with other clients via a centralized learning process, which ingests complementary knowledge from all clients; in addition, the guidelines also refer to the support for decentralized and distributed data management, for heterogeneous devices, and for different time scales: those are enabled by the independent local operation of each one of the clients. Thirdly, the guideline about the low inference time and the energy consumption is addressed via the adoption of low complexity ML models, both in the local (DBSCAN algorithm) as well as the centralized (CART algorithm) learning processes. Last but not least, the FL-powered NI functionalities guideline is addressed, via several intelligent agents deployed in the various FL setting clients acting cooperatively, via sharing their DBSCAN-based outliers and border points, which are described in the following in detail.

The solution utilizes the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), which is a classical approach that has been applied in several outlier detection problems. DBSCAN performs unsupervised learning and classifies the analyzed data points into core points (normal behavior), border points (potentially anomalous behavior) and outliers (anomalous behavior).

The first step of the whole process is to configure the DBSCAN parameters, namely the values of ϵ (i.e., the minimum distance that shall separate the two nearest points in different clusters) and the minPts (i.e., the minimum number of points required to form a dense region). This configuration is dataset-specific and depends on the investigated feature vector size. Then, the DBSCAN is triggered for each FL client to execute locally based on the latest data received. Each client performs a distributed, "own-evaluation" of the process output, via calculating the Silhouette Coefficient Score (SCS). Then, only if the SCS indicates a satisfactory value (i.e., positive value and close to 1), then the respective client is requested to transmit the DBSCAN's output to the central FL controller, i.e., the extracted outliers, border points, SCS value and data volume. The latter is important in the centralized process, as the data volume that has been processed by each one of the FL clients, defines its respective "weight" in the federation process (algorithm pseudocode follows for more information).

Specifically, the centralized step adjusts the population of the received datasets, (i.e., the vector of the outliers, border points, SCS value, and data volume received from each FL client) by a factor. The population includes the logged/processed data volume of client k , during epoch one training period, over the sum of all FL clients' data. Then, the CART algorithm is used on the adjusted data; CART is a *Gini impurity index*-based decision-tree extraction algorithm, which extracts a number of rules that are then broadcasted to the FL clients of the system.

Figure 42. Overview of the Federated Learning-powered Anomaly Detection solution.

In this hybrid approach, the FL clients are applying rule-based anomaly detection for real-time operation, while the unsupervised DBSCAN is used at different timescales and requests for new incoming data towards enhancing the centralized CART model.

The development of the aforementioned solution is completed and an initial lab-based validation is realised. The initial results demonstrate a response time of the Federated learning-powered algorithm (K3) of around 200-250 ms including all the network and protocol delays. The next step is the collection and analysis of KPI K7. The final results of the evaluation will be presented in detail in D5.3.

4.3.2 Anomaly detection for a roaming platform (A19)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	For anomaly detection, the industry standard is currently relying on alarm systems or to react to tickets raised by the customers. Because of the complexity of the ecosystem and, consequently, of the anomalies that arise within the roaming platform, these latter come with significant delay, and are usually dealt with on a case-by-case basis. Our solution aims to reduce the reaction time of operating teams to anomalies occurring in the system by integrating NI functionalities for anomaly detection. Eventually, we aim to move towards real-time proactive approaches for anomaly detection.
K7	The goal of our solution is to capture anomalies that the currently missed by the alarm systems in place, but otherwise dealt with (and documented) via ticketing systems. We evaluate the performance of the anomaly detection approach based on ground truth anomalies that we collect from the ticketing system of a live roaming platform for IoT managed connectivity.

In this section, we present the continuation of the efforts we previously presented towards evaluating an anomaly detection approach tailored for IoT verticals. While in D5.1 we focused on capturing anomalies for a specific IoT vertical, we now aim to make our approach more generalizable, and easier to deploy for different clients.

We show that monitoring signaling traffic between the radio network provider (i.e., the visited MNO) and the core network operator (i.e., the home MNO that the IoT Provider uses or operates) can provide fine-grained insights into system health and device behavior. We have built two unique datasets, one for each of the two different operational IoT provider models: an IoT platform based in Spain (D8), and a dedicated IoT operator based in Germany (D8*). These two datasets include the control traffic that flows through the corresponding roaming hubs these providers use, and allow us to identify and characterize per-device communication patterns. Though the two IoT providers support different customers in different parts of the world, we show that the emerging signaling patterns from the different populations of devices are similar. The insights gained in this work for the basic understanding required to inform the design of anomaly detection approaches that are valid for different entities, regardless of their customer base. Monitoring signaling traffic allows for a much less intrusive view than monitoring application traffic. In mobile networks in particular, complex and diverse protocols let devices connect to the radio network first, and then establish the data communication channel over which application traffic is carried in an encrypted fashion. Visibility is thus much more limited compared to passive measurements in the traditional Internet.

4.3.2.1 Feature Engineering

To enable the automatic extraction of actionable information from raw data, we design a machine learning pipeline. Our goal is to automatically group devices that exhibit similar behaviour. We obtain these by analyzing the combined MAP and GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) signaling traffic of each device. In total, we include 143 features encompassing i) overall statistics, ii) message types and signalling patterns, iii) device activity, iv) mobility statistics, and v) longitudinal activity statistics. The features cover different levels and directions to describe devices as holistically as possible.¹⁰

Based on these features, we find that the two datasets present different characteristics. This is due to a multitude of factors, e.g., different data connectivity, different IoT verticals the two providers serve, and different business models and systems the operators run.

4.3.2.2 Device Classification

We now investigate if it is possible to identify common behaviors, e.g., groups of devices that exhibit similar signaling traffic patterns. Next, we are interested if there exist generic patterns that emerge in both datasets. For this, we rely on unsupervised machine learning approaches. First, we generate the full set of features for each device in each dataset. Then we run dimensionality reduction with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the feature set. This significantly reduces the dimensionality of the feature space to a number of principal components that retain at least 80% of the variability of the initial input data. We next perform k-means clustering on this reduced feature set. We identify $k = 8$ as the optimal number of clusters based on the Dunn index in both cases. Other indices provided similar results regarding the optimal number of clusters.

D8 Profiles – IoT Platform. We provide an overview of the clustering results for the IoT platform in Figure 43. We show the mean values for the subset of features with the highest feature importance to distinguish and characterize clusters from one another. For this, we consider four groups of characteristics, which we map to the sets of features we previously introduced. The first group includes overall statistics that allow us to distinguish between the use of pure phone connections or phone plus data connections (i.e., percentage of GTP/MAP Dialogues). The second group includes overall statistics regarding the errors and rejects in the signaling procedures. The third group includes features related to the mobility of devices. The fourth group includes message type statistics, which breaks down the use of specific signaling procedures. For example, some clusters only contain devices that are characterized by the low use of GTP messages, thus little signaling related to data traffic.

Device Cluster	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Overall Statistics: Phone & Data Usage								
MAP Dialogues [%]	83.4	77.8	87.2	89.2	66.9	92.2	25.0	77.7
GTP Dialogues [%]	16.6	22.2	12.8	10.8	33.1	7.8	75.0	22.3
Overall Statistics: Errors & Rejects								
Errors [%]	0.46	0.20	0.46	0.08	0.14	0.36	0.67	0.16
Rejects [%]	0.43	0.68	55.71	0.46	1.15	1.14	0.21	0.58
Selected Mobility Features								
Cell ID Changes	21.96	0.08	0.23	128.13	9.20	5.46	54.53	51.34
Operator Changes	3.08	0.01	0.03	77.58	0.38	0.28	1.49	1.14
Message Type Statistics: Protocol Usage								
SAI [%]	30.6	21.8	15.4	32.5	29.7	46.6	10.1	39.5
UL [%]	13.0	11.1	5.5	19.8	15.2	20.0	5.4	14.9
UL_GPRS [%]	15.3	4.0	4.0	19.1	5.9	6.6	1.6	6.0
PDP_CREATE [%]	9.2	11.3	6.4	6.6	16.9	4.2	38.2	11.8
PDP_DELETE [%]	7.4	10.7	6.3	4.1	16.2	3.6	36.2	10.4
PDP_UPDATE [%]	8.3	11.1	6.4	4.8	16.6	3.9	37.5	11.1

Figure 43. Traffic Pattern for the IoT Platform (D8).

Device Cluster	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Overall Statistics: Phone & Data Usage								
MAP Dialogues [%]	39	99.4	63	86	81	81	54	99.1
GTP Dialogues [%]	61	0.7	37	14	19	19	46	0.9
Overall Statistics: Errors & Rejects								
Errors [%]	5.4	1.9	5.1	2.6	2.6	28	2	0.34
Rejects [%]	0.51	0.24	1.5	0.72	1.7	0.76	0.67	97
Unclassified [%]	1.7	35	3.2	3.1	2.6	2.6	2	0.27
Select Mobility Features								
Cell ID Changes	129.42	0.19	567.43	18.03	43.38	6.04	317.93	8.30
Operator Changes	4.41	4.20	114.51	15.29	5.76	0.63	45.30	0.51
Message Type Statistics: Protocol Usage								
SAI [%]	27.2	5.3	41.8	40.4	53.7	44.3	32.8	94.5
UL [%]	6.0	38.4	5.7	12.7	19.7	19.8	9.6	4.0
UL_GPRS [%]	2.5	0.6	4.0	18.5	2.3	6.7	3.3	0.1
PDP_CREATE [%]	32.5	0.3	15.3	6.5	9.2	10.3	15.1	0.5
PDP_DELETE [%]	27.0	0.1	11.0	4.1	7.3	3.8	13.6	0.3
PDP_UPDATE [%]	1.7	0.2	10.4	2.9	2.2	5.2	16.9	0.1

Figure 44. Traffic Patterns for the Dedicated IoT Operator (D8*).

All percentage values we include in Figure 43 indicate the ratio between the one feature value to the total number of dialogues triggered by a device. We show the average values of the features over all the devices that are included in a given cluster. To help the reader, we color cells according to the baseline range of the entire dataset: blue – if the values are above the 80% quantile, and red – if the values are below the 20% quantile. This highlights outliers in both directions. Cluster 1 has a high percentage of UL_GPRS messages, with an average of 15.3% of the total messages per device. This indicates a high signaling volume originating from the Serving GPRS Support Node (SGSN), which we further corroborate with the occurrence of Send Authentication Information (SAI) messages originating at the SGSNs (not included in the table). Mobility and error features show no irregularities. Thus, we attribute cluster 1 to a device profile with regular behavior but a high volume of signaling originating from SGSNs.

¹⁰ https://github.com/anonymousFlabbergast/Mobicom2023_IoT

Cluster 2 captures devices that are likely stationary, with an average of 0.08 radio cell changes and 0.01 operator changes over the 30-day period. This is also consistent with the low ratio of UL_GPRS messages, indicating the lack of mobility-related HLR updates. Devices in cluster 2 are also characterized by an error rate of only 0.2% and a low reject rate of 0.68%. We conjecture that, due to their lack of mobility, these devices have good signal strength to successfully complete signaling procedures most of the time. Furthermore, we find that devices in this cluster exhibit long GTP tunnel durations, indicating long-lived data connections.

Focusing on cluster 3, we see it is mainly characterized by a high reject rate (55.71% per device), indicating it contains devices that tend to fail to complete the signaling procedures. These may include, for example, devices trying to establish connections to invalid roaming partners, devices that are using deactivated SIM cards, or devices that attempt to connect in poor coverage areas.

Cluster 4 clearly contains devices that exhibit a very high degree of mobility. They frequently change the cell and the operator and have a high percentage of UL and UL_GPRS messages that support this observation. Devices in this cluster also exhibit low GTP signaling ratios, indicating limited use of data connectivity.

Clusters 5 and 8 do not exhibit extreme characteristics aside from their low error and reject rates. The difference between the two clusters is the higher mobility indicator (cell changes) of cluster 8. Hence, we categorize clusters 5 and 8 as containing devices with no exceptional properties.

Clusters 6 and 7, on the other hand, exhibit mainly opposing properties regarding the type of signaling procedures they trigger. Cluster 6 devices trigger, on average, a high percentage of MAP signaling messages (92.2% of signaling dialogues are MAP), whereas cluster 7 devices trigger mostly GTP signaling (with 75.0% GTP-related signaling per device). The per-message-type breakdown ratios further support this separation of the two clusters. Cluster 6 devices use then circuit-switched technologies, while cluster 7 devices use mostly data connectivity.

D8* Profiles – Dedicated IoT Operator. Following the same clustering methodology, we extract signaling profiles from D8*. In Figure 44 we show the results.

Here, cluster 1 exhibits two major characteristics: devices show a high ratio of data-related signaling, which both the high percentage of GTP dialogues and the high percentages of PDP_CREATE and PDP_DELETE messages confirm. The low ratio of PDP_UPDATE messages indicates that devices use short-lived GTP tunnels instead of relying on the update mechanism. We infer that this might be an artifact of the manufacturer settings (e.g., due to quota limits). Devices also exhibit a significantly high number of radio cell changes but a low number of network operator changes. This indicates that these are mobile devices that largely remain attached to the same operator. We infer that these devices have regional mobility over a relatively small geographical area.

Cluster 2 aggregates devices that mainly trigger MAP signaling. Devices in this cluster also exhibit a large ratio of unclassified dialogues indicating the use of non-data related communication. The mobility features show that devices are mostly stationary. These devices may thus reflect very old IoT devices that connect via SMS.

Clusters 3 and 7 both contain devices that exhibit a large degree of mobility, as indicated by the high numbers for both cell changes and operator changes. This occurs if devices move over large geographical distances, traversing regions covered by multiple operators, or for devices that frequently alternate between two operators in areas with coverage of more than one operator. Both types of mobility result in the same pattern when it comes to the observed signaling traffic.

Clusters 4 and 5 exhibit largely similar characteristics and contain mainly nondescript devices. The major difference between the two clusters is the degree of mobility these devices exhibit. While cluster 4 shows a low average number of cell changes, the number of operator changes is almost three times higher compared to cluster 5. We assume that this is an artifact of the radio deployments available to the devices in the areas where they operate (i.e., per country or region differences in radio deployment). Cluster 6 aggregates devices that exhibit a very high error rate. This means that observed signaling interactions violate the signaling standardization through unexpected data, out of order or missing messages, or invalid signaling attempts.

Finally, cluster 8 contains devices that fail to perform successful signaling, with a very high ratio of rejected dialogues (i.e., 97%). Similar to D8, this occurs if devices try to roam with operators without valid roaming agreements or if deployed sim cards are either not yet or no longer activated.

The analysis of device signaling characteristics allows identifying macroscopic patterns that are explainable. The unsupervised learning approach greatly simplifies the analysis of the administrators, who can further use their domain knowledge to interpret the results. In addition, some clusters clearly pinpoint groups of devices that have problems, e.g., generating a large number of errors or using old technology. This information is instrumental for the network operator for both management and business actions.

Cluster	Mobility	Data Usage	Reject Behavior	Protocol Usage
DAT1 (IoT Platform)				
1	-	-	▼	▲ UL_GPRS
2	▼	-	▼	▼ SAI ▼ UL_GPRS
3	▼	-	▲	▼ SAI
4	▲	▼	▼	▲ UL ▲ UL_GPRS
5	-	-	▼	-
6	▼	▼	▼	▲ SAI ▲ UL
7	-	▲	▼	▲ GTP ▼ MAP
8	-	-	▼	-
DAT2 (Dedicated IoT Operator)				
1	-	▲	▼	▼ PDP_UPDATE
2	▼	▼	▼	▲ UL
3	▲	-	▼	▲ PDP_UPDATE
4	-	-	▼	▲ UL_GPRS
5	-	-	▼	▼ PDP_UPDATE
6	▼	-	▼	▲ Error Rate
7	▲	-	▼	▲ PDP_UPDATE
8	▼	▼	▲	▲ SAI

Figure 45. Signaling traffic profile mapping for both datasets and all four identified traffic profiles. ▲ cluster exhibits high values; ▼ low values; - medium values.

Comparison of Clustering Results. While the operations and customer bases of these two providers are different, we found that the datasets contain similar profiles but at different granularity. We provide a direct comparison of the results for the two independent datasets. We condense the identified descriptions into four profiles and assign qualitative indicators according to the values in Figure 43 and Figure 44. This simplifies the comparison of signaling patterns. Figure 45 presents this mapping between signaling profiles and clusters in each of the datasets.

Mobility. In both datasets, we identify clusters (cluster 4 in D8 and clusters 3 and 7 in D8*) that exhibit significant mobility (high number of operator and cell changes). When looking at the specific feature values for these clusters, we observe that devices – while exhibiting strong mobility in both datasets – differ in the way they use data connectivity. On average, only around 11% of signaling traffic consists of GTP dialogues in D8, while devices in D8* exhibit 37% and 46% GTP dialogues on average, with D8 having more IoT devices that do not rely on data connectivity (e.g., shipment tracking) than D8*.

Data Usage. Data usage characteristics represent our second behavioral profile. Differentiation by data usage shows that our clustering approach on both datasets is able to isolate devices that either exhibit excessive data usage (cluster 7 in D8, cluster 1 in D8*) or very limited data usage (clusters 4 and 6 in D8, cluster 2 in D8*). Note that cluster 8 in D8 also shows very low data-related signaling. However, this is due to the fact that devices in this cluster largely fail to perform successful signaling and hence, never get the chance to establish data connectivity. This is again due to different configurations of the two providers (e.g., quota limits). These clusters may suggest the IoT operators to adapt their plans.

Reject Behavior. The reject behavior of devices maps to cluster 3 for D8 and cluster 8 for D8*. With a mean reject rate of 55% and 97%, respectively, both exhibit significantly higher reject rates than all other clusters. This profile points to the fact that these devices largely fail to perform any meaningful signaling, likely due to deactivated SIMs, or buggy implementations. They bring unnecessary costs for operators and carriers and justify the need for network management decisions to alleviate the issues they pose.

Protocol Usage. Finally, we were able to identify clusters showing distinct protocol usage patterns in both datasets. Namely, clusters 1 and 4 in D8 as well as cluster 4 in D8*, show high amounts of signaling messages originating from the SGSN (UL_GPRS) while at the same time only showing low to moderate data usage, indicating irregular signaling behavior. Conversely, clusters 1 and 7 in D8 exhibit low and high usage of PDP_UPDATE dialogues despite showing low and moderate data usage, respectively. This indicates irregular device behavior, such as excessive creation and deletion of data tunnels for cluster 1 or abnormally high data tunnel duration in the case of cluster 7. This suggests possible implementation issues.

The profiles we identify through clustering generalize to both deployments for our datasets. We expect this to be applicable to other networks and datasets as well. We see this as a step towards creating common profiles for IoT devices based on mobile signaling that researchers can use as a starting point and network operators can leverage to simplify their actions. We achieve this thanks to the generality of the features that characterize device behavior, thus allowing common and macroscopic patterns to emerge. As the next steps, we are testing anomaly detection approaches using this knowledge. We aim to explore the approaches that we already reported in D4.1 and D4.2. We will report these results in D5.3.

4.3.3 Anomaly detection in mobile service traffic at base station level (A25)

Collected KPI	Justification
K7	We measure the anomaly detection recall and sensitivity for traffic demand forecasting, such that the system raises the alarm if the probability of the anticipated traffic being outside the reference interval is beyond a certain threshold. The evaluation shows that the proposed solution improves by 25% the F-score over state-of-the-art approaches and achieves at least 85%, scoring in both precision and recall for scenarios of interest.

The promising results obtained during the first iteration of the project from the application of full hybrid approaches in anticipatory capacity *allocation* motivated us to study other applications of such NI methods. Such hybrid methods merge both statistical analysis and deep learning structures. This activity is focused on anticipatory anomaly detection for traffic load in the network. Specifically, we design an NI network function that must trigger an alert in the event of expecting an abnormal future traffic load for a specific mobile service. The first solution to hybrid approaches was presented in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [26]

We also provided in Section 4.3 of Deliverable 4.2 [2] the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of Deliverable 2.2 [27] as well as its mapping to major standards. This solution complies with the full hybrid approach proposed in Section 4.2.4 of D2.2 as a better alternative to pure deep learning AI models commonly used in the literature for network traffic forecasting.

The anomaly detection problem is introduced by the DAEMON project in Section 4.3 of Deliverable 4.2, where Figure 17 represents the problem and explains the operation of anomaly detection. There exists a predictor module in charge of producing a probability distribution of the traffic demand that the target service will generate in the next time slot. Such a probabilistic prediction is compared against a reference interval that encompasses the expected range of normal traffic values in the following time slot. After that, the system raises the alarm if the probability of the anticipated traffic being outside the reference interval is beyond a certain threshold. The correctness of the anticipatory anomaly detection can be determined by checking whether the actual traffic falls into the expected interval or not and computing precision and recall scores.

We set this use case in a virtualized network environment running an end-to-end network slicing model, where proactive load anomaly detection is paramount for the timely identification of undesired situations which could be amended by, e.g., new network configurations. In such settings, the anomalous load detection NI operates at the granularity of individual services. Specifically, we run experiments for slices that each accommodate one of four different services. For each slice, we consider different base stations and assess the performance of the anomaly detection algorithm discussed that relies on forecasting models of the slice traffic at each such base station.

4.3.3.1 Performance

We compare our solution TES-RNN with three state-of-the-art benchmark models. The first one, the so-called "INFOCOM17," is a popular forecasting technique that is explicitly designed to predict mobile network traffic at the level of individual base stations. It leverages a Deep Neural Network (DNN) architecture where both global and local Stacked Auto-Encoder (SAE) layers are used to learn spatial features in the data, followed by Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) layers that capture temporal correlations. This benchmark represents the state of the art in point forecast at the base station level, i.e., the problem at hand. The second benchmark is named "ES-RNN", which is the hybrid method from which TES-RNN was built and that is not tailored for capacity forecasting. Finally, a third benchmark, referred to as "RNN", consists only of the machine learning part of TES-RNN, without statistical modeling.

We evaluate two different metrics. First, the Mobile traffic prediction accuracy tasks for which TES-RNN was first developed in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [26], and presented in Section 4.6.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [3], but this time for a different use case of independent base stations. Second, we measure the Anomaly detection performance.

1) *Mobile traffic prediction accuracy*: Figure 46(a) shows the results for all models, and services, averaged over five different base stations. Independently of the test configuration, TES-RNN yields a more accurate prediction than INFOCOM17. The average Mean Squared Error (MSE) reduction across all base stations is in the 15%-30% range, peaking at 50% for the Facebook case.

2) *Anomaly detection performance*: Having observed the superior accuracy of TES-RNN mobile traffic prediction, we investigate how this reflects on the actual performance of anomaly detection. We emulate the situation in which the network analytics function of a mobile network gathers data from the User Plane Function (UPF) to monitor, e.g., the excessive usage of the network by a terminal, and has to generate an alarm if such an event is anticipated to happen in the near future. We consider for our test

a scenario where different base stations are monitored with the algorithm introduced in Section 4.3 of Deliverable 4.2 [2]. Figure 46(b) shows the performance of all the benchmarks in terms of the F1 Score, averaged over the five selected base stations for the four selected application types. TES-RNN always achieves the best performance, while competitors provide unbalanced results, highly depending on the considered application. In particular, the baseline ES-RNN almost always triggers the anomalous load alarm, as the predicted values are often well above the thresholds (and the real values). To further corroborate the quality of TES-RNN in this kind of task, we also evaluate its effectiveness with variable values of its key hyperparameter, denoted π_A , and explained in detail in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [26]. More specifically, we show in Figure 46(c) the ROC curve for the selected benchmarks. TES-RNN always yields the best pairing between the Recall and the false positive rate for all the considered π_A in the range between 30% and 95%.

Figure 46. Benchmarking between INFOCOM17, RNN and TES-RNN forecast. (a) MSE values, (b) F1 Scores, and (c) ROC Curve for the Facebook service for different thresholds for the statistical modeling. Subplots (a) and (c) do not show values for ES-RNN because it results in exceedingly high overestimation and a very high number of false positives, hence a very poor performance.

We also analyzed the complexity of the proposed solutions in terms of the average training time for a single prediction. The results are reported in Table 18 and refer to experiments on an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU. In the first use case, TES-RNN required an average of 16.93 minutes per capacity allocation experiment (combining training and testing), whereas ES-RNN needed 16.32 minutes. INFOCOM17 was the most taxing model, with a mean of 24.64 minutes per run. For the second use case, TES-RNN required an average of 6.8 minutes for a single forecasting experiment, while INFOCOM17 needed an average of 51.61 minutes to process the spatial dependency data needed by the model. Overall, TES-RNN can be trained as fast as less optimized models (i.e., ES-RNN) and much faster than state-of-the-art solutions, and is only slower than models with lower performance (such as RNN).

Table 18. Required complexity (mean training time) of each of the considered algorithms.

Use Case	TES-RNN	ES-RNN	RNN	INFOCOM17
First Use Case	16.93	16.32	4.56	24.64
Second Use Case	6.8	6.5	2.09	51.61

4.3.3.2 Conclusions

The proposed solution is a first-of-its-kind hybrid forecasting model for mobile networks that enhances a recently proposed method for the joint optimization of statistical models and neural network architectures. The solution offers unprecedented performance in supporting different anticipatory networking tasks, not only traffic forecast but also the capacity allocation and anomaly detection. When confronted with practical application use cases characterized by different real-world traffic volumes and dynamics, TES-RNN granted gains of up to 25% over state-of-the-art predictors that were specifically designed for the target problem. As a result, we believe that TES-RNN paves the way for a new and improved generation of forecasting models that will contribute to the success of fully automated, zero-touch mobile network architectures, and further experiments will be performed to understand its maximum potential.

4.4 NI for Edge orchestration

Evaluation E4 targets NI solutions for service orchestration and resource allocation algorithms in the Edge micro-domain. We performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E4 via activities A10-A17. Table 19 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate progress and main innovations of such activities. Moreover, Table 19 shows that one activity involved in this functionality is already completed. In particular, A12 (Section 4.4.3) concluded their research on the specific topics.

Table 19. List of activities for E4.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Evaluation Progress
A10	Video analytics with edge computing	E4	D5	K2	K2	3	No	70%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Compute-aware scheduling for analytics VNF								
A11	Multi-timescale edge orchestration	E4	T4	K2, K5, K8	K5, K8	4	Yes	90%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Multi-timescale management and orchestration of edge services and resources								
A12	WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management	E4	D6	K5, K8	K8	3	No	100%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Enabling fast WLAN performance prediction for spectrum optimization								
A13	Data-driven resource orchestration	E4	D1a	K5, K8, K9	K5, K8, K9	5	No demo; Pilot executed	90%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Clustering of device population to extract resource requirement profiles								
A14	Multi-timescale network slice reservation	E4	None ¹¹	K4	K4	2	No	80%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Slice reservation policies for optimal resource employment based on OCO								
A15	Testing EnergyEdgeCloudSim	E4	S5	K1, K2, K3, K4	K1, K2, K3	3	Yes	90%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Energy-aware VNF orchestration								
A16	Towards autonomous VNF scaling	E4	S1	K4	K4	3	No	75%
<i>Main innovation:</i> General-purpose NI solution for autonomous VNF auto-scaling at edge								
A17	Auto scaling Virtualized RAN caches	E4	D9	K3, K4	K3, K4	2	No	70%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Jointly optimize dynamic cache rental, content placement, and request-cache association in wireless scenarios								
A26	Energy-aware VNF orchestration	E4	None	K1, K2, K3	K1, K2	3	No	60%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Proactive auto-scaling mechanisms in edge-based infrastructures to anticipate user service requests.								

4.4.1 Video analytics with edge computing (A10)

Collected KPI	Justification
K2	By leveraging the fact that some systems offer access to how to allocate their computing resources or have multiple GPUs, we can assign multiple users to the same (or different) resources by modifying the decision vector. This results in saving computing resources, if needed.

In Section 4.4.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [3] we examined the issue of offloading analytics tasks, and more precisely, image recognition, in the context of edge computing. We proved and showcased that our proposed algorithm, which computes the compression and under-sampling ratio, achieved optimal

performance without violating the desired constraints. This thread was enriched in Section 2.4 of Deliverable D3.2 [1], where we manifested how it adheres to the requirement and guidelines presented in D2.2 [27]. Our aim is to update this activity in the upcoming Deliverable for WP5 (namely, D5.3), by extending our analysis and providing enhanced results.

4.4.2 Multi-timescale edge orchestration (A11)

Collected KPI	Justification
K2	In this experiment, we test the CPU load of the edge computing node where the edge service is running. This way, we increased the awareness of CPU load and how such a load impacts the vertical response time. Such awareness of CPU load from the Maestro algorithm will lead to saving computational resources, as it turns out to increase the average response time, which needs to be prevented for vehicular edge services.
K5	Service reliability in the context of our work is defined as a ratio of served and received requests at the edge service. We calculate it with reference to the number of users, i.e., vehicles (10, 50, 80, and 100) that are simultaneously consuming the service deployed at the edge. During the test, the service was capable of handling three concurrent requests, and for that type of service, we calculated the reliability with respect to the average response time that the edge service took in different testing rounds.
K8	Vertical response time has been measured in terms of the average response time of the edge service that is serving the user, i.e., the vehicle. We measure it as round-trip time that consists of (i) the time needed for the request to arrive from the user to the edge service, (ii) the processing time at the edge service, and (iii) the time needed for the response to be transferred back to the user.

For the purpose of testing multi-timescale edge orchestration, we implemented two algorithms that trigger edge service relocation. These algorithms are: (1) rule-based algorithm that makes a decision to relocate service based on the current CPU load on the source edge computing node, and (2) MAESTRO that proactively performs the selection of a new target node to which the observed edge Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) service should be relocated in order to maintain/achieve the required service response time. It works in an automated and intelligent way thanks to the Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) mechanism that takes into account various metrics, such as CPU, memory, and power utilization, as well as the predicted average response time for a vehicle client. The prediction is based on the Support Vector Regression (SVR) model that is trained at the edge orchestrator level. The details of the MAESTRO algorithm are presented in D3.2, and here we briefly refer to the results achieved.

Figure 47. Latency and reliability results of benchmarking Maestro and rule-based algorithm.

As we defined in [28], in case the vehicle is moving, we define a tolerable latency for retrieving important warnings, and as it depends on the type of the use case and the average speed, the value of this tolerable latency should be defined as a functional requirement (e.g., by use case developers). For the type of vehicular use cases where notifications/warnings are generated and collected from edge services (as a result of processing data from sensors and other vehicles) to extend the contextual perception of a vehicle, the result we obtained can be considered as satisfactory due to the following reasons. In case the average speed of the vehicle is 80km/h, we can define tolerable latency to be 15ms, as a vehicle will move only 0.33m until it gets a new notification. This functional requirement needs to be studied with more prominent attention in the case of autonomous driving or teleoperation of a vehicle, for which more ML models need to be studied and compared against each other to determine the satisfactory level of prediction accuracy.

In Figure 47, we show the result of the gain in average service response time (latency measured at the client side), which can be achieved by performing edge service relocation in a proactive and automated way, i.e., by applying the MAESTRO algorithm. First, the results show the average response time measured at the client side for application instances running on Edge 1 and Edge 2. Second, it shows the behavior of the MAESTRO algorithm against a simple rule-based algorithm, thereby examining the way they trigger service relocation. As the cloud orchestrator is constantly monitoring CPU data from different edge domains, it applies the SVR model to predict the average response time for a particular type of vehicular edge service. In the case of MAESTRO, if the predicted values of the average response time in the upcoming three samples (three minutes upfront in total) are larger than the tolerable latency, which we consider as 15ms for a used type of service, then the cloud orchestrator applies MCDM and potentially requests an application relocation to Edge 2 from Edge 1. On the other side, a rule-based algorithm simply compares the current average response time with the threshold (i.e., 15ms) and triggers the relocation. In Figure 47, for each of the samples, it can be seen whether these two algorithms trigger relocation for service deployment on Edge 1 or not. For instance, in sample 10, MAESTRO is triggering the service relocation from Edge 1 to Edge 2 in a proactive way, which prevents the vehicle user to experience an increased response time, as in case of relocation, the response time will be lower than 15ms, while on the contrary, it will reach 120ms on Edge 1. This shows how MAESTRO outperforms rule-based algorithms, which are most commonly used in state-of-the-art NFV MANO systems.

However, we also need to check how these decisions affect the reliability of the service. As the service reliability can be defined as a ratio of served and received requests, in Figure 47, we show how it changes from sample to sample in case the service is placed on Edge 1 and if multiple users (10, 50, 80, and 100) are consuming the service. The type of service we used in this performance analysis is capable of serving three concurrent requests, i.e., if concurrently served, they achieve an average response time shown in Figure 59. In the case of 89ms response time (sample 1), the vehicular edge service is capable of serving 33.59 requests/s (served). Clearly, the reliability of the service will depend on the overall number of received requests, i.e., the number of users. If there are 80 vehicles consuming the service at the same time (80 requests/s), the service reliability drops down to 0.42 in case service is consumed from Edge 1, which is completely unacceptable for most of the V2X services that require a reliability of at least five nines (99.999%). Further, in sample 17, the reliability would drop to 0.9862 for 100 vehicles if the service is not proactively relocated, which would happen in case of the rule-based algorithm as it does not proactively trigger the relocation in the 16th sample, as MAESTRO does. The same applies to sample 19, which brings completely intolerable reliability values if the service is not previously relocated, as in the case of MAESTRO being the one that triggers relocation in sample 18 (Figure 47). Such results show the true benefit of the quality-aware MAESTRO algorithm performing edge orchestration in a proactive and automated way, thereby re-attaching the user from one edge to another when the algorithm triggers the relocation.

Concerning the re-attachment of vehicle client from one edge to another, in this experiment, we utilized the Eclipse Zenoh framework to disseminate notifications from edge orchestrator to vehicle client. Furthermore, this vehicular client is capable of dynamically changing the service endpoint depending on the input received from edge orchestrators, by applying a new rule on its programmable data plane.

4.4.3 WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management (A12)

Collected KPI	Justification
K5	We could not collect this KPI, since ATARI was only validated with synthetic data. Moreover, the solution was not deployed as a service to, e.g., assign more channels to a critical service if it is detected that the performance of the WLAN supporting that service is deteriorating.
K8	An interference management application must timely evaluate the WLAN performance under a given configuration. ATARI could provide such an evaluation within milliseconds range (average inference time for a given deployment), which could improve the response time of the service.

In this activity, we trained and evaluated four state-of-the-art ML models to predict the throughput of all WLAN devices in an enterprise-like scenario containing a different number of APs and STAs applying DCB. The results were reported in Section 4.4.3 of D5.1 [3]. Moreover, in Section 3.2 of D3.2 [1] we decomposed ATARI, a GNN model for Wi-Fi throughput prediction in highly dense scenarios, into the blocks of the proposed extension of the MAPE-K loop, the N-MAPE-K [27].

Besides decomposing ATARI, we also discussed how the Graph Neural Network (GNN) model could be used in futuristic Software Defined WLANs (SD-WLANs) following the ITU architectural framework for machine learning in future networks, including IMT-2020 [29]. The proposed GNN model can be used as an interference management application where the control plane would trigger the execution of this

application once a new channel configuration is introduced into the data plane or when the control plane realizes its performance is degrading. Then, the model allows a timely evaluation of the WLAN performance under alternative channel configurations.

While it is true that such an assessment would only be carried out a few times per hour (i.e., longer timescales), the radio environment is constantly changing, so the prediction can only take up to a few seconds. If the prediction takes more time, then the performance of the devices could be severely hindered. In that sense, alternative network models (e.g., network simulators or mathematical models) might fail to produce timely evaluations. For instance, given a deployment of 12 overlapping WLANs (e.g., topology) and a particular configuration (e.g., a set of channels that could be bonded) from D6, Komondor [30] might take between 1 and 10 seconds to produce a prediction. On the contrary, the same scenario with an already trained GNN model might take between 7 and 27 milliseconds. Therefore, we can conclude that with ML we could at least improve in 99% the response time of an interference management application, acting in the application plane of future SD-WLANs.

Despite our model could also be used to take more advanced decisions, e.g., assign more channels to a critical service if it is detected that the performance of the WLAN supporting that service is deteriorating, we could not collect any metrics that are related to K5. Thus, we conclude our research on this activity and we will not report any more updates in the upcoming deliverables.

4.4.4 Data-driven resource orchestration in the MNO (A13)

Collected KPI	Justification
K5	Our solution extracts the requirements of specific clusters of end-user devices. With these, the operator can make better decisions in terms of resources allocations (e.g., under extreme mobility), thus increasing the network reliability.
K8	The clustering approach we propose is specifically useful for vertical applications that might rely on roaming to connect their devices globally. By easily identifying and mapping the requirements of inbound roamers, the radio network operator can improve the vertical service response time significantly.
K9	With a clear mapping of end-user devices clusters and their requirements in terms of connectivity, the operator is able to perform a more optimal resources allocation.

In this activity, we present a proof-of-concept implementation of the solution we presented in Section 3.4 of D3.2 on data-driven resources orchestration. We provide here two main experimental contributions:

- We describe how we integrate our clustering approach within the big data platform of a large operational MNO (testing servers), leveraging T14 and D1a.
- We discuss how the results of our MNO smart classification of the device population connecting to an operator prompted us to we investigate the potential of using third-party infrastructure in order to host core network functions for an operator deploying their device globally (e.g., offering managed connectivity for connected cars worldwide). The split of the user plane from the control plane at both the radio front and the core is one of the major upgrades in 5G. This paves the way not just for better management of data and control packets but also to enable truly global operations of an operator. We argue that, with this approach, any mobile operator can potentially convert into a global provider, thus avoiding home-routed roaming configuration and enabling the end-user to achieve a good experience potentially worldwide through regional breakout. We envision a scenario where the mobile operator provides the local breakout solution to each end-user, in correlation to its corresponding requirements, as we extracted them from the clustering analysis above.

4.4.4.1 Pilot for Clustering Devices within an MNO's User Population

We leverage access to an MNO's big data platform (T14) to test and integrate our clustering approach. This activity is part of the pilot we have conducted with Virgin Media O2 UK, where we have integrated our user-catalog processing pipeline within their production systems. With this, we have ran the clustering approach, to further extract the end-user profiles. These results have also been transferred to the operator.

As VMO2 is currently deploying their 5G Core within the UK, we are also working to update the users' catalog with the information from the Access and Mobility management Function (AMF) feed that we collect within the MNO's big data platform (which we will integrate with the 4G Mobility Management Entity (MME) feed).

4.4.4.2 Proof of Concept for Performance Improvement of Roaming Devices

Our analysis in Section 3.4. of D3.2 highlighted two major challenges within the current operational landscape of the cellular ecosystem: (i) the heterogeneity of connectivity requirements of end-user devices and (ii) the increased demand for global connectivity of devices, especially those serving IoT verticals. In other words, our analysis uncovered a sharp increase in the need for connecting extremely heterogeneous terminals that operate globally in different environments around the world, with varying performance requirements. This surging demand in global/ubiquitous cellular connectivity comes both from the massive number of connected IoT devices as well as from people who are progressively switching (together with all their devices) to a digital nomad lifestyle. The rise of a large, new group of traveling, remote workers is one of the prevailing side-effects of the COVID-19-impacted work world. This growing digital nomad community across the globe is fueling the demand for international seamless connectivity. Support for things roaming globally is now critical for IoT vertical applications, from connected cars to smart meters.

The 'Global SIM' is now a product that individuals and IoT companies demand, and it is being satisfied by a new breed of providers of mobile communications, the Mobile Network Aggregators (MNA). Similarly to Mobile Virtual Network Operators (MVNOs), MNAs rely on the infrastructure of MNOs to provide services, marketing themselves as "Global Operators". Instead of relying on a single base MNO, MNAs multiplex their clients across multiple MNOs in order to ensure optimal service and sustained quality of experience (QoE), without the added cost of operating the network.

Roaming and the associated ecosystem are essential pillars that support MNAs' operations in multiple countries, without the need of finding a local communication provider in every country where their end-users operate. MNAs benefit from the extensive global network infrastructure that international carriers (e.g., incumbent tier-one operators such as Vodafone, Tata, Telefonica, or Orange) have been shaping for the past decades.

The emerging MNA model is appealing to the Internet companies, which now crossed into the telco world, such as Google's Fi Project. Furthermore, Cloud communication Platforms as a Service (CPaaS) such as Twilio or EMnify provide MNA services by aggregating networks at the international level, thus aiming for global service, and making connectivity available through simple interfaces to application and service developers world-wide.

Taxonomy and limitations of the current operator models. There are several types of mobile operators with different operation models available in the market today; we show these configurations in Figure 48.

@HOME	Traditional MNO	Light MVNO	Full MNVO	Light MNA	Full MNA
Sales	MNO	Light MVNO	Full MNVO	Light MNA	Full MNA
Core	MNO	Base MNO	Full MNVO	Base MNO	Full MNA
Radio	MNO	Base MNO	Base MNO	Base MNO	Base MNO

Figure 48. Types of MNO.

An MNO is an entity that owns (or has the exploitation rights) of a cellular network (i.e., base stations, network core, spectrum, etc). This was the initial operation model deployed to provide mobile communication services. Examples of MNOs include Vodafone, Orange, O2, AT&T, NTT to name a few. Later on, the MVNO operation model emerged. Specifically, the MVNO is an entity that offers mobile network services to end-users, but does not own nor operate fully a cellular network. The MVNO is defined by its lack of ownership of radio spectrum resources.

In order to operate, an MVNO needs to have agreements in place to access the network of a base MNO. The implementation of the MVNO varies, and thus there are many different types on MVNOs. The type of MVNO is determined by how "thick" or "thin" a technological layer the MVNO adds over its access to its base MNO's network.

A *light* MVNO is a service provider that has its own customer support, marketing, sales and distribution operations, and may have the ability to set its tariffs independently from the retail prices of the base MNO. One such example is giffgaff in the UK, which uses O2 UK as a base MNO. A *full* MVNO has a core

network implementation operating essentially the same technology as anMNO, only missing their own radio network. They thus run their own core network, and rely on a base MNO who can offer access to radio resources. One example is Sky Mobile, which operates as a full MVNO in the UK, using O2 UK as a base operator.

Much more recently, we have witnessed the emergence of a new type of MVNO, namely the MNA. While "traditional" MVNOs have agreements with a single base MNO, an MNA is an MVNO that exploits more than one base MNO, either in one single economy, or across different economies. Examples of MNAs include Google Fi, Truphone, Twilio or Lycamobile. Aggregating multiple base MNOs allows the MNA's customers to dynamically change the base MNO to which they attach. This change of base MNOs depends on different factors, including policy, coverage or performance.

We further classify MNAs into *full* MNAs or *light* MNAs, depending on whether they operate their own core network or not. We also differentiate the MNAs based on the geographic coverage of the multiple base MNOs they aggregate. In the general case, the base MNOs aggregated can cover the same or different geographic regions. A particular case is when the different base MNOs aggregated provide coverage in different geographic regions that do not overlap, notably different economies. If this is the case, we call this specific type of MNA a multi-country MVNO. These multi-country MVNOs usually have commercial offers in each of the different economies where they operate.

We acknowledge that, as in most taxonomies, there are corner cases that we cannot neatly classify into one of the categories. In our case, there is the case where a full MVNO has commercial agreements with one or several IP Packet Exchange (IPX) Provider (IPX-P), and does not depend on a specific base MNO (e.g., the MVNO might use global IMSI ranges). In this case, with a single agreement, the MVNO has "direct" access to several base MNOs located in different economies, depending on the footprint of the IPX-P. This configuration lies somewhere between the full MNA and the full MVNO, since it has a single agreement but connects to multiple base MNOs. We call this the "Global Mobile Network Operator (GMNO)" model, which currently depends on the IPX-P.

Under this scenario, the GMNO can optimize the placement of the UPF in order to minimize the end-to-end latency from the end-user devices to the application server (which, in a global deployment scenario, might be in a different economy than the end-user device).

Experimental Setup. We utilise the edge (wavelength), local and regional deployments of Amazon global infrastructure to deploy control and user plane functions of open-source 5G implementations (namely, Open5GS and UERANSIM).

The setup we build aims to emulate different roaming configurations. For this, we rely on the global infrastructure including both storage and compute services that AWS offers. This includes:

- a *regional* infrastructure with data centers present in a region (e.g., US East/Ohio region). Within this deployment, a cluster of isolated and physically separate data centers are found in a geographical area.
- a *local* infrastructure hosted as an extension of regional infrastructure to run latency sensitive and high bandwidth applications. For example, Netflix uses AWS local zone deployments for their content creation process.
- an *edge* infrastructure hosted within telecommunications providers' data centers and connected to the operator's 5G network. We consider this as first point a user can breakout to the Internet from MNOs network.

Table 20. Locations of deployed UPF and DNN names as identified by the UEs to breakout at a visited location (namely, US or Germany).

	UK		US				EU (Germany)	
Breakout Type	Home (London)	Edge (Vodafone)	Edge (Verizon)	Local (Las Vegas)	Regional (Oregon)	National (Ohio)	Edge (Vodafone)	Regional (Frankfurt)
DNN	edge.london	home	edge.sfo	local.las	regional.or	national.oh	edge.ber	edge.fra

Connectivity. For our PoC deployment, we assume an end-user with 5G connectivity who has their network home location in the UK. To emulate the user roaming behavior, we test two different scenarios, where the user roams in two locations: (i) in the US (San Francisco) and (ii) within Europe (Berlin, Germany). With current 4G/LTE technologies, the default roaming configuration would be HR roaming, where the traffic is routed back to the UK. We argue that, by using 5G Control and User Plane Separation at the core, we can keep the control plane functions in the trusted, centralized home network location, while dynamically moving the user plane function with the roaming user. We handle this connectivity by deploying control and user planes built using Open5GS. We deploy the control plane, which includes Session Management Function (SMF) and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), at the

regional infrastructure in the user's home location (London, UK). The user plane enables breakout to the internet, and hence we deploy it across multiple locations in the US and EU (as per Table 20). The selection of UPF to breakout is chosen by the DNN setting in the 5G UE. We use UERANSIM to deploy a simulated environment of 5G RAN and 5G UE in the edge infrastructure.

Figure 49. Page load time to different websites in function of the breakout point considered for the roaming configuration.

Results. In order to capture the end-user performance under the scenarios we include in Table 20 we measure web performance. We focus on the web Page Load Time (PLT) as the representative metric. We use as target four websites, namely, www.ucla.edu in the US, www.uclouvain.be in Belgium, www.url.edu in Spain and www.mit.edu, which is served by a CDN. We show our results in Figure 49. We use as a baseline the measurements for the non-roaming scenario (marked “home (UK)” in Figure 49). The goal of our measurements analysis is to establish which roaming configuration can offer the same performance that the end-user enjoys while at home. We find that when content is served by a CDN, the regional breakout configuration offers comparable performance to the no-roaming scenario, regardless of the location where the end-user travels (e.g., US or Germany, in our case). This is a direct consequence of the close location of the content replica to the end user, which is dictated by the location of the breakout point. From the case of end-user roaming in the US, we see that the local breakout configuration yields similar performance to regional breakout, likely as a result of the small distance between the locations of the infrastructures used in this scenario.

When a CDN is not serving the web content, the distance between the location of the end-user breakout point and the content location impacts the web performance. For example, if edge breakout in San Francisco offers the optimal performance for accessing content hosted in California (ucla.edu), we see this is no longer the case when accessing content hosted in Europe (uclouvain.be, url.edu). The PLT we measure in this latter case is, in fact, similar to the one we measure under the home-routed roaming (HR) configuration. The same is true for accessing US-based content from Germany, under the regional breakout configuration. Surprisingly, however, we find that the PLT for Europe-hosted web content is slightly smaller in the US (San Francisco) edge breakout scenario than all of the other configurations (local/regional/national/home breakout). We conjecture that this is a side-effect of relying on the carrier's infrastructure (i.e., Verizon), while for the other configurations the AWS private backbone impacts the delays between the various instances.

Given the large geographical areas that we target in our PoC, we believe that integrating an intelligent approach to select the best location for the UPF would result in over-engineering our solutions. In this scenario, simply moving the user plane closer to the actual location of the user can translate into significant improvements in terms of end-user performance and, implicitly, their quality of experience.

4.4.5 Multi-timescale network slice reservation (A14)

Collected KPI	Justification
K4	We propose a set of slice reservation policies, based on the theory of online convex optimization, which enables the Service Provider to learn how to reserve resources optimally, while respecting the financial budget and service level agreements.

In this activity, we run experiments to evaluate the performance of the Online Learning for Reservations (OLR) algorithm and its extensions, namely the slice orchestration (OLR-SO) and mixed time scale (OLR-

MTS), proposed in Section 5.5 of Deliverable 3.1 [26]. We examine how system factors affect the learning performance and explain how this affects the design of network virtualization marketplaces.

A network operator (NO) sells virtualized resources to service providers (SPs), which consist of (i) wireless spectrum, (ii) backhaul capacity, (iii) computing, and (iv) storage resources. In the multi time scale case, we consider that the SP can reserve: $[0, D_1]$ radio resources at the base stations (BSs); $[0, D_2]$ link capacity that connects the BSs to the servers; and $[0, D_3]$ processing capacity at the servers, where D_1, D_2, D_3 are the maximum reservation requests. When $D = 1$, we deal with normalized reservations, and all variables are expressed in terms of the flow volume (Mbps). Two cases are studied, based on the distribution of the parameters of interest (i.e., user needs and price evolution): Case 1: parameters are uniformly distributed and Case 2: parameters are drawn from non-stationary process. For the evaluation, average regret over time and constraint violation over time are used as metrics.

4.4.5.1 Main performance evaluation results

In the figures that follow, OLR and OLR-MTS are plotted for simulation parameters $K = 3$ and $D = 1$, unless stated otherwise. Similarly, for OLR-SO and OLR-MTS-SO, the parameters are chosen as $K = 3$ and $D = [0.5, 1, 0.5]$, unless stated otherwise.

In Figure 50 and Figure 51, we compare the convergence of the OLR and OLR-SO solutions, respectively, to the convergence of the theoretical bounds (regret and fit). Since the theoretical bound reflects the worst-case situation, we notice that the solution always converges more quickly. In Figure 52 and Figure 53, we present a comparison between OLR and OLR-MTS, and OLR-SO and OLR-MTS-SO, respectively. We observe that the MTS versions (i.e., OLR-MTS and OLR-MTS-SO) exhibit a faster regret convergence; yet, the difference is small and eventually both algorithms reach asymptotically a zero mean regret state.

From Figure 54 and Figure 55, we plot the influence of the learning rates on the regret and violation convergence. We set $\nu = 1$ and $\mu \in \{0.1, 0.05, 0.01\}$. As predicted in our analysis, a lower value of μ favors over-reservation, hence the performance is better and the budget consumption is higher. Figure 56 and Figure 57 delineate the effect of period length K and diameter D on the regret of OLR. Indeed, it is shown that the regret grows linearly as K and D increase, leading to performance drop. The same observations but for OLR-SO are depicted in Figure 58 and Figure 59.

In Figure 60, we plot the performance and violation ratio (i.e., performance/violation of OLR or OLR-MTS over the performance/violation of the benchmark) and we showcase that OLR and OLR-MTS achieve their best performance for $B = 2$ in the stationary case (i.e., Case 1) and $B = 1$ for the non-stationary case (i.e., Case 2). The respective violation ration in the latter case is 1.65% of the total allocated budget, which is outstanding, given that it surpasses the 1.016 performance achieved at $B = 4$. Similarly, for OLR-SO and OLR-MTS-SO in Figure 61, $B = 1$ and $B = 4$ achieve the best performance in Case 1, while $B = 2$ and $B = 8$ dominate in the non-stationary Case 2.

Figure 50. Regret and violation convergence of OLR.

Figure 51. Regret and violation convergence of OLR-SO.

Figure 52. Comparison between OLR and OLR-MTS in regret and violation convergence.

Figure 53. Comparison between OLR-SO and OLR-MTS-SO in regret and violation convergence.

Figure 54. Impact of learning rate of OLR for different values of learning rates.

Figure 55. Impact of learning rate of OLR-SO for different values of learning rates.

Figure 56. Effect of K in regret of OLR.

Figure 57. Effect of D in regret of OLR.

Figure 58. Effect of K in regret of OLR-SO.

Figure 59 Effect of D in regret of OLR-SO.

Figure 60. Performance and violation ratio of OLR and OLR-MTS with respect to benchmark.

Figure 61. Performance and violation ratio of OLR-SO and OLR-MTS-SO with respect to benchmark.

Here, we evaluated the performance of the proposed algorithms for slice reservation, namely OLR and its variants, OLR-MTS and OLR-SO. Our strategies, specifically, provide optimal slice orchestration even when the SP demands are time-varying and are robust to arbitrary changes in resource costs. The results show the convergence of OLR and OLR-SO in both stationary and non-stationary cases, and it can be concluded that the OLR-MTS performs better than the OLR.

4.4.6 Testing EnergyEdgeCloudSim (A15)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	EnergyEdgeCloudSim uses an internal model to estimate the energy consumption and savings on energy consumption of the VNFs.
K2	Saving on computational resources are related to saving on computational resources.
K3	This metric is provided by EnergyEdgeCloudSim.
K4	The OPEX savings achieved by EnergyEdgeCloudSim come exclusively from the energy savings explained in K1.

Regarding this activity, we do not have relevant results to be reported in this deliverable specific to EnergyEdgeCloudSim. The validation of this tool is now linked to the HADES approach that has been reported in Section 4.4.9.

4.4.7 Towards autonomous VNF scaling (A16)

Collected KPI	Justification
K4	We formulated the scaling problem as a multi-objective problem which includes the cost associated to the instantiation of a VNF. The proposed DRL agent can minimize the number of SLA violations while keeping the number of replicas under control, which saves opex compared to a traditional solution (overprovisioning).

In section 5.2 of D4.2 [2], we presented two scaling algorithms: a traditional Proportional Integral (PI) solution and RL based scaling solution. To compare both solutions, we use the simulator S1, described in D5.1 [3]. The results of this comparison were actually presented in D5.1, Section 4.4.7. Therefore, to avoid replicating information, we do not show them here.

Complementing the results, we also trained and evaluated a Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) agent using Stable-Baselines3 (SB3) default values. SB3 is a framework that implements popular RL algorithms for benchmarking purposes. PPO is a model-free algorithm that does not require knowledge of the system dynamics. Moreover, PPO is an on-policy algorithm which means that the algorithm improves the strategy that is used to make decisions, resulting in more stable learning during training [31]. PPO is also easier to implement and tune than other RL algorithms. We trained the agent following the same approach as reported in D5.1.

The objective of this RL agent is to fulfill the agreed SLA with the minimum number of replicas. Therefore, in every time step, the agent pays an immediate cost depending on how good or bad the action it took is. The cost of taking action when the environment moves from one state to another can be defined as a weighted function, including the following contributions.

- If the agent cannot fulfill the SLA, it incurs a performance cost w_{perf} , which is paid every time the perceived peak latency exceeds a predefined threshold. The cost is zero otherwise.
- If the agent must deploy a new replica, a resource cost w_{res} is paid; this can be seen as a rental cost in cloud environments or the consumed energy of the replica while it is running.

We evaluated different cost function weights ($(w_{perf}, w_{res}) = (0.99, 0.01), (0.5, 0.5), \text{ and } (0.01, 0.99)$) to show how the scalers can adapt their behavior based on what they are focused on optimizing. For instance, by optimizing performance over resources, the scaler will more likely pay attention to fulfilling the SLA while disregarding the number of replicas. Since the RL behavior during training highly depends on the initial weights of the neural network, we trained the PPO scaler several times with different seeds. In each training, the same weight configuration is used. Notice that, despite training and testing the RL in separate processes, RL can still learn during the testing phase, similar to an online learning method. On the contrary, once the PI parameter values are set, its behavior is deterministic. Moreover, for the reward function defined here, the best set of PI parameters is insensitive to the weights. Figure 62 shows the behavior of the proposed scalers on the testing trace in terms of the peak latency, where the red line identifies the SLA. In this case, the SLA specifies a service's maximum tolerated peak latency (24ms). Similarly, Figure 63 shows how many violations are made by the scalers.

Figure 62. Testing results showing the peak latency vs replicas trade-off.

Figure 63. Testing results showing the SLA violations vs replicas trade-off.

As it can be seen, when the PPO is trained with a reward function that optimizes the resources over the performance (i.e., green dots), the average amount of replicas is always lower than five; however, there is no guarantee of the achievement of the SLA. For instance, the darker green dot in both figures creates, on average, 4.003 replicas, obtaining an average peak latency of 600.75ms, which translates into violating the SLA about 91.7% of the time. On the contrary, when the scaler is trained with a reward

function that optimizes the performance over the resources (i.e., blue dots), the violations are reduced to their minimum at the expense of creating more replicas. The scaler on the darker blue dot, for example, creates an average of 5.544 replicas, obtaining an average of 8.5ms of peak latency, minimizing the violation of the SLA to 0.0023% of the time. It also can be observed how the PPO tries to find a balance between both objectives when the weights are equal (i.e., orange dots). This clearly indicates that the PPO performs plausibly, optimizing the objective it should optimize and trying to balance both objectives when indicated. On average, the solution in dark orange creates 5.04 replicas, having an average of 10.24ms of peak latency and violating the SLA just 1.1% of the time. Nevertheless, without having an optimal strategy, which indicates the optimal number of replicas achieving the SLA, there is no simple and fast comparison between the designed strategies. In that sense, we use the PI scaler as a reference point to the RL-based scaler since it provides a solution that shows a good trade-off between both objectives (i.e., minimizing the number of replicas while fulfilling the SLA). The solution shown as a black diamond in both figures creates, on average, 4.82 replicas, having an average of 9.62ms of peak latency and violating the SLA 0.0098% of the time.

4.4.8 Auto scaling Virtualised RAN caches (A17)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	We formulated an optimization problem for dynamic cache rental, file caching and user association for wireless edge caching networks in a fashion that maximizes aggregated delay savings and/or ensures servicing fairness across users, while respecting average budget constraint.
K4	Follows from the explanation of K3 above.

In Section 4.4.8 of Deliverable 5.1 [3], we presented the evaluation of our proposed elastic femtocaching algorithm, devised for maximizing the performance of vRANs, while respecting the monetary budget spent when leasing cache capacity. No updates are reported in this deliverable; however, Deliverable 5.3 will expand this activity.

4.4.9 Energy-aware VNF orchestration (A26)

Collected KPI	Justification
K1	We use EnergyEdgeCloudSim to measure the energy and compute energy savings.
K2	The reduction on energy consumption comes directly from the savings on energy consumption.

In D4.1, we have presented a solution for proactive auto-scaling in the edge. In this deliverable, we report the feasibility analysis of this approach in a simulated edge-based infrastructure that serves an actual dynamic edge workload.

4.4.9.1 Research Questions

The methodology used in this study is the goal-question-metric approach as follows: "Analyze the feasibility of using our proactive auto-scaling approach to reduce the energy consumption in edge-based infrastructures". To achieve this objective, we set the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: *To what extent can our proposal reduce energy consumption in edge infrastructures?* This question will reveal whether our approach results in a significant decrease in energy consumption.

RQ2: *Which policy performs best in decreasing energy consumption and minimizing the number of failed requests?* This question is an extension of the previous one but keeps in mind that deactivating resources may result in failed requests due to a lack of available resources.

RQ3: *Is our approach fast enough to be feasible to be used at runtime?* This question evaluates the applicability of auto-scaling at runtime in terms of the execution time of the modules implemented. Since the critical point in terms of execution time is the Essential Node Identifier (ENI) module, the evaluation will focus on this module for different problem sizes and operation modes.

RQ4: *How important is it to adjust the mode of operation at runtime? In which cases does it make sense?* The answers to these questions will reveal when the system can be fed back with information from current deployments to modify its mode of operation.

4.4.9.2 Experimental setup

To answer the RQs, we have built an IoT scenario using the EdgeCloudSim simulator [32] EdgeCloudSim is an open-source tool that provides a simulation environment specific to Edge Computing. We extended this simulator to consider the nodes' energy consumption during the simulation, returning the energy

consumed by each edge device at the end of the simulation using the energy consumption model presented in Section 3.2.4 of Deliverable 5.1. To ensure its correct operation, the simulator's core remains intact, and we have performed extensive validation work.

The Shanghai Telcom dataset [33] has been used to simulate the edge workload. It contains six months of mobile phone records accessing the Internet via base stations distributed over Shanghai (i.e. more than 7.2 million records from 9481 mobile devices and 3233 base stations).

A previous data analysis [34] revealed that the workload of June had the lowest percentage of records with missing data and that the second day is representative of the rest days of June (the overall workload is periodic). In the same work, we observe a different trend in three different periods of June: (1) a period in which the number of requests increases over time, which includes late night and early morning; (2) an interval of time in which the number of requests decreases over time (morning); and (3) a period in which the number of requests fluctuates, which includes afternoon to evening. Thus, we will apply our proposal to these three scenarios to evaluate their behavior in different workload contexts. As in [34], we also select one hour from each period: the 2nd, 12th, and 14th hours simulating 14 minutes of each one that contains 107, 276, and 270 requests, respectively. The user requests will ask for the service provided by eight different applications, with varying requirements in terms of CPU, memory, disk, peripherals, and data to transmit and receive. Applications are equally likely to be requested by users.

Regarding the number of IoT devices (i.e., users) and requests, these values are specified for each workload pattern according to the dataset's number of devices and requests. Experiments consider an infrastructure of 20 edge devices with randomized characteristics. Their maximal energy consumption is between 20 and 300 Watts; the idle energy consumption (α) is between 20 and 50%, P^{Tx} and P^{Rx} (transmission power when transmitting and receiving) between 1-3 Watts; the sleep energy consumption (β) between 0.01 and 0.5; the switching energy consumption is between 10-50 Joules; the deployment energy consumption between 0.5-1 Joules; the instructions per second of the CPU between 100000 and 300000 million¹². In the same way, the applications' requirements (CPU, RAM, disk, and data to send and receive) have also been randomized. Experiments have been performed 30 times on one thread of an AMD Ryzen 7 1700X processor, and we have conducted a subsequent exhaustive statistical study of the results¹³.

4.4.9.3 Reduction on energy consumption

This section evaluates to what extent our proposal reduces energy consumption and its impact on the number of failed requests.

4.4.9.3.1 Dynamic energy consumption

Sometimes, different applications and users share the same node, so they cannot go into sleep mode. In this case, the only way to reduce energy consumption is by assigning applications to the most energy-efficient nodes. Thus, in this section, we focus on reducing (dynamic) energy consumption obtained through our new orchestrator policy, Green fit. This policy compares the energy consumption of running applications. Then, this policy selects the one that consumes less energy from among the nodes that meet the application requirements, with sufficient resources available and located within the user's reach. We compare the energy consumption obtained by Green fit with Best fit [35] (which selects the node with the most available resources), First fit (which assigns the application to the first node that meets the application requirements), Random fit (which selects a random node that accomplishes the application's needs [36]), and Fastest fit (which searches for the most powerful node in terms of CPU capable of running the application).

Figure 64. Energy consumption of the analysed policies.

¹² Results spreadsheet available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7248106>

¹³ At this level of the development, activity A14 has been validated by using simple Python scripts.

Figure 64 shows the results in terms of energy consumption for the three periods of time considered and compares them with Green fit. In all cases, our policy obtains the lowest energy consumption (we consider dynamic and idle energy consumption). Specifically, experiments show up to 15.9% of reduction in energy consumption (14th hour) compared with Fastest fit. As expected, the decrease in energy consumption is major for the 12th and 14th hours (the hours with more requests) since we focus on dynamic energy consumption, which is directly related to workload. Regarding the execution time, predictably, the Fastest fit obtains the lowest service time on average, having Green fit and Random fit similar service times on average. Note that all the assignments accomplish the applications' requirements in terms of QoS. The percentage of failed requests is 0% in all cases, with enough infrastructure resources to allocate the user requests.

4.4.9.3.2 Dynamic and idle energy consumption

We apply our auto-scaling approach for the same infrastructure, applications, and periods. We have set the auto-scaling interval in one minute, and the orchestration policy used is Green fit.

Some predictive models provide just the number of expected requests, not the applications demanded—as is our case [37] [38]. As the resources needed to meet these requests will depend on the required applications, we have elaborated four resource reservation policies. If we expect ten requests in the next period and handle eight applications with a uniform probability of being requested, each application would be requested 1.25 times, which is not feasible. Then, we consider that each application is demanded once, while two requests are uncertain. On this basis, we define four assignment policies: *Random*, which would assign the two remaining requests randomly; *Oversizing*, which would consider that each application is demanded twice; and *Most/Least* resource demanding, which would assign these two uncertain requests to the most/least resource-demanding task. Note that our algorithm gives a solution for the worst-case scenario, in which the entire workload arrives immediately after performing the auto-scaling.

Figure 65 shows the average energy consumption (left y-axis) and percentage of failed requests (right y-axis) obtained with the different resource reservation policies and operation modes. As shown in Figure 65 and as expected, the Least resource-demanding policy is the one that gets the highest energy consumption reductions. Regarding the number of failed requests, in the Operation Mode 1 (OM1) (left side of Figure 65), the second hour is the period with the most failed requests, with 1.5% in the best case (Most and Least resource-demanding policies, respectively). Experiments show a 24.8% decrease on average in the failed requests using the Most resource demanding policy compared with Oversizing. The policy with the highest number of failed requests is the least resource-demanding and has better energy consumption.

Figure 65. Energy consumption (left y-axis) and percentage of failed requests (right y-axis) applying our auto-scaling approach for OM1 (left) and OM2 (right).

Nevertheless, in the 12th and 14th hours, the Least resource-demanding policy obtains an affordable 1.5% (12th hour) and 1.8% (14th hour) of failed requests, with a decrease in the energy consumption of 14% and 13%, respectively, when compared with Random Fit policy (the second best in terms of energy consumption). This means that this policy could be a good choice in some scenarios. Regarding Operation Mode 2 (OM2) (right side of Figure 65), the percentage of failed requests is 0% or almost 0% in most cases, being 3% in the worst case (2nd hour and Least resource demanding policy). Therefore, the results related to accepted requests are better in some cases than in other proposals. Regarding execution time, all resource reservation policies have obtained similar times since they use the same allocation policy (Green fit).

We compare the energy consumption with and without auto-scaling. Experiments report an average reduction in the energy consumption of 91.1%, 73.3%, and 66.2% in the 2nd, 12th, and 14th hours in the case of OM1, and 90%, 53% and 52.6%, respectively, for OM2 (left side of Figure 66). In the case of OM2, the energy consumption increases by 26% on average compared to OM1. OM1 obtains the most significant reduction in energy consumption in the Least resource-demanding policy, which achieves 92.5% energy savings compared with the Fastest fit (right side of Figure 66), with better performance than other works (and applied to a more heterogeneous infrastructure).

Figure 66. Comparison of average energy consumption with and without auto-scaling (left) and energy consumption reduction in the best case (right).

4.4.9.4 Execution latency

The time it takes for nodes to process a request depends on the nodes' capabilities. This section evaluates the response times for the different modes of operation of the auto-scaling system. Note that the allocation in our proposal ensures the requirements in terms of QoS in all cases. Thus, on average, the time required to complete a request with and without auto-scaling is very similar. Specifically, experiments reveal that OM1 increases on average by 3.2% the response time in the 2nd hour while reducing it by 2.1% and 2.7% for the 12th and 14th hours. In the case of OM2, the response time increases by 2.8% in the 2nd hour, decreasing by 2.8% and 2.6% in the 12th and 14th hours. Note that using more energy-efficient nodes is not necessarily subject to an increase in execution time, being possible to minimize consumption and latency simultaneously [39].

4.4.9.5 Scalability

The time the ENI needs to provide a solution may vary according to the problem size, compromising the proposal's applicability. Thus, this section evaluates the ENI's execution time for different problem sizes. With this purpose, we develop a Benchmark version of our module, which allows setting the number of nodes and expected requests. This section addresses RQ4.

A preliminary study revealed that the ENI returns the solution almost instantly for less than 20 nodes infrastructures. Thus, the number of nodes has been set at 20 and 30, respectively, while the number of expected requests has been increased to the limit of infrastructure resources: up to 330 requests in the case of 20 nodes and up to 410 for an infrastructure of 30 nodes. The characteristics of the nodes (CPU, RAM, storage, free resources, eMax, a, peripherals, etc.) and requests expected (requirements in terms of CPU, RAM, disk, data to transmit/receive, etc.) have been randomized in each experiment.

Figure 67 shows the results of the experiments in which we consider both operation modes of our solution. Regarding OM1, for an infrastructure formed by 20 nodes, the ENI has required about 11 seconds in the worst case (170 requests), and just 0.4 seconds in the case of 90 expected requests. This time decreases to 1.5 seconds when 210 requests are expected and 0.02 when 290. The infrastructure's capability is insufficient when the expected number of requests increases up to 330, returning that the problem is unsatisfactory in about 0.007 seconds. In the case of an infrastructure of 30 edge nodes, the execution time is 0.1, 0.3, and 1.8 seconds when 10, 50, and 90 requests are expected. In the worst case, this time grows to 175 seconds (210 requests, about 50% of the infrastructure's capabilities). Again, this time decreases when the request requirements exceed the infrastructure capacity, being 0.24, 0.009, and 0.01 seconds when 330, 370, and 410 requests are expected.

Figure 67. ENI's execution time according to the problem size.

In OM2, the number of nodes working and their free resources has been randomly generated. To provide a realistic scenario, we consider that the number of nodes working is necessary to allocate 25% of the previous workload (assumed like the current one). This time, ENI returns a solution almost instantaneously in most cases, requiring around 0.02 seconds in the worst case (30 nodes and 170 requests expected). This is because once a node is considered part of the solution, the ENI module will assign it as many tasks as possible to reduce the idle EC. Thus, OM2 helps the ENI to reduce the search space.

Experiments reveal that the execution time is higher when the resources requested are about half of the nodes' capabilities (see Figure 67). The reason for this is that when the number of tasks demanded increases, the number of devices involved and, therefore, the search space increases. We found the peak of this phenomenon when half of the infrastructure resources are demanded, decreasing gradually until all the resources are needed. Experiments also reveal that the execution time highly depends on the requests' requirements and nodes' capabilities, finding a big difference between executions of the same problem size. While the case of an infrastructure of 20 nodes and 170 requests expected requires about 11 seconds on average, in some executions, the time needed is 0.4 seconds. That means that the applicability of our solution in OM1 must be studied for the target infrastructure and expected requests. Experiments reveal that OM2 helps the module return the solution faster regarding the difference between operation modes.

4.4.9.6 Answers to research questions

In this section, we answer the research questions proposed in Section 4.4.9.1.

RQ1: *To what extent can our proposal reduce energy consumption in edge infrastructures? When the infrastructure nodes are shared and cannot be put in sleep mode, we have obtained up to a 15.9% reduction in energy consumption. In this scenario, the more requests are received, the more energy is saved (compared with other policies). Applying the auto-scaling approach, we reduce the energy consumption a 44% in the worst case and up to 92.5% when using the OM1 and the Least resource-demanding policy. The energy consumption reduction is due to the time the nodes remain in sleep mode; the lower the workload, the longer the downtime and the energy consumption reduction. The results show that our proposal has obtained a more significant reduction in energy consumption than other works [36] [40] [41]. This energy savings is even more remarkable when considering non-IT appliances (e.g., cooling and lighting), which can consume around 33%-52% of an infrastructure of up to 500 nodes.*

RQ2: *Which policy performs best in decreasing energy consumption and minimizing the number of failed requests? The joint use of OM1 and the Least resource-demanding policy obtains the most significant energy consumption reduction (up to 92.5%). Although the percentage of failed requests for one of the periods evaluated (2nd hour) is high, the failed requests in the other periods (1.5% and 1.8%) are affordable, which works best for such periods. Regarding the first period (2nd hour), the policy that has worked best is the Most resource-demanding, with just 1.5% of failed requests and a 92.5% of reduction in energy consumption. When the service must have high availability, the ENI's resource-preservative operation mode (OM2) obtains 0%, or almost 0%, failed requests in most cases. Compared to other proposals, our auto-scaling module can obtain better results in request acceptance rate.*

RQ3: *Is our approach fast enough to be feasible to be used at runtime? Experimentation (see Figure 67) shows that the ENI execution time is longer when the services requested require about half of the infrastructure capacity. The applicability of ENI in OM1 will depend on the auto-scaling interval, as the execution time should always be less than this. For 20-node infrastructures, the average execution time obtained in the worst case is 11 seconds. Since performing auto-scaling with a higher frequency does not make sense, we can state that the ENI in OM1 is usable for infrastructures of 20 nodes or less. For more extensive infrastructures, the execution time may be higher than the auto-scaling frequency, compromising the feasibility (although there are significant differences in execution time depending on the application and infrastructure characteristics). In this case, it is possible to decrease the auto-scaling interval, thus reducing the expected workload. The auto-scaling system can reduce the predicted workload automatically if it detects that the execution time is too long. Another solution would be to consider the infrastructure as two separate infrastructures and divide the workload between them. In any case, experiments reveal that the second operation mode (OM2) reduces the search space and helps the algorithm to find a solution almost instantaneously.*

RQ4: *How important is it to adjust the mode of operation at runtime? In which cases does it make sense? The experiments revealed that when the number of failed requests is too high, the Least resource-demanding resource-allocation policy achieves the most significant reduction in energy consumption with acceptable failed response rates. Nevertheless, sometimes, the number of failed requests may be excessive. In such cases, modifying the resource reservation policy when such a pattern is detected (e.g., to Most resource demanding or Oversizing, see Figure 65) would solve the issue. This illustrates the importance of providing an auto-scaling solution with different modes of operation so that the behavior of the auto-scaling solution can be adapted to suit the changing context of dynamic workloads. Concerning the autoscaling's execution time, the feasibility of using the ENI module in OM1 for infrastructures of 20 nodes or less has been demonstrated in Section 4.4.9.5. However, for more extensive infrastructures or when the workload characteristics make the auto-scaling process difficult, it is possible to modify the operating mode of the algorithm at runtime. As discussed in RQ3, another solution would be to increase the auto-scaling frequency (thus decreasing the expected workload), which can be quickly done at runtime.*

4.5 NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning

Evaluation E6 focuses on the evaluation of NI solutions for long-timescale operations, i.e., MANO, VNF placement and the associated resource allocation. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of challenges and solutions related to E6 via activity A20 and A22. Table 21 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate progress and main innovations of such activities.

Table 21. List of activities for E6.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Evaluation Progress
A20	Anticipatory capacity allocation	E6	D3	K2, K4	K2, K4	3	No	90%
	<i>Main innovation:</i> Anticipatory provisioning of network resources to individual network slices so as to avoid underprovisioning while minimizing the unnecessary allocation of resources							
A21	Virtual Machine reservation	E6	D3	K2, K9	K2, K9	3	No	100%
	<i>Main innovation:</i> Prediction of the number of VMs that need to be allocated in advance to each NSSI, so as to run the VNFs required to serve the demand generated by the corresponding mobile service							
A22	Minimisation of video streaming slice OPEX	E6	D3	K4, K9	K4, K9	3	No	100%
	<i>Main innovation:</i> Minimisation of the monetary OPerating EXpenses (OPEX) associated to running the video streaming slices at the network Edge							
A27	Learning with Predictions for Edge Caching and Computing	E6	D9	K9	K9	3	No	80%
	<i>Main innovation:</i> Online learning-based network management using forecasting models (or predictions).							

4.5.1 Anticipatory capacity allocation (A20)

Collected KPI	Justification
K2	In the data-driven evaluation with a real national-level dataset from an operator, we verified that the proposed solution requires less resources to be computed w.r.t. to previous state-of-the-art solutions. In Table 18 . Required complexity (mean training time) of each of the considered algorithms., we show that the required complexity (mean training time) is reduced by 50% for two different use cases.
K4	The proposed solution reduces the Mean Square Error of the traffic forecast at least by 30%, peaking at 50% for some of the services

This activity focuses on a capacity forecasting scenario, where the anticipatory NI function is responsible of allocating network resources (e.g., compute, transport, or memory resources) to each one of the network slices present in the corresponding section of the network. The critical trade-off to be considered here is that of ensuring no underestimation of required resources, which would cause a disruption of the end user service and a possible violation of Service Level Agreements with service providers and slice requesters, while minimizing any overprovisioning that would freeze unnecessary resources, preventing those resources to be used for other slices or elements of the network.

The solution presented by the DAEMON project addressing this problem is named TES-RNN. It was introduced in Section 4.1 of Deliverable 4.1 [26], where its full hybrid approach incorporating both statistical analysis and deep learning structures was described. The outcome of the application of TES-RNN in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [3], where it was shown that it can outperform the capacity forecasting performance of state-of-the-art solutions, providing also an in-depth analysis of a prediction instance and proving that TES-RNN is flexible and allows us to control the SLA violations and the operation point in the trade-off between SLA violations and overprovisioning. We also provided in Section 3.1 of Deliverable 4.2 [2] the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of Deliverable 2.2 [27], as well as its mapping to major standards. Indeed, TES-RNN comply

with the full hybrid approach proposed in Section 4.2.4 of D2.2 [27] as a better alternative to pure deep learning AI models commonly used in the literature for network traffic forecasting. We refer to the mentioned previous deliverables for a more detailed description of the methods and results.

In the analysis presented in Section 4.6.1 of Deliverable 5.1 [3] we showed that TES-RNN provided gains up to 25% over state-of-the-art forecasting methods particularly designed for the target problem in practical application use cases characterized by real-world traffic volumes and dynamics. These foundations motivated further research on hybrid approaches to NI design, and, in fact, lead to the development of Activity A25, which was presented in Section 4.3.3.

4.5.2 Virtual Machine reservation (A21)

Collected KPI	Justification
K2	We collected the KPIs through a simulation and data-driven evaluation making use of a real national-level dataset from an operator. DAEMON's solution is able to reduce the cost of anticipatory reservation of VM by 40% (cf. Section 4.6.2 of Deliverable 5.1 [3]), what in turn reduces the computational resources required at the edge.
K9	We have shown that DAEMON's proposal is able to reduce the aforementioned costs while keeping the percentage of time with SLA violations below 0.5%.

This activity targets a capacity forecasting use case intended for a core network datacenter. In the situation in which different video streaming services (or, more generally, any service provider) are assigned individual and dedicated Network Slice Subnet Instances (NSSI), the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) that is responsible of the datacenter resources control must predict the number of Virtual Machines (VMs) required for each NSSI *in advance*, such that all the required VNFs can be deployed to serve the demand generated by the corresponding service. Naturally, it is desirable that only the strictly necessary set of VMs is reserved for each NSSI to reduce unnecessary costs. In this scenario, we develop a suitable NI to manage VM reservations to accommodate future demands for each NSSI/service.

The solution presented by the DAEMON project addressing this problem is coined LossLeaP, for *Loss Learning Predictor*. It was introduced in Section 4.2 of Deliverable 4.1 [26] where we show how LossLeaP is able to learn the implicit (and partially unknown to the operator) operating costs of the datacenter and the local VM management strategies. The outcome of the application of LossLeaP in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.2 of Deliverable 5.1 [3] where it was shown that LossLeaP is substantially more efficient and precise than even a fine-tuned decision-making policy based on a legacy prediction. We also provided in Section 3.2 of Deliverable 4.2 [2] the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of Deliverable 2.2 [27], as well as its mapping to major standards. Indeed, LossLeaP comply with the guidelines from Section 4.1 of D2.2 [27] in terms of adaptation of legacy AI models to the specificities of real-world NI problems, and the proposed solution overcomes the common loss-metric mismatch in a fully automated way, in alignment with the strategy outlined in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2 [27]. The experiments were performed with traffic demands for each video streaming service from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of this document and in Section 3.3.3. of Deliverable 5.1 [3] We refer to the mentioned deliverables for a more detailed description of the methods and results.

The significant gains provided by this solution (achieving with a 4x – 20x reduction of SLA violations), motivates us to extend the refinement of the design of loss-learning architectures for NI to use them to other different NI use cases, and these new results are planned to appear in the next project deliverables.

4.5.3 Minimization of video streaming slice OPEX (A22)

Collected KPI	Justification
K4	We collected the KPIs through a simulation and data-driven evaluation making use of a real national-level dataset from an operator. DAEMON's solution is able to provide an OPEX saving of 30% w.r.t. to state-of-the-art (SotA) solutions, with the addition that the SotA solution requires a perfect knowledge of the OPEX derived from the network operation, while DAEMON's solution is generic and is able to learn an unknown function characterizing the OPEX. The gain w.r.t. to standard approaches is above 60%
K9	DAEMON's solution is able to achieve OPEX saving that are only a 10% higher than the ideal optimal solution. Here we should note that the optimal solution is an unattainable approach in which it is assumed that the system knows the future traffic with perfect accuracy.

This activity casts the capacity forecasting problem in a mobile Edge environment where computational facilities serve a large number of individual radio access base stations located in their proximity, with the aim of reducing latency in service provisioning. This activity is another use case of the self-learning solution LossLeaP mentioned in the case of A21 presented in Section 4.6.2, and it also shares with that activity the use of the realistic traffic demands for different services from Dataset D3 described in Section 3.3 of this document and in Section 3.3.3 of Deliverable 5.1 [3]. In this case, our management goal is the minimization of the economic Operating Expenses (OPEX) incurred by running the video streaming slices at the network Edge. Therefore, the tasks is to recurrently readapting and rescaling the computation resources associated to each NSSI.

This activity serves as an example of the flexibility of the LossLeaP solution mentioned in Section 4.6.2. The outcome of the application of LossLeaP in the proposed scenario was described in Section 4.6.3 of Deliverable 5.1 [3] where it was shown that loss-learning models can effectively support NI also in the case of resource allocations that target the reduction of OPEX. We also provided in Section 3.3 of Deliverable 4.2 [2] the relationship of this activity with the requirements and guidelines of Deliverable 2.2 [27] as well as its mapping to major standards. As mentioned for the previous activity, LossLeaP comply with the guidelines from Section 4.1 of D2.2 [27] in alignment with the strategy outlined in Section 4.1.3 of D2.2 [27]. We refer to the mentioned previous deliverables for a more detailed description of the methods and results.

Experiments with real-world measurement data prove the significant advantage that a loss-learning approach yields over a state-of-the-art capacity predictor. These findings foster further research on these applications, and current non-finished advances on OPEX reduction jointly (and automatically) handled with admission control through NI solutions will be presented in incoming deliverables.

4.5.4 Learning with Predictions for Edge Caching and Computing (A27)

Collected KPI	Justification
K9	We propose online learning-based caching policies that utilize predictions (of unknown quality) to boost performance, if those predictions are accurate, while still maintaining robust performance bounds otherwise. Thus, our proposed system reaches very close (or coincides) with the optimal performance.

As mentioned in Section 3.4 of D4.2 [2] our goal is to deduce an online learning policy that leverages predictions for future service/content requests of the edge server to accelerate performance. To that end, we simulated multiple cases.

Case1: Single cache

In this case, a cache edge receives requests from users and learns to cache the files that are most likely to be requested. The requests are generated using two real datasets, and one stationary request pattern. Each request is made for a file from a library of 10k unique files, and the cache capacity is set at $C=100$. For each request pattern, we plot the average utility (hit-rate) achieved by the different algorithms that we simulated. Recall that BHS is the Best in Hindsight policy (the benchmark we seek to match), OGD is an online gradient descent algorithm of [42] (current state-of-the-art). And the OBC is our proposed policy. The ρ parameters refelects the quality of the predictions fed to our algorithm. A quality of 0 means that every prediction is wrong., whereas a value of 0.7 means that 70% of the predictions are correct (i.e., it is indeed the case that the file predicted to be requested is requested). As shown in the figures, OBC hit rate increases with time and approaches the benchmark. It does so faster for the case of good predictions, which is expected. Nonetheless OBC's hit rate still increases with time even in the case of bad predictions, which is in line of what was proven.

Figure 68. Utility in the single cache model with one rec-sys of different recommendation quality levels (i.e., ρ) in (a) Zipf requests with $\zeta = 1.1$, (b) YouTube request traces, (c) MovieLens request traces.

Case 2: Caching network

In this case, we consider a caching network with 3 caches and 4 user locations, where the first two locations are connected with caches 1 and 2, and the rest are connected to caches 2 and 3. The utility vector is $(1, 2, 100)$, $\forall i, j$, (i.e., the utility for serving a request from cache 1 is 1, and from cache 2 is 10, and so on). Thus, an efficient policy places popular files on cache 3. This is the setup used in [1] that we adopt here to make a fair comparison. For the stationary request scenario, we consider a library of $N = 1000$ files and cache capacity of $C = 100$. For the trace scenario, files with at least 10 requests are considered, forming a library of $N = 456$ files for the YouTube dataset, and we set $C = 50$, and $N = 1152$ for the ML dataset, and we increase $C = 100$. The location of each request is selected uniformly at random. Similar to the single-cache case, we plot the average utility (which resembles of the online policies and the best static configuration until each t). Recall that the area between a policy and BHS is the average regret of that policy. To avoid clutter, we shade this area for OGD in the first subfigure, as an example, and for OBC in the next two.

Figure 69. Attained utility in the bipartite model under different recommendation quality levels in (a) Zipf requests with $\zeta = 1.1$, (b) YouTube request traces, (c) MovieLens request trace.

The effect of good predictions is again evident as OBC maintains utility within 5.5% of BHS's utility after 2.5k time steps. Also, even when the predictions are inaccurate, OBC preserves the sublinear regret, achieving a gap of 30.4% and 8.5% for $t = 1k$ and $t = 10k$, respectively. Akin patterns appear in the trace scenarios. Namely the similarity between OBC with good predictions and BHS, and the improvement in OBC utility despite predictions.

Case 3: Single cache, multiple predictions sources.

In this case, we adapt the setup of case 1. However, we consider that the caching algorithm has access to more than one source of predictions, as discussed in D4.2, Sec 4.2, the experts framework is used here.

We evaluate the experts algorithm (XC) with 3 experts: an FTRL expert, and two other optimistic experts, resembling two different prediction sources. The first optimistic expert is endowed with a predictor (e.g., a recommendation system) that gets followed with probability $\rho = 2\%$. For the other it is $\rho = 20\%$. As shown in the plots, XC achieves negative regret on the traces (it outperforms the BHS policy) and converges to the performance of the best expert (0.20 utility). In the stationary Zipf request pattern, the optimal cache is for the files with top probabilities, which are easily captured by BHS. Thus, BHS policy performs the best. Below, we show the advantages of OBC compared to XC with two experts: an FTRL expert and a recommendation-based expert. ρ alternates between 100% and 0% (i.e., requesting the file recommended at a time step t , and any other file. Here, OBC outperforms π_{XC} since the alternating prediction accuracy induces frequent switching between the two experts in XC.

Figure 70. Utility in the single cache model with two rec-sys of recommendation qualities $\rho = 2\%$ and $\rho = 20\%$, each modeled as an expert within XC, in (a) Zipf requests with $\zeta = 1.1$, (b) YouTube request traces, (c) MovieLens request traces. (d) Comparison.

4.6 NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface

Evaluation E7 targets the assessment of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), a novel technology comprised of a large passive antenna array able to reflect impinging signals with configurable phases, which help attaining beamforming gains passively. The DAEMON consortium performed assessments of

challenges and solutions related to E7 via activity A23. Table 22 summarises the tools, KPIs, TRL, PoC plans, approximate progress and main innovations of such activity.

Table 22. List of activities for E7.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Progress
A23	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Prototype	E7	T9	K6	None	3	Yes	50%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Increase spectrum capacity by using reconfigurable reflectors								

4.6.1 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Prototype (A23)

Collected KPI	Justification
K5	This KPI has not yet been collected.

This activity involves the design, an implementation of a RIS prototype that can validate the NI developed within WP3.

Figure 71. RIS board and unit cell.

The main purpose of our RIS is to perform 3D beamforming passively, i.e., re-focus the energy received from impinging RF signals towards specified directions without active (energy-consuming) RF components. Figure 71 illustrates a **board** consisting of a grid of $N_x \times N_y$ **unit cells** distributed in a 2D array. Unit cells are elements that can reflect RF signals with configurable phase shifts.

Phase shifts are configured by a microcontroller unit (MCU), which can be programmed from an external controller. Conventional RIS designs are characterised by dedicated $N_x \times N_y$ connections from the MCU to each unit cell. However, MCUs only support a limited number of such connections, which constrains the maximum number of cells and, consequently, the achievable beamforming gains. A more scalable approach is to connect each cell with a pair of buses, denoted as **column/row cell selection buses**, that select the cell to be configured, and a **phase configuration bus**, which communicates the desired configuration index out of a discrete set. In this way, we reduce the complexity of the design from $N_x \times N_y$ to $N_x + N_y$ connections per board. As shown in the right-hand side of Figure 71, each unit cell connects both column/row selection buses with an **AND gate**. Hence, when the MCU sets a high voltage state in row x and column y , the MCU activates the configuration bus for unit cell (x, y) , whereas all the remaining gates across the board will output a low voltage state (0 V). Each cell also integrates a set of **flip-flop D**, which exploit the high-state exiting the AND gate as a rising edge to update and send out the value stored in memory. We designed our RIS with 3-bit phase shifters, which enable high spatial resolution codebooks. Therefore, each cell uses three 1-bit phase configuration buses and three flip-flops. The latter are connected to the **configuration ports** in an **RF switch**. An RF switch is a component that can redirect the RF signal received from an **input port** towards one **output port**, as indicated by the configuration ports. The input port is connected to a **patch antenna**, the ultimate responsible for interacting with the medium, through a **feeding line**. Each output port (except one) uses an open-ended **delay line** with a suitably-designed length to reflect impinging signals with a specific time delay, shifting the signal phase. We reserve one output port of the RF switch to connect an **absorber**, an impedance-matching component that absorbs the energy of incoming signals instead of reflecting them back. We call this configuration absorption state, and it let us virtually optimise the reflective area of the RIS to meet system

constraints. For instance, we can flexibly adapt to different time constraints when optimising the RIS configuration (which takes longer the larger the number of active cells in the RIS. This is illustrated Figure 72. Alternatively, an energy harvester may be employed instead to re-use the dissipated energy to feed a low-consuming MCU, becoming self-sustainable boards, which we leave for future work.

Our RIS design is modular: as shown in Figure 73 multiple boards can be coordinated through a common bus. The disposition of the unit cells across different boards has been carefully designed to have a separation of $\lambda/2$, where λ is the operating wavelength. Such modular boards let us increase/decrease the physical area of our structure without compromising the inter-cell distance.

Figure 72. Shape-adaptive RIS.

Figure 73. Multi-board RIS.

We prototyped our design using a two-layer PCB (Printed Circuit Board). The substrate material is FR-4, a composite material made of woven fiberglass with an epoxy resin binder that is flame resistant. Its relative electrical permittivity is in the range of $\epsilon_r = [4.1,4.8]$, and is coated by two layers of 1-ounce copper ($35 \mu\text{m}$). In general, thick substrates and high permittivity lead to small bandwidths and low efficiency due to surface waves. Since the operating frequency of our prototype is $f = 5.3 \text{ GHz}$ ($\lambda = 56.56 \text{ mm}$), we chose a substrate thickness of $h = 0.53 \text{ mm}$, that is in the range $0.003\lambda \leq h \leq 0.05\lambda$.

4.6.1.1 Patch Antenna

Patch antennas are implemented by cutting out a particular shape from the copper of the board's upper layer. In this way, the remaining metallic shape can radiate at the desired frequency while the back layer operates as ground for the antenna. Following the conventional literature on antenna design, we used a rectangular shape, as shown in Figure 74. In more detail, we used the transmission-line model from [1] to calculate its width W and length L as follows:

$$W = \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{0.5(\epsilon_r + 1)}} = 16.9 \text{ mm},$$

$$L = L_{eff} - 2\Delta L = 13.15 \text{ mm},$$

where $\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1 + 12 \frac{h}{w}} \right)$ is the effective dielectric constant that takes into account the fact that the electric field lines reside in the substrate and partially in the air, $L_{eff} = \frac{c}{2f\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}}$ is the effective length, c is the speed of light, and $\Delta L = 0.412h \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{eff} + 0.3}{\epsilon_{eff} - 0.258} \cdot \frac{h/w + 0.264}{h/w + 0.8}$ is an offset to obtain the antenna physical length from L_{eff} .

Figure 74. Layout of the patch antenna design.

Figure 75. TDR chart of a 0.95 mm-width microstrip.

As shown in Figure 74, a microstrip connects each antenna to the RF switch. To this end, we selected an inset feeding approach, with a notch at the edge of the antenna. This approach allows us to adapt the antenna to a precise characteristic impedance, which is crucial to maximize power transfer. Given this

notch (see details later), we refined the geometry derived before with the parameters shown Figure 74 by exhaustive search using a full-wave simulator, thus setting $W = 15.5$ mm and $L = 12.8$ mm. In the following we describe in detail two crucial parameters, namely (i) the width of the microstrip that connects the RF switch (see Figure 74), and (ii) the position of the notch. The former is essential to guarantee impedance-matching, and, since the usual characteristic impedance is 50Ω , the width of all the microstrips must be selected accordingly.

4.6.1.2 Width of the feeding line

To avoid power loss between the feeding line and the RF switch, their characteristic impedance should match. Therefore, we used a standard model to estimate a 0.95-mm line width, which equalises the 50Ω -impedance of the switch.

To validate this, we printed a 0.95mm-width microstrip and applied the Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) technique using a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) to measure the actual characteristic impedance along the line. TDR generates a pulse with a short rising time that allows us to calculate the impedance along the line based on the received reflections.

As depicted in Figure 75 (green), this experiment shows that the actual impedance along the line is smaller than the predicted 50Ω . Such a mismatch with the impedance of the switch would incur some power loss at every unit cell and, consequently, poor beamforming gains overall.

Consequently, we opted for a simple empirical approach: we printed out several 135 mm-length microstrips with different widths, and applied the TDR method to each sample. Figure 75 shows with an orange line the result of the selected sample, with a width equal to 0.75 mm, which provided the best performance. Ignoring the large oscillation at the beginning of the line, which is due to the soldered SMA connector that we used to connect the line and the VNA, the experiment shows a perfect match with the expected value of 50Ω .

4.6.1.3 Notch

The second relevant parameter is the depth of the notch, which should minimise the amount of reflected power. This is achieved when the impedance of the antenna matches that of the feeding line. However, the antenna's impedance diminishes as one moves towards its center because the current's intensity is higher at that point. Hence, it is important to carefully design the depth of the notch.

Following an analytical method, we first estimated the impedance at the bottom edge of the antenna and centered on the horizontal plane (see red bullet in Figure 74). At this point, the impedance is purely resistive, i.e., its reactance is zero, and should be equal to $R_{edge} \approx 341 \Omega$ (we omit the details of the mathematical model to reduce clutter). Then, the optimal depth of the notch can be computed as:

$$h_{\text{notch}} = \frac{L}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{R}{R_{edge}}} \right) \approx 4.9 \text{ mm},$$

where R is the desired impedance (i.e., 50Ω). We attempted to validate this result with the full-wave simulator and found that a 3.5-mm depth, cutting across the patch antenna as shown in Figure 74, maximises performance ($\sim 30\%$ difference with respect to the model). Figure 77 shows with a blue line the amount of power that is reflected, estimated by the simulator and referred to as S_{11} parameter in antenna design. The result shows good performance at 5.5 GHz, the operating frequency of choice. Figure 76 shows the simulated radiation pattern, with minimal backwards propagation. Note that the antenna is not very directive and has an expected gain of 1.5dBi, which is common for this type of low-cost antennas.

Figure 76. Expected radiation pattern of the patch antenna.

Figure 77: S_{11} parameter of two patch antenna samples.

To validate the patch design, we printed a sample antenna with the aforementioned parameters. Using our VNA, we measured the empirical S_{11} and plotted the result with a red line in Figure 77. Perhaps surprisingly, the minimal- S_{11} frequency point is 5.3 GHz instead of the intended 5.5 GHz. After some

research, we realised that the offset stems from an error on the nominal permittivity $\epsilon_r = 4.3$ used in our model/simulations for the PCB substrate. After some iterations with our simulator, we estimated the real permittivity to be $\epsilon_r = 4.66$. In light of this, we changed the operating frequency to $f = 5.3$ GHz.

From Figure 77, we can also estimate that the bandwidth of our approach, i.e., the range of frequencies where the antenna's S_{11} is ≤ -10 dB, is 118MHz (note the black horizontal line). We finally note that, at 5.3 GHz, the S_{11} is -41 dB, which corresponds to a Voltage Standing Wave Ration (VSWR) of 1.018. This means that the power from the feeding line that is reflected back is negligible, which was our goal.

4.6.1.4 Phase shifters

At each cell, a specific phase shift φ is applied by *routing* the RF signal towards a specific delay line, implemented with a microstrip, that reflects the signal back to the patch antenna. To this end, we use a 3-bit RF switch SKY13418-485LF, which has 1 input port (attached to the feeding line), 3 configuration ports (more later), and 8 output ports connected to delay lines of different lengths. Given one configuration (input-output mapping encoded as 3 bits in the configuration ports), the resulting phase shift follows as:

$$\varphi = \frac{360 \cdot 2l \cdot f}{c \cdot v_f},$$

where l denotes the distance travelled from the patch antenna to the end of the delay line (including the switch and the feeding and delay lines), and v_f is the velocity factor of the microstrip material. Note that $2l$ accounts for the round-trip between antenna and delay line. To estimate v_f empirically, we take advantage of the TDR technique used earlier, which also measures the time $d_{\text{microstrip}}$ it takes for a signal to travel through a microstrip of length $l_{\text{microstrip}}$. As shown in Figure 75, $d_{\text{microstrip}} = 1.51$ ns for a line of $l_{\text{microstrip}} = 135$ mm, which is sufficiently long to force the signal to travel at least 2λ and hence enable highly accurate delay estimates. We then calculate $v_f = \frac{v_{\text{microstrip}}}{c} = 0.298 \approx 0.3$, where $v_{\text{microstrip}} = \frac{l_{\text{microstrip}}}{d_{\text{microstrip}}}$ is the velocity of the signal through the microstrip.

Table 23. RF switch output ports, the length of the associated delay lines, and the resulting phase shifts.

Output port	7	6	5	1	3	2	4
φ (deg)	51.42	102.85	154.28	205.71	257.14	308.57	360
l (mm)	1.21	2.42	3.64	4.85	6.08	7.28	8.49

Given v_f and the selected microstrips width derived before (0.75 mm), we can calculate the length of the delay lines corresponding to the phase shifts that need to be encoded into each output port, as indicated in Table 23. Note that port 8 has no associated phase shift. Instead, this port connects with a delay line that ends with a 50Ω -resistor, which prevents the signal to be reflected back. We refer to this configuration as “absorption state”, which enables us to build *virtual* RISs of any size and shape. Alternatively, an energy harvester can be used to feed the MCU and effectively make it self-sustainable. The resulting design is shown in Figure 78.

Figure 78. RF switch and delay lines.

4.6.1.5 Microcontroller Unit (MCU)

An MCU is in charge of parametrising the configuration ports of the RF switch in each unit cell. We have selected the STM32L071V8T6 MCU from STMicroelectronics, which is low cost, high-speed (configuring 100 cells takes < 35 ms), and low energy-consuming (62 mW in high-performing mode). We note that we have not optimised the MCU, which we leave for future work. For instance, we only use the MCU's high-performance (high-consuming) mode, although it provides low-consuming modes too. Exploiting these modes could reduce its energy consumption to the order of μW , which is amenable to energy harvesters.

4.6.1.6 RIS board

The spacing between unit cells (antennas) has to be carefully designed to maximise beamforming gains. Roughly speaking, a small spacing increases the probability of mutual coupling, which decreases the efficiency of each antenna because of surface waves propagation. Conversely, a large spacing leads

to grating lobes. All in all, the inter-cell spacing depends on the maximum steering angle θ_{max} of the main lobe, which is given by $d_{max} = \frac{\lambda}{1 + \sin(\theta_{max})}$. Note that, though $d_{max} = \lambda/2$ maximises the steering angle range of the array, $\theta_{max} = 90^\circ$ is not achievable in practice.

Prior to developing a prototype, we simulated a 10×10 RIS board with a regular 10×10 planar antenna array. In our first set of simulations, each antenna element is fed with equal power from an open-ended transmission line that induces a phase delay that is optimised offline to maximise power towards the selected azimuth and elevation angles. Figure 79 and Figure 80 show the expected radiation pattern of two different configurations that maximise power towards an elevation of $\phi = 0^\circ$ and, respectively, an azimuth of $\theta = \{0^\circ, 80^\circ\}$.

Figure 79. $\theta = 0^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ$.

Figure 80. $\theta = 80^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ$.

On the one hand, we can observe from Figure 79 that the array can achieve a narrow beam pattern, with a Half Power Beamwidth (HPBW) equal to 10.1° , with a gain of 25 dBi in the intended direction, which halves with a 10-degree offset. No back-radiation is expected. On the other hand, Figure 80 shows that a large steering angle of $\theta = 80^\circ$ dissipates half the energy towards the opposite direction and drops the power of the beam to 19.3 dBi.

Note however that the power radiated by a RIS comes from an external source that illuminates the surface. In order to simulate this behavior, we generated a plane wave linearly polarised, and measured the resulting Radar Cross Section (RCS). The RCS estimates how much of the incident power at every point of the surface is scattered back to the receiver. Hence, we expect high RCS values in the direction of the main beam and lower in other directions. This is indeed confirmed in Figure 81 for an incidence angle of 0° and 30° , respectively. In both cases, the RIS is configured to reflect the received signal perpendicularly to the incidence angle of the received signal, i.e., the RIS should maximise power in the same direction of the incidence angle, which is confirmed by both figures with an RCS approximately equal to 12 – 13 dBsm in the intended direction. This highlights the fact that, in real life scenarios, the angle of arrival must be known to the controller to maximise beamforming gains.

Figure 81. RCS of a 10×10 RIS illuminated by a plane wave.

During Y3, our goal is to manufacture 10 boards of 10×10 unit cells each. All the phase and selection buses, which connect each unit cell with an MCU, will be built with microstrips. Unit cells will be deployed in a PCB layout such that the same inter-cell distance can be maintained across co-located boards. The remaining elements (flip-flops, resistors, etc.), shall be standard components assembled on the PCB. Once manufactured, we will assess its performance and the results will be presented in D5.3.

4.7 NI for In-backhaul learning

The DAEMON consortium decided to define a new evaluation area as **Evaluation 8**, which captures the activities we have been performing related to the NI functionality In-backhaul learning (F3, as described in WP2). Since the partners started carrying out various activities within this NI functionality area, we separated them to highlight these specific activities.

Table 24. List of activities for E8.

ID	Name	Evaluation	Tool	Planned KPIs	Collected KPIs	Target TRL	Planned for PoC demo	Progress
A18	In-backhaul learning	E8	D7, D11, D12, T12	K3, K7	K3, K7	2	TBD	50%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Inference fully performed in the user plane, at line rate, via programmable switches								
A28	Efficient backhaul circuit switching	E8	None	K3	K3	3	No	80%
<i>Main innovation:</i> Backhaul circuit switching to increase the speed and efficiency								

4.7.1 In-backhaul learning (A18)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	We measured the in-switch latency in case of normal forwarding and in case <i>Flowrest</i> is applied. We report 107 nanoseconds as the response time of <i>Flowrest</i> , which is the difference between the latency of <i>Flowrest</i> and the latency during normal forwarding.
K7	We report that the Precision and the Recall of <i>Flowrest</i> in an anomaly detection use case, based on D7, where we classify benign and malicious traffic, are respectively 0.99 and 0.98.

As described in Section 5.1 of D3.2 [1], we designed *Flowrest* as a solution to perform the inference phase of Random Forest (RF) models for the classification of individual flows of packets fully into production-grade programmable switches at line rate. *Flowrest* exploits flow-level features, calculated over multiple packets of the same flow, that proved very effective in traffic classification tasks. Besides, our solution takes into account by design the inherent limitations, in terms of available memory and mathematical operations, of network hardware.

We evaluate *Flowrest* in testbed T12, described in Section 3.1.12 of D5.1 [3], using off-the-shelf Tofino switches. We run experiments to evaluate our solution's classification performance and memory scalability in four use cases with different complexity. We compose the four use cases using three datasets, namely D7, D11 and D12, respectively described in Sections 3.3.7, 3.3.11 and 3.3.12 of D5.1 [3]. The use cases vary mainly in the number of classes the inference targets, representing an increasing complexity from two to 26 classes. We also measure the latency experienced by the packets traversing the switch to evaluate the response time of our solution targeting KPI K3.

In the literature, no flow-level solution exists that we can use as a term for comparison. Solutions like *pForest* [43] have no hardware implementation and can run in emulation environments only. For this reason, we compare *Flowrest* with a packet-level benchmark based on *Planter* [44] [45]. As *Flowrest* itself exploits *Planter*'s RF mapping (described in detail in Section 5.1.3.2 of D3.2 [1]) and *Planter*'s authors provide no code for their solution, we implemented the benchmark by removing from *Flowrest* the flow management logic. The following three subsections show the performance and memory evaluation results and the latency measurements.

4.7.1.1 Classification performance

Figure 82 summarizes the performance of *Flowrest* and the packet-level benchmark. We provide a comparison between the two solutions in terms of F1-score, Precision and Recall in plots (a), (b) and (c), respectively, across the four use cases, ordered by their number of classes in abscissa. *Flowrest* shows a good F1-score performance, which varies from 0.99 in the binary case to 0.86 when 26 classes are considered. The packet-level benchmark F1-score is close to *Flowrest* in the binary task but drops to 0.62 in the most complex use case. The packet-level benchmark does not scale well with the number of categories, as the gain of *Flowrest* varies from just 2% to 39%. We observe similar trends in the plots of

Precision and Recall, remarking that the flow-level classification seems to help improve, especially the Recall performance. In plot (d), we show a breakdown of the F1 score per class in the most complex use case with 26 categories instead. Flowrest yields an F1 score above 0.85 in 9 classes, with another six classes above 0.50. While the other classes have F1 scores below 0.50, these classes do not have a good representation in the dataset; instead, the performance is especially good for well-represented classes, as proven by the high aggregate F1-score in (a). When comparing our solution to the packet-level approach, Flowrest consistently outperforms the benchmark apart from a couple of outliers.

Figure 82. Flowrest vs benchmark evaluation across the use cases in terms of (a) F1-score, (b) Precision and (c) Recall; (d) shows a break-down of the F1-score per class.

Finally, we highlight that the first use case is an anomaly detection use case based on dataset D7, where we classify traffic as benign or malicious. In this particular use case, the Precision and Recall scores of Flowrest are respectively 0.99 and 0.98. We use these two results to meet KPI K7.

4.7.1.2 Memory scalability

Figure 83. Flowrest vs benchmark memory usage comparison.

Since the flow-level framework is much more structured than the minimum support needed for packet-level inference, it needs more resources for the programmable switch. Figure 83.(a) shows the resource usage of Flowrest and the benchmark compared to the total average resources used by the baseline P4 program for core L2/L3 switching functions, i.e., switch.p4. Flowrest consumes 15% to 29% of such program, which is a low and very reasonable figure but is still sensibly higher than in a per-packet approach where the same values range from 3% to 11%. However, plot (b) shows that the absolute usage difference is almost constant, and the relative consumption decreases. This result points out a stable difference between the two solutions, which is accountable to the flow management logic of Flowrest.

Nevertheless, the cost of such logic is not affected by the dimensionality of the task. This result is corroborated by plot (d), which shows an almost fixed offset in the consumption of resources like Static Random Access Memory (SRAM), which is used to store flow data, and Very Long Instruction Word (VLIW) that allocates arithmetic instructions applied to flow-level features. Finally, in plot (d), we remark that Flowrest does not entail any added cost in terms of usage of expensive and scarce resources such as PHV and TCAM.

4.7.1.3 In-switch latency

We measure the latency experienced by the packets traversing the switch in three different scenarios:

- i) when no inference is performed, and the switch is just forwarding normally the packets;
- ii) when packet-level inference is performed;
- iii) when Flowrest is applied.

We measure the latency by using timestamps available in the programmable pipeline of the switch. In particular, we use the timestamp assigned when the packet enters the switch's ingress port and a timestamp set when the packet reaches the egress parser. We calculate latency as the difference between the latter and the former. We clarify that there is no logic in the switch's egress pipeline, so the calculated latency well represents the time it takes the packet to traverse the switch. Table 25 summarizes the results of the experiments and shows that in-switch latency has the same order of

magnitude in all cases. In particular, we observe that the difference between Flowrest's latency and the no inference case latency is just 108 nanoseconds. We claim such a latency as the response time of Flowrest to be used to meet KPI K3.

Table 25. In-switch latency comparison.

Scenario	Measured latency [nanoseconds]
No Inference	284
Packet-level inference	318
Flowrest	392

4.7.2 Efficient backhaul circuit switching (A28)

Collected KPI	Justification
K3	We demonstrate how different traffic matrices affect the performance of a circuit switch in terms of throughput, configurations computation time, and number of configurations.

In this activity, we present the numerical evaluation of Birkhoff+, a robust, fast and efficient algorithm proposed in Section 5.2 of Deliverable 3.2 [1] to address the problem of backhaul circuit switching. The experiments are conducted to showcase the advantages of the proposed algorithm in terms of (i) throughput, (ii) computation time, and (iii) the number of configurations. The algorithm's performance is compared with other state-of-the-art algorithms, namely Birkhoff, FW, FCFW, Solstice, and Eclipse. We generate sparse traffic matrices by sampling permutations uniformly at random with 12 flows; 3 large, carrying 70% of the load, and 9 small, carrying the remaining 30%. We assume that traffic matrices are doubly stochastic, and the results presented are the average of 50 realizations.

4.7.2.1 Main performance evaluation results

In Figure 84.a, we notice that Solstice, Birkhoff+, and Birkhoff+(10) have superior sparsity performance compared to the rest of the algorithms, with Birkhoff+(10) outperforming the rest for $\epsilon < 0.1$. From Figure 84.b, which depicts the decomposition error vs the decomposition time, it is evident that Birkhoff+ is the fastest, followed by Birkhoff+(10).

Figure 84. Decomposition error (ϵ) depending on (a) the number of permutations and (b) time.

As a next step in the evaluation procedure, we consider a circuit switch with $n = 100$ ports to calculate the switching configurations. In the experiments that follow, the traffic matrix is associated with a time window W , in a way that the total time spent on transmitting and reconfiguring does not exceed that threshold. It is crucial to note that (i) Birkhoff, (ii) FW, and (iii) FCFW are not considered in the plots below because they have either poor performance or speed (see Figure 84).

In Figure 85, we delineate the algorithms' performance in terms of throughput (Figure 85.a), running time (Figure 85.b), and the number of configurations depending on the ratio δ/W , i.e., the impact of the reconfiguration delay proportionally to the time window duration (Figure 85.c). From Figure 85.a, Birkhoff+(10) outperforms the other algorithms in terms of throughput by 7% for $\delta/W = 10^{-2}$, while Birkhoff+'s throughput is almost equal to Eclipse's and Solstice's. As far as the time for computing the switching configurations, Solstice and Eclipse are slower than Birkhoff+ and Birkhoff+(10) by order of magnitude (see Figure 85.b), and Birkhoff+(10) can acquire decompositions with half of the configurations compared to other algorithms when $\epsilon = 10^{-4}$ (see Figure 85.c).

In Figure 86, we assess the algorithms' performance based on the skewness and sparsity of the demand matrix for $\delta/W = 10^{-2}$. To achieve this, we vary the fraction of the load carried by the small flows, and

we notice that (i) Birkhoff+(10) performs better than the rest of the algorithms, and (ii) for various demand matrices, Birkhoff+, Solstice, and Eclipse have about identical performance.

Figure 85. Circuit switch performance depending on δ/W .

Figure 86. Circuit switch performance depending on the load carried by the small flows.

Figure 87 displays the performance of circuit switching with respect to the number of permutations needed to generate the traffic matrix. More specifically, from Figure 87.a, it can be seen that the throughput of all algorithms decreases as the demand matrix becomes denser. At the same time, from Figure 87.b, it is visible that the running time of Birkhoff+(10) is not increasing significantly with denser or sparser traffic matrices. Moreover, from Figure 87.c, it can be observed that the number of switching configurations increases with the density of the traffic matrix for all algorithms.

Figure 87. Circuit switch performance depending on the number of permutation matrices used to generate the traffic matrix.

4.7.2.2 Conclusions

In this activity, we evaluated the performance of the proposed algorithm Birkhoff+. We showed that it is superior to state-of-the-art algorithms in terms of throughput, running time, and the number of switching configurations.

5 DAEMON PoC demonstrations

DAEMON aims at growing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the NI technologies corresponding to the NI functionality areas that we identified. Section 4 provided an overview of the TRL for each activity within the evaluation areas that we address. Based on these, in Table 26 we summarize the TRL level corresponding to each NI functionality (and its corresponding evaluation). We mention that for two different NI functionalities (namely, F2 and F8), we plan to expand our evaluations into pilots with industrial partners.

Table 26. TRL status for each DAEMON NI functionality.

NI Functionality	Evaluation	TRL	Demo Status
F1	E7: NI to configure a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	TRL3	Not Planned (PoC only)
F2	E4: NI for Edge orchestration	TRL4 □ TRL5	Executed (Others Planned)
F3	E8: NI for in-backhaul learning	TRL3	Planned
F4	E1: NI for sustainable virtualised Radio Access Network	TRL4	Executed (Others planned)
F5	E2: NI for VNF placement and control	TRL3	Executed
F6	E6: NI for capacity forecasting and self-learning	TRL3	Not Planned (PoC only)
F7			
F8	E3: NI for real-time anomaly detection	TRL4	Executed
	E5: NI for automated anomaly response	TRL5	Planned

The 30 activities corresponding to the eight evaluations we have presented in the previous section allowed us to quantify the nine KPIs that DAEMON aims to capture. The KPI collection efforts relied on PoC (proof of concept) evaluations that we have performed (or are planning to perform) for each of the eight evaluation areas.

In this section, we report which of these PoC efforts also maps to a demonstration activity. Over Y1 and Y2 of the project, we have already executed four different demonstrations, each corresponding to a different evaluation area, i.e., E1, E2, E3 and E4). **We further report on the executed demos in Section 5.1.**

We plan three additional PoC demonstrations, each corresponding to three additional evaluations (namely, E7, E8 and E5). **We further report on the planned demos in Section 5.2.**

Aside from the per-evaluation PoC demonstration, we also report on the DAEMON-wide demonstration activities. Namely, we report on our plans to showcase two project-wide activities: (i) **Integrated NI functionalities demo**; and (ii) **DAEMON architecture demo**. The goal of these two demonstration activities is to showcase the manner in which the NI functionalities we propose would integrate natively within the next-generation mobile network architecture.

5.1 Executed Demonstrations

5.1.1 Evaluation E1: Reliable Distributed Unit for Virtualization

We have developed an experimental demonstrator to showcase our work in the context of Activity 1.

In this demonstration, we set up a testbed comprised of a server with a pool of 5x Intel Xeon x86 cores @1.9GHz. We first deploy a full-fledged 3GPP-compliant eNB implemented with srsRAN, which we refer to as "DU under Test (DuT)" and connect a UE sending and receiving as much traffic as possible from the eNB. To monitor performance metrics, we implemented the dashboard shown in Figure 88 (top part, indicated DU under Test metrics). The top section of the dashboard depicts the downlink throughput, the uplink throughput and the 99th percentile of the TTI processing latency in the wireless link.

To demonstrate the problem of vanilla DU pipelines when sharing a computing platform, during the demonstration we sequentially add "Competing DUs (cDUs)" implemented with Intel FlexRAN. Given a sufficiently large competing workload, the network throughput of the DU under Test degrades substantially, as shown for 6 cDUs in Figure 88. As shown in the dashboard, the reason behind such throughput loss is that the TTI latency frequently exceeds a deadline represented in red in the dashboard. This problem was formally presented in D5.1.

Figure 88. The problem when multiple DUs share the same computing platform.

To address this problem, we designed and developed Nuberu, as introduced in Section 4.1.1 and demonstrated this technology in the same testbed and scenarios as before. A snapshot of the dashboard when using Nuberu is depicted in Figure 89. As shown by the figure, during the demonstration, we reached up to 15 Competing DUs without compromising network throughput in the DU under Test. The key reason behind this is that Nuberu preserves TTI latencies below the deadline (represented with a red line), demonstrating in this way the ability of Nuberu to operate in shared computing platforms.

Figure 89. Nuberu - A DU design that is resilient to computing fluctuations in shared computing platforms.

5.1.2 Evaluation E2: Energy-driven RAN orchestration

This experimental demonstrator showcases our work in the context of Activity A4.

We set up a testbed composed of two general-purpose computing platforms with two attached SDRs (USRP B210). A full-fledged virtualized Base Station (vBS) and a UE are deployed into a small computer (PC). We measure the power consumption of the vBS using an external digital power meter (GW-Instek GPM-8213). The power meter provides real time measurements that can be obtained via an SCPI interface.

We track the evolution of the system on the dashboard shown in Figure 90. At the top, we present the uplink and downlink configuration policies enforced by the learning algorithm. These configuration policies change in real time in the live demo at every time interval, which is 5 seconds in this demonstration. On the left, we show the real power consumption of the virtualized base station with the red area. In green, we set a power consumption limit. On the right, we show the network load dynamics in yellow and the achieved network throughput in green. Finally, at the bottom, we show the system's reward over time.

Figure 90. Demonstration of the energy-driven vRAN orchestrator NI.

We emulate daily network load patterns collected from a real base station in Germany for 5 days. We can observe these daily load patterns in yellow on the uplink and downlink throughput plots (right dashboard). For the sake of convenience, 5 minutes are represented as 5 seconds in the demonstration dashboard. We change the power budget of the base station to evaluate how our algorithm adapts.

During the first day, the power budget is set to a high value. As the algorithm has no prior knowledge of the system, some random exploration actions are selected. After a few iterations, the algorithm selects high-performance actions, maximizing uplink and downlink throughput. Then, the power budget is progressively reduced at the beginning of each day. Depending on the power budget, some configurations are removed from the safe set of configurations (in terms of power consumption). This penalizes downlink throughput first because uplink processing is power compute-intensive and hence more power-hungry. During the last day, the power budget is very limited, and the algorithm is forced to sacrifice both uplink and downlink throughput substantially, which explain the loss in reward during peak load periods. In this way, we demonstrate the integration of Bayesian online learning algorithm for energy-driven RAN orchestration.

5.1.3 Evaluation E3: FL Anomaly Detection

The solution of Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection is presented in detail in Section 4.3.1 of the current document (Activity 9). In order to stress the importance of the proposed solution, this approach is compared to the legacy approaches of centralized and distributed anomaly detection. Figure 91 illustrates the results of the comparison.

Figure 91. Comparison between Centralised, Distributed and Federated Learning Anomaly Detection.

In addition, we developed and demonstrated a prototype in order to showcase the main functionalities of the proposed solution and to demonstrate their main innovations. The developed components are illustrated in Figure 92 and includes: a) the development of FL Controller and FL Client back-ends using Python; b) the development of FL Controller and FL Client front-ends using React; and c) the deployment of all components as Docker containers into the infrastructure. In the same figure, the sequence of actions for the realisation of the demo script are also presented and explained. In detail, each FL Client collects KPIs (CPU, Memory, Disk utilisation) and applies DBSCAN on its latest batch of data. Each FL Client generates each own local DBSCAN model. Then, all FL Clients forward the local model to the FL Controller. The FL Controller, analyses all the received models and generates a global model. This global model is further broadcasted to all FL Clients. Finally, each FL Client updates their own local model based on the received global model.

Figure 92. Demonstration of Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection solution.

5.1.4 Evaluation E4: Edge Orchestration

In Section 3.1 of D3.2 [1], we presented the detailed overview of the AI-enhanced edge orchestration solution, detailing both the AI-enhanced NFV MANO framework and the MAESTRO algorithm that is used for the purpose of proactively triggering the edge service relocation in order to maintain the required levels of service quality.

For the purpose of experimentation and the demo, our NFV MANO framework is deployed on the Smart Highway testbed (Antwerp, Belgium), and the Virtual Wall testbed (Ghent, Belgium). It consists of two layers, cloud and edge. In the edge, we deploy Kubernetes clusters and Eclipse Zenoh on the Roadside Units (RSUs) (Figure 93), which perform autonomous MANO operations upon the deployed edge services. The edge service used in the experimentation and demo activities is a containerized service aimed at supporting emergency situations on the highways, thereby distributing notifications to the affected vehicles and informing them about the emergency vehicle that needs to be pass through in an unhindered manner.

In the demo, we consider each RSU as an edge domain that consists of one or multiple edge nodes (i.e., MEC hosts), and as such, it is managed by one edge orchestrator. This orchestrator follows the principles defined by ETSI NFV MANO framework and is in charge of the lifecycle management (e.g., instantiation, scaling, termination) of all edge services (including V2X ones). In parallel, the cloud orchestrator oversees the global system optimization, and it makes less granular decisions depending on the e.g., locations and density of vehicles on the roads for our particular real-life use case.

In the demo, we deployed two types of algorithms that are working centrally (in the centralized orchestrator), collecting data from the distributed RSUs (Figure 94), and making the decision whether edge service needs to be relocated or not.

Figure 93. Distributed data collection in the Smart Highway demo setup.

Figure 94. Centralized orchestrator collecting data from RSUs.

As described in Section 4.4.2, these two algorithms are: (1) the rule-based algorithm that makes decision to relocate services based on the current CPU load on the source edge computing node, and (2) MAESTRO, that proactively performs the selection of a new target node to which the observed edge V2X service should be relocated in order to maintain/achieve the required service response time. It works in an automated and intelligent way thanks to the MCDM mechanism that takes into account various metrics, such as CPU, memory, and power utilization (more details in Section 4.4.2, and D3.2), as well as the predicted average response time for a vehicle client. The prediction is based on the SVR model (more details in Section 4.4.2, and D3.2) that is trained at the edge orchestrator level. The details of MAESTRO algorithm are presented in D3.2, and in Section 4.4.2 we just briefly refer to the results achieved.

In Figure 95, we visualize the interaction between the vehicle and the edge service via Eclipse zenoh, thereby subscribing to the topic where edge service publishes alarms and notifications about relocation and change of service endpoint. During the demo, we collected different types of measurements, as explained above, thus Figure 96 is showing five panels in Grafana that are displaying the real-time data collected from the edge infrastructure (CPU, Power, and RAM usage from different Roadside units, i.e., edge computing nodes) via Eclipse Zenoh. The same data is consumed by orchestrators to make decisions on proactive relocation. Finally, Figure 97 is illustrating a snapshot of the demo, where we show the decisions made by the aforementioned ML-based algorithm (i.e., MAESTRO), and simple rule-based algorithm. As both algorithms produced the same output: RSU5 selected for the edge service deployment, the green dot is showing the location of the RSU5 to which the vehicle is currently connected. During the demo, we have used the testbed vehicle (Onboard unit inside the vehicle) to perform testing and reconnecting from one edge service to the other.

Figure 95. Enforcing relocation decisions on the edge orchestrators for service deployment.

Figure 96. Grafana overview of metrics collected in real-time via Eclipse Zenoh.

Figure 97. Showcasing the decision to which edge service (deployed on the RSU) vehicle should connect (RSU5 selected, green).

5.2 Planned Demonstrations

5.2.1 Planned Demos for PoC/Pilots per Evaluation Category

Evaluation with Planned PoC/Pilot Demo	Description	Tools/Means
E1	We plan a demonstration of activity A2 during Year 3. This will showcase a solution we are developing within WP3 to optimize cost and energy efficiency in an O-RAN cloud platform with heterogeneous computing resources shared by multiple 5G Distributed Units (DUs).	Experimental PoC on testbed (T1)
E2	We plan to demonstrate the work of the HADES approach (activity A7) using a case scenario on augmented reality. Specifically, we use the Planetarium System presented in Section 4.2.4.1.	Experimental PoC on testbed (T13)
E3	We plan a demonstration of the evaluation we performed within activity A19 . This will showcase the anomaly detection pipeline we designed and tested in collaboration with Telefonica's IoT Managed Connectivity Platform. Our evaluation relies on a large-scale dataset that we collect from the IoT platform, comprising of a sample per-device of mobility signaling traffic. The NI functionality we developed within A19 has a TRL 5 based on the pilot we carried out with Telefonica's IoT Platform.	Data-driven (D8)
E4	We plan to demonstrate the work of EnergyEdgeCloudSim (activity A15) using the Shanghai data set. EnergyEdgeCloud is an extension of EdgeCloudSim, an open-source tool that provides a simulation environment specific to Edge Computing. Concretely, we have modified this simulator to consider the	Data-Driven (D15)

	energy consumption during the simulation and to return the amount of energy consumed by each edge device at the end of the simulation using the energy consumption.	
E8	We plan to demonstrate In-backhaul learning (activity A18) with an experimental PoC that exploits testbed T12. The demonstration aims at: i) showing that our solution Flowrest outperforms a packet-level benchmark in terms of classification score (i.e, F1-score, Precision, Recall); ii) the inference is performed at line-rate. To achieve this, we evaluate our solution with a multi-class traffic classification use case and run three experiments: i) we perform normal forwarding to measure the in-switch latency of a legacy switch; ii) we perform packet-level classification by running a benchmark solution to measure both the classification performance and the in-switch latency; iii) we apply our solution Flowrest and measure both the classification performance and the in-switch latency. We summarize and show in a dashboard the results of the experiments.	Experimental Demo on testbed T12.
NIP Architecture	In testbeds T4 and T8 the NIP architecture (described in WP2) will be deployed and a set of solutions (two solutions as a first step) will be realised following the NIP approach. In order to showcase the NIP approach and the solutions we will demonstrate a Smart-Highway scenario in which anomalies (QoS degradations in vehicular services) are detected in a real time manner and actions in edge orchestrators are triggered as a response to them. A first version of the NIP demo is already deployed and it is described in detail in the next section (5.2.2).	Experimental Demo on Testbed (T4, T8)

Figure 98. Prototype demonstrating NIS/NIF/NIF-C pipeline generation, deployment and monitoring.

5.2.2 NIP Architecture Demo

This paragraph reports the first version of the NIP architecture demo. In detail, the basic Network Intelligent (NI) architecture described in detail in D2.2 [27] is realized as a prototype using the Kubernetes [46] as the main deployment environment. In addition, the Kubeflow tool [47] is used as the main tool for performing MLOps operations and as the baseline for developing some of the NI Orchestration functionalities. In addition, the selected functionalities of the NI Orchestrator are developed from scratch. The Eclipse Zenoh framework [48] is used for data flow programming among the NIF-C and for metric collection and aggregation.

In detail, and in relation with the NI architecture described in D2.2 [27], Kubernetes serves as the main deployment environment taking care of the MANO functionalities on top a virtualized infrastructure. The Kubeflow deployment is realized as a Kubeflow cluster with one controller and 3 worker nodes, in which the NIF-C are deployed as pods. The management of NIF-Cs is carried out by the NIF component manager through the Kubernetes API. As described in D2.2 [27], a set of interconnected NIF-Cs following

the N-MAPE-K representation form a NIF. This is realized by implementing a pipeline of pods managed by the NIF Manager utilizing the Kubeflow Pipelines SDK. This is illustrated in Figure 98. The generated pipeline of NIF-Cs is first defined in python, then translated in YAML (Step 1 in Figure 98), and by using the developed service which utilize the Kubeflow pipeline service (Step 2), it finally deployed in Kubernetes (both the pods and the services that ensure the pods' connectivity)(Step 3). Then, the whole pipeline can be monitored during openarion time (Step 4). In the same fashion, the NI Orchestrator manages the NISs (using Kubeflow) in a higher hierarchical level.

A set of NI Orchestrator functionalities including: a) NIS composition; b) NIS lifecycle management; c) NIS workflow configuration; d) NIS selection; and e) Monitoring; are realized by building on the functionalities already available in the Kubeflow framework. The developed NI Orchestration monitoring service provides monitoring of: a) NIF-C/NIF/NIS deployment status; b) NIF/NIS pipeline progress; c) MLOps progress; d) resource utilization; and e) performance KPIs. The rest of the functionalities are planned to be developed as separate modules integrated with the final solution.

The MLOps operations responsible for the model retrain are realized as ML pipelines in the Kubeflow environment. The NIF/NIS catalog is realized as a Docker repository linked to the Kubernetes environment.

Finally, it is important to stress that the NIF-C taxonomy (e.g., analysis, planning), as well as the adopted communication paradigm (Eclipse zenoh) is followed by the development of the different components and the context it is exposed both in the NIF/NIS Catalogs (as Dockers with prebuild libraries) and NIF/NIS creation process (different types with preconfigured attributes). This context is further used by the solution for executing tasks related with application of policies and conflict resolution.

6 Conclusion and outlook

In this document, we presented an update on the results of the work carried out in WP5 on the evaluation of the performance, sustainability and reliability of the 30 NI-solutions we developed across WP3 and WP4 of the DAEMON project. We validated such solutions against the 9 target KPIs of the project, which have been measured and assessed by a comprehensive set of 8 evaluations involving technical tools such as experimental testbeds, simulators or emulators, and datasets. These evaluations validate all the NI functionalities we defined in WP2.

We have re-organized our evaluations by grouping together E3 and E5, both dealing with automated anomaly detection and response. Furthermore, we introduced a new evaluation E8 that tackles NI solutions for in-backhaul learning.

Overall, each of the 30 NI-solutions integrate proof-of-concept activities that enabled us to collect the corresponding KPIs per activity. Furthermore, for two NI-solutions we plan to evolve these PoC into pilots with commercial units.

We evaluate the technical readiness level of each NI functionality area by reporting our results and, furthermore, preparing demonstrations of the PoC activities.

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